

**Defining and modelling the microbiome in chronic
obstructive pulmonary disease**

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Abstract

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), a chronic and degenerative lung disease, is the third leading cause of death worldwide, claiming the lives of approximately 6.1 million people annually. Progression of COPD is reliant on several factors from host genetics to lifestyle choices. One factor that drives disease progression, which has received increasing amounts of attention in the past decade, is the lung microbiome. However, what is still unclear is the mechanisms by which this occurs. COPD patients are chronically colonised by bacterial pathogens and experience frequent respiratory infections as a result of compromised clearance mechanisms. All the above evidence points towards the presence of biofilms within the COPD lung.

Firstly, using bioinformatic approaches the literature surrounding the area of the microbiome in COPD was analysed to identify past, current and potential future trends as well as any gaps in current knowledge of the microbiome in COPD. Further work aimed to clarify the role of the microbiome in COPD and address current limitations that were identified in the bioinformatic-based literature search. While identifying a bias towards certain bacteria, no other clear trends were observed. In contrast to cystic fibrosis, which showed evidence of functional analysis, the COPD microbiome literature showed no evidence of this and therefore revealed what is lacking in our understanding of the COPD microbiome and therefore identified a potential future trend.

Secondly, using *in silico* approaches, a meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in health and COPD was performed. Throughout the COPD microbiome literature, there are some conflicting findings surrounding aspects such as bacterial diversity and the presence or absence of certain organisms. Therefore, the following analyses aimed to address this. This was achieved through the secondary analysis of microbiome sequencing data that had been deposited into online repositories. This analysis identified that study-specific experimental design features were behind the conflicting findings in the literature, indicating that less study-to-study variation in sample collection and processing methods would improve our ability to properly synthesise results in meta-analyses such as this one. No significant differences were observed in the diversity of the healthy and COPD lung microbiomes and key members of the COPD microbiome were identified as bacteria associated with the oropharynx such as *Streptococcus*, *Haemophilus*, *Moraxella*,

Abstract

Prevotella, *Staphylococcus* and *Porphyromonas*. Next, to address some of the limitations in the literature surrounding the functionality of the microbiome, enriched metabolic pathways of the COPD microbiome were identified. This analysis revealed an enrichment of bacterial virulence associated pathways, indicating the mechanisms by which the microbiome can drive inflammation in COPD.

Next, a multi-species biofilm model, containing bacteria and fungi, was developed and characterised by assessing its antimicrobial susceptibilities and immunogenicity. This biofilm model contained bacteria identified within the meta-analysis in the previous chapter. Characterisation of this model revealed *Candida albicans* as a key member of the biofilm which promoted bacterial growth by acting as a substrate for the bacteria to bind. These interactions lead to multi-species biofilms being highly tolerant to antimicrobial therapies that are commonly used in COPD therapy. Even in combination, antifungals and antibiotics were not sufficient to kill or remove the biofilm. Supernatants from these biofilms also displayed an ability to elicit an immune response from epithelial cells. This was then increased following antimicrobial treatment. These findings point towards, oropharyngeal bacteria interacting with fungi in the respiratory tract, promoting antimicrobial tolerance and driving inflammation.

Lastly, the effects of bacteria on *C. albicans* at a transcriptional level were investigated with the intentions of identifying potential mechanisms behind the increased antimicrobial tolerance and immunogenicity observed in the previous chapter. Bacteria were found to increase fungal virulence within a biofilm environment and therefore other potential mechanisms by which the COPD microbiome drives lung inflammation were identified. Future studies should continue to address current limitations in the literature, in particular the functionality of the COPD microbiome and developing ways in which it can be accurately studied *in vitro*.

Contents

Abstract.....	i
Contents.....	iii
Tables.....	vii
Figures.....	viii
Authors declaration.....	xi
List of publications.....	xii
Acknowledgements.....	xiii
List of appendices.....	xv
Abbreviations.....	xvi
1 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.....	3
1.1.1 Clinical presentations of COPD.....	3
1.1.2 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease diagnosis.....	6
1.1.3 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease epidemiology.....	7
1.1.4 Immunology and the immune response.....	9
1.1.5 Therapeutics in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.....	11
1.2 Microbiology of the lungs.....	14
1.2.1 The microbiome of the healthy lungs.....	15
1.2.2 The mycobiome of the healthy lung.....	15
1.2.3 The lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.....	16
1.2.4 The mycobiome of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.....	17
1.3 Biofilms.....	18
1.3.1 Fungal biofilms.....	19
1.3.2 Interkingdom biofilms.....	22
1.3.3 Biofilms in the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease lung.....	25
1.4 Oral-lung axis.....	29
1.5 OMICs in health and disease.....	31
1.5.1 Illumina sequencing.....	32
1.5.2 Microbiome sequencing.....	32
1.5.3 Transcriptomics.....	33
1.6 Summary and aims.....	34
2 Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature.....	35
2.1 Introduction.....	36
2.2 Aims and hypothesis.....	38
2.3 Methods.....	39

Contents

2.3.1	Data collection.....	39
2.3.2	Bibliometric analysis.....	39
2.3.3	pyTag annotation.....	40
2.3.4	Statistical analysis.....	40
2.4	Results.....	42
2.4.1	Initial search.....	42
2.4.2	Annual growth rates.....	42
2.4.3	Contribution to the field by country.....	43
2.4.4	Identifying the top contributing authors.....	45
2.4.5	Identifying literature trends by article keywords.....	47
2.4.6	Keyword analysis using pyTag.....	50
2.4.7	‘Organism’ related keyword quantification.....	52
2.4.8	‘Organism’ related terms whose frequency differed between disease groups.....	53
2.4.9	Temporal changes in ‘organism’ ontology terms.....	54
2.4.10	Quantification of ontology terms related to biological processes.....	55
2.4.11	‘Biological process’ related terms that can differentiate disease groups.....	56
2.4.12	Temporal changes in ‘biological process’ ontological terms.....	57
2.5	Discussion.....	58
2.6	Key findings:.....	61
3	Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.....	62
3.1	Introduction.....	63
3.2	Aims and Hypotheses.....	65
3.3	Materials and methods.....	67
3.3.1	Search criteria and study collection.....	67
3.3.2	Study inclusion and exclusion criteria.....	68
3.3.3	Data retrieval and processing.....	68
3.3.4	Microbiome diversity and composition analyses.....	69
3.3.5	Random forest classifiers and linear discriminant analysis.....	70
3.3.6	Statistical analysis.....	70
3.4	Results.....	71
3.4.1	Study collection and characteristics.....	71
3.4.2	Microbial diversity within the COPD microbiome.....	78
3.4.3	Community composition in the COPD lung.....	81
3.4.4	The lung microbiome as a predictor of COPD.....	84
3.4.5	Functional annotation of the COPD microbiome.....	87
3.5	Discussion.....	90
3.6	Key Findings.....	93

Contents

4	Developing an informed biofilm model	94
4.1	Introduction	95
4.2	Aims and hypotheses	97
4.3	Materials and methods	98
4.3.1	Microbial storage and standardisation	98
4.3.2	Media preparation	98
4.3.3	Biofilm growth and analysis	98
4.3.4	DNA extraction and purification	99
4.3.5	Biofilm composition analysis	99
4.3.6	Visualisation of inter-kingdom biofilm interactions	100
4.3.7	Visualising multi-species biofilms	101
4.3.8	Antimicrobial compounds	101
4.3.9	Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of single and multi-species communities 101	
4.3.10	Oral epithelial cells exposed to biofilm supernatants	102
4.3.11	Gene expression in epithelial cells	102
4.3.12	Epithelial cell protein release	103
4.3.13	Immunofluorescence	104
4.3.14	Statistical analysis	104
4.4	Results	105
4.4.1	Multi-species biofilm growth	105
4.4.2	Bacteria bind to <i>Candida albicans</i> hyphae with high affinities	106
4.4.3	Visualisation of direct fungal-bacterial interactions in a mature biofilm	108
4.4.4	Single and multi-species biofilms tolerate antimicrobial challenge	109
4.4.5	Biofilm composition changes with antimicrobial challenge	112
4.4.6	Immunogenicity of multi-species biofilms	114
4.5	Discussion	118
4.5.1	Key findings	121
5	Modulation of the <i>Candida albicans</i> transcriptome by <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	122
5.1	Introduction	123
5.2	Aims and hypotheses	126
5.3	Materials and methods	127
5.3.1	Microbial storage and standardisation	127
5.3.2	Media preparation	127
5.3.3	Biofilm growth and analysis	127
5.3.4	DNA extraction and purification	128
5.3.5	Biofilm composition analysis	129

Contents

5.3.6	Visualisation of inter-kingdom biofilm interactions	129
5.3.7	RNA extraction and sequencing.....	130
5.3.8	Statistical analysis.....	132
5.4	Results	133
5.4.1	<i>Candida albicans</i> and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> form robust dual-species biofilms	133
5.4.2	<i>Candida albicans</i> promotes the growth of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	134
5.4.3	Ecel1 does not influence staphylococcal binding to <i>Candida albicans</i>	137
5.4.4	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> is responsible for modulating the <i>Candida albicans</i> transcriptome in mature biofilms.....	139
5.4.5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> creates a more virulent fungal genotype in mature dual-species biofilms	143
5.5	Discussion.....	149
5.6	Key findings	153
6	General Discussion	154
6.1	Introduction	155
6.2	Identifying current and future trends in COPD microbiome research.....	155
6.3	Defining the microbiome in COPD and investigating its functionality	156
6.4	Antimicrobial therapies in COPD cannot remove multi-species consortia.....	157
6.5	Fungi aid in driving inflammation in the COPD lung.....	158
6.6	Future work.....	160
6.7	Concluding remarks.....	160
	References	162

Tables

Table 1.1: GOLD disease classification and diagnosis based on FEV1/FVC ratio	6
Table 2.1: Search terms used to identify articles from the PubMed and Clarivate Analytics Web of Science™ databases.	42
Table 3.1: Keyword searches performed to identify lung microbiome studies focusing on COPD and healthy lung.	67
Table 3.2: Shortlisted study characteristics	73
Table 3.3: Area under the curve produced by each set of random forest test data	85
Table 4.1: Primers used to identify biofilm organisms and measure gene expression	100
Table 4.2: Biofilms display decreased susceptibility to antimicrobials compared to planktonic counterparts	110
Table 5.1: Species specific primers used to identify <i>C. albicans</i> and <i>S. aureus</i> .	129
Table 5.2: Percentage of hyphae in each subcategory of bacterial binding	137

Figures

Figure 1.1: Healthy and diseased lung, bronchi and alveoli.	5
Figure 1.2: Geographical heatmap of COPD prevalence in Europe.	9
Figure 1.3: The life cycle of biofilm cells.	19
Figure 1.4: Biofilm publications per year.	20
Figure 1.5: Nutrient gradients within biofilms.	26
Figure 1.6: Mechanisms by which biofilms interact with the host and antibiotics in COPD.	28
Figure 1.7: The human respiratory tract.	30
Figure 2.1: Bibliometric analysis pipeline by the Bibliometrix web application.	40
Figure 2.2: Comprehensive ontology-based analysis pipeline using pyTag software.	41
Figure 2.3: Number of research articles per year.	43
Figure 2.4: Scientific contribution per country.	44
Figure 2.5: Most productive authors over time.	46
Figure 2.6: Most frequent key words in lung microbiome research in COPD, CF and asthma.	49
Figure 2.7: NMDS scaling reveals clustering of recent lung microbiome studies.	51
Figure 2.8: Most commonly used 'organism' ontology terms.	52
Figure 2.9: Most commonly used 'biological process' ontology terms.	55
Figure 2.10: Comparison of the use of "organism" ontology terms between disease groups.	53
Figure 2.11: Comparison of the use of "biological process" ontology terms between disease groups.	56
Figure 2.12: Temporal changes in the use of 'organism' ontology terms.	54
Figure 2.13: Temporal changes in the use of 'biological process' ontology terms.	57
Figure 3.1: Graphical abstract of meta-analysis pipeline.	66
Figure 3.2: Study acquisition pipeline.	71
Figure 3.3: Average number of reads per sample per study.	72
Figure 3.4: Study characteristics.	77
Figure 3.5: Principle co-ordinate analysis of microbiome samples by disease status and study.	78
Figure 3.6: Alpha-diversity of the healthy and COPD lung microbiomes.	79
Figure 3.7: Relative abundances of the most abundant phyla and genera in COPD and healthy patients.	82
Figure 3.8: Summary of most abundant genera in COPD and in health.	83

Figures

Figure 3.9: Receiver operator characteristic curves in the classification of lung microbiomes.	85
Figure 3.10: Most important genera use in classifying COPD and healthy lungs.	86
Figure 3.11: Linear discriminant analysis displaying the genera that best classify health and disease.	87
Figure 3.12: Significantly enriched pathways in the lung microbiome.	88
Figure 3.13: Network displaying connectivity of significantly enriched pathways.	89
Figure 4.1: <i>Candida albicans</i> is required for effective multi-species biofilm formation.	105
Figure 4.2: Bacteria visually confirmed as being poor biofilm formers.	106
Figure 4.3: Bacteria adhere directly to <i>Candida albicans</i> hyphae in dual-species biofilms.	107
Figure 4.4: <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and <i>Candida albicans</i> have a high binding affinity for one another.	108
Figure 4.5: Microbe specific labelling of organisms shows cell-cell interactions taking place within complex multi-species biofilms.	109
Figure 4.6: Antimicrobial therapies are ineffective against multi-species biofilms.	111
Figure 4.7: Current antimicrobials used in the management of COPD are ineffective in killing pre-formed biofilms.	112
Figure 4.8: Antibiotic treatments induce compositional shifts in multi-species biofilm composition.	113
Figure 4.9: IL-8 production in stimulated epithelial cells.	115
Figure 5.1: Experimental pipeline for RNA extraction.	131
Figure 5.2: Bioinformatic pipeline use in the analysis of the <i>Candida albicans</i> transcriptome.	132
Figure 5.3: Loss of ALS3p significantly affects <i>Candida-Staphylococcus</i> biofilm interactions.	134
Figure 5.4: <i>Candida albicans</i> Als3 is required for <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> mycofilm formation.	136
Figure 5.5: <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> adheres directly to <i>Candida albicans</i> .	138
Figure 5.6: Presence of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> determines mature biofilm transcriptome.	139
Figure 5.7: Levels of differential gene expression is comparable between single and dual-species biofilms at early time points.	141
Figure 5.8: <i>Candida albicans</i> transcriptional changes occur in mature polymicrobial biofilms.	142

Figures

Figure 5.9: <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> induces strain specific gene upregulation in <i>Candida albicans</i> .	143
Figure 5.10: Differential levels of gene expression is observed at 24 h in dual-species biofilms.	144
Figure 5.11: <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> induces significant upregulation of biofilm-associated genes when binding to Als3.	147
Figure 5.12: Identification of key genes with increased expression in dual-species biofilms.	148

Authors declaration

I declare that I have carried out the work in this thesis unless otherwise acknowledged or cited, under the supervision of Dr William MacKay, Professor Craig Williams, Dr Gary Litherland and Dr Anne Crilly. I further declare that this thesis has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Personal details withheld.

Bryn Short

List of publications

Short, B., Delaney, C., McKloud, E., Brown, J. L., Kean, R., Litherland, G. J., Williams, C., Martin, S. L., MacKay, W. G. and Ramage, G. 2021 Investigating the Transcriptome of *Candida albicans* in a Dual-Species *Staphylococcus aureus* Biofilm Model. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, 11.

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Baibek, A., Üçüncü, M., **Short, B.**, Ramage, G., Lilienkampf, A. and Bradley, M. 2021. Dyeing fungi: amphotericin B based fluorescent probes for multiplexed imaging. *ChemComm*, 57, 1899-1902.

Brown, J. L., Johnston, W., Delaney, C., **Short, B.**, Butcher, Mark C., Young, T., Butcher, J., Riggio, M., Culshaw, S and Ramage, G. 2019. Polymicrobial oral biofilm models: simplifying the complex. *Journal of Medical Microbiology*, 68, 1573-1684.

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Short, B., Brown, J. L., Delaney, C., Sherry, L., Williams, C., Ramage, G. and Kean, R. 2019. *Candida auris* exhibits resilient biofilm characteristics in vitro: implications for environmental persistence. *Journal of Hospital Infection*, 103, 92-96.

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List of appendices

- i. PCoA plots of all beta-diversity measures
- ii. High quality copies of figures created in RStudio
- iii. Gene counts from RNA-sequencing experiment with *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*

Abbreviations

AAT: Alpha-1-antitrypsin
AECOPD: Acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
agr: Accessory gene regulator
Als3: Agglutinin-like sequence 3
AM: Alveolar macrophages
ANOVA: Analysis of variance
AUC: Area under the curve
b2ME: b-2-mercaptoethanol
BAL: Bronchoalveolar lavage
CBA: Colombia blood agar
CF: Cystic fibrosis
CFE: Colony forming equivalent
CFW: Calcofluor white
CLR: Centre log ratio
CLSM: Confocal laser-scanning microscope
COPD: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
CT: Computerised tomography
CV: Crystal violet
DDBJ: DNA data bank of Japan
DMSO: Dimethyl sulfoxide
EBI: European bioinformatic institute
ECE: Extent of cell elongation
ECM: Extracellular matrix
eDNA: Extracellular DNA
EFG: Enhanced filamentous growth
ENA: European nucleotide archive
ES: Early studies
FAA: Fastidious anaerobe agar
FEV1: Forced expiratory volume in 1 second
FVC: Forced vital capacity
GOLD: Global initiative for COPD
hwp1: Hyphal wall protein 1
ICS: Inhaled corticosteroids
IL: Interleukin

Abbreviations

IO: Impulse oscillometry
KO: Kegg orthologies
KSFM: Keratinocyte serum-free medium
LABA: Long acting beta-2 agonist
LB: Luria bertani
LDA: Linear discriminant analysis
MCP: Multi-country publications
NCBI: National centre for biotechnology information
NE: Neutrophil elastase
NF: Nuclear factor
NGS: Next generation sequencing
NMDS: Non-metric multidimensional scaling
NTHi: Non-typeable Haemophilus influenzae
OM: Otitis media
OUT: Operational taxonomic unit
PBS: Phosphate buffered saline
PCoA: Principal co-ordinate analysis
pdgX: Periredoxin-glutaredoxin
PERMANOVA: Permutational multivariate analysis of variance
PFA: Paraformaldehyde
PMIC: Planktonic minimum inhibitory concentration
PPM: Potentially pathogenic microorganism
qPCR: Quantitative polymerase chain reaction
QS: Quorum sensing
RCT: Randomised control trial
RIN: RNA integrity number
ROC: Receiver operator characteristic
RPMI: Roswell parks memorial institute
RS: Recent studies
RT: Reverse transcription
SAB: Sabourauds dextrose
SABA: Short acting beta-2 agonist
SCP: Single-country publications
SMIC: Sessile minimum inhibitory concentration
SRA: Sequence read archive
TC: Total citations

Abbreviations

THB: Todd hewit broth

TNF: Tumour necrosis factor

WoS: Web of Science

XTT: 2,3-bis(2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulfo-phenyl)-2H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide

YPD: Yeast peptone dextrose

1 Introduction

Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), a chronic and degenerative lung disease, is the third leading cause of death worldwide, claiming the lives of approximately 6.1 million people (11% of the 55.4 million deaths in 2019) (WHO, 2020). Hallmark symptoms of COPD are cough, dyspnoea, and excess sputum production. Less common but just as troublesome symptoms include but are not limited to wheezing and chest tightness (Miravittles and Ribera, 2017). Progression of COPD is reliant on several factors from host genetics to lifestyle choices. One factor that drives disease progression, which has received increasing amounts of attention in the past decade, is the lung microbiome (Mammen and Sethi, 2016). Differences in the lung microbiome between health and COPD as well as compositional differences between different disease severities and phenotypes have been documented over the years (Cameron et al., 2016, Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Mayhew et al., 2018, Millares et al., 2019, Sinha et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2017, Wang et al., 2019). All these findings indicate that the microbiome plays a significant role in COPD severity and, in turn, disease progression. However, due to the lack of functional analyses that have been performed on the lung microbiome and its constituents in COPD, the mechanisms by which it influences disease progression are still unclear. This is partly due to the lack of ways to investigate the microbiological aspects of COPD *in vitro* whilst remaining true to *in vivo* characteristics.

This introductory chapter aims to review the current literature related to COPD, the lung microbiome of COPD patients and the role of interkingdom biofilms in its pathogenesis. This chapter will also address our current knowledge of clinical management and *in vitro* modelling systems of these diseases.

Some aspects of this chapter have been published in Critical reviews in Microbiology and Current Clinical Microbiology Reports:

Short, B., Carson, S., Devlin, A.-C., Reihill, J. A., Crilly, A., Mackay, W., Ramage, G., Williams, C., Lundy, F. T., Mcgarvey, L. P., et al. 2021. Non-typeable *Haemophilus influenzae* chronic colonization in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). *Critical Reviews in Microbiology*, 47, 192-205.

Delaney, C., Kean, R., **Short, B.**, Tumelty, M., Mclean, W., Nile, C. J. & Ramage, G. 2018. Fungi at the Scene of the Crime: Innocent Bystanders or Accomplices in Oral Infections? *Current Clinical Microbiology Reports*, 5, 190-200.

1.1 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

1.1.1 *Clinical presentations of COPD*

COPD is a chronic, progressive condition affecting the respiratory system (Figure 1.1). It is characterised by the irreversible and continuous decline in lung function and airflow (Su et al., 2015). COPD is estimated to affect over 200 million people worldwide and 2% of the UK population (roughly 2 million people). COPD has recently become the 3rd leading cause of mortality worldwide (WHO, 2020) as a result of continued exposure to risk factors such as cigarette smoke and an aging and increasing population (Mathers and Loncar, 2006). The cause of COPD is multi-factorial and most likely a result of inhalation of cigarette smoke in combination of air pollutants and genetic susceptibilities (Castaldi et al., 2010).

Clinical presentations of COPD vary from person to person, but the distinctive symptoms remain cough, dyspnoea and phlegm. Studying COPD phenotypes is an area of great interest yet there needs to exist a mid-point of oversimplifying the term COPD and treating each case as a separate condition due to high levels of heterogeneity. COPD is an umbrella term that encompasses the spectrum of non-reversible obstructive lung diseases such as chronic bronchitis and emphysema (Devine, 2008). The prevalence of chronic bronchitis ranges from 3-22% in the general population, however, in sub-populations of COPD patients, prevalence can rise to nearly 75% (Dotan et al., 2019). Bronchitis is defined by symptoms such as chronic cough and mucus hypersecretion. Mucus hypersecretion, also known as mucus metaplasia, is caused by overstimulation of immune cells within the airways (Kim and Criner, 2013). The overproduction of mucus associated with bronchitis in combination with airway inflammation ultimately leads to narrowing of bronchial airways (Dotan et al., 2019). The primary reason for the observed mucus hypersecretion is due to its overproduction and secretion by goblet cells. Generally, this is a response to cigarette smoke exposure (Deshmukh et al., 2005), viral and bacterial infections (Holtzman et al., 2005, Burgel and Nadel, 2004). Knock-on effects such as poor ciliary function, airway occlusion and weakened respiratory muscles are observed because of mucus hypersecretion (Kim and Criner, 2013).

Another major condition that COPD encompasses is emphysema. Much like bronchitis, it is characterised by sputum production, dyspnoea and cough (Sharafkhaneh et al., 2008). These symptoms are due to cell death in the alveolar wall or collapse of alveolar septal structures. Smoking has been linked to more than 90% of emphysema cases and mutations

Introduction

of the α -1-antitrypsin (AAT) gene are thought to contribute to the remaining cases (Tuder et al., 2003). In cases where individuals have an AAT deficiency and also smoke, risk of emphysema is increased and these individuals develop emphysema significantly earlier than non-smoking counterparts (Mayer et al., 2006). AAT is a serine protease inhibitor, which can protect against the effects of cigarette smoke. The protease-binding domain of AAT traps and neutralises potentially destructive enzymes such as neutrophil elastases that are increased due to cigarette smoke exposure (Lockett et al., 2012). However, with mutations in the α -1-antitrypsin gene leading to deficiencies this can lead to an imbalance in proteases and their neutralisers. This protease/anti-protease imbalance theory is a leading hypothesis in the development of emphysema as a fragile balance between proteases and anti-proteases exists in order to maintain proper lung function (Goldklang and Stockley, 2016). A loss of this equilibrium can cause increased damage and improper repair of lung epithelium. Ineffective repair of damaged epithelial cells could result in the mutations in α -1-antitrypsin that are already associated with emphysema (Sharafkhaneh et al., 2008). Elastin fragments, created by the proteolysis of elastin also have chemoattractant properties on monocytes. Therefore, creating a positive feedback loop, exacerbating lung inflammation and destruction (Houghton et al., 2006). The study of COPD symptoms is an area of recent interest, but further investigation is needed to determine their long-term outcomes.

Figure 1.1: Healthy and diseased lung, bronchi and alveoli. Healthy and diseased lung, bronchi and alveoli. The left-hand side of the image shows a healthy lung, bronchus and alveoli which show no evidence of airway obstruction. Bronchi typical of bronchitis is depicted on the right-hand side of the image which is inflamed and filled with mucus which is typical of bronchitis. This inflammation and mucus production results in smaller bronchial lumen. Alveoli in the bottom right-hand corner are collapsed due to degradation of elastin fragments and alveolar septal structures which are characteristic of emphysema. Image was created using BioRender.com.

For the most part, COPD symptoms remain stable but just like in other major inflammatory diseases, those suffering from COPD can go through periods where symptom severity increases significantly. AECOPD can be caused by a number of factors such as bacterial or viral infection or environmental stressors such as air pollution (Crisafulli et al., 2018). These periods occur on average once or twice per year and are called acute exacerbations of COPD (AECOPD) and increase the rate of lung deterioration and are associated with increased hospitalisation and mortality (Crisafulli et al., 2018). In the past there has been a distinct lack of homogeneity in the definition of AECOPD but now experts in the field have come to agree on more homogenous definitions (GOLD, 2021, Wedzicha

et al., 2017, NICE, 2018). Simply put, AECOPD is defined by onset or worsening of symptoms that require additional therapy.

1.1.2 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease diagnosis

The Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) was established in 1998 with one of the key aims being to improve the diagnosis of COPD. However, COPD has a long asymptomatic phase during which, lung function deteriorates (Devine, 2008) and is not normally diagnosed until clinical symptoms are detectable and by this time the disease is moderately advanced (Arne et al., 2010). This aspect contributes to the difficulties in estimating the number of individuals suffering from COPD worldwide. Therefore, the impact COPD has on the population is seriously underestimated. However, some regard COPD as a preventable and treatable disease through lifestyle changes such as smoking cessation and increased exercise. Therefore, timely detection and diagnosis is paramount (Celli et al., 2004, Ambrosino and Bertella, 2018).

A COPD diagnosis is considered for patients presenting with symptoms such as cough, sputum production, dyspnoea and a history of exposure to risk factors. Diagnoses that are more accurate then require spirometry. Spirometry, a method of measuring the speed and amount of air that can be inhaled and exhaled, is the most common tool for diagnosing pulmonary diseases such as COPD (Arne et al., 2010). A forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁)/forced vital capacity (FVC; the maximum volume of air that can be exhaled following maximum inhalation) of ≤ 0.7 after administering a bronchodilator indicates the presence of airflow limitation. An FEV₁ of $>80\%$ of the predicted value points towards mild COPD with decreasing predicted FEV₁ values designating more severe disease stages (Celli et al., 2004).

Table 1.1: GOLD disease classification and diagnosis based on FEV₁/FVC ratio

GOLD Stage	Disease Severity	FEV ₁ /FVC (post bronchodilator)	FEV ₁ (% of predicted)
1	Mild	< 0.7	≥ 80
2	Moderate	< 0.7	50 - 80
3	Severe	< 0.7	30 - 50
4	Very Severe	< 0.7	≥ 30

Spirometry remains the preferred method of diagnosis, but it can be ineffective in diagnosing early COPD due to its reliance on airflow obstruction which may not become apparent until the disease is more advanced (Arne et al., 2010).

A 2015 study confirmed this where current and former smokers who did not meet spirometric criteria for COPD diagnosis took part in a variety of tests to identify evidence of respiratory disease (Regan et al., 2015). Findings confirmed 54% of participants had one or more respiratory impairments and 42% had emphysema or thickening of the airways following computerised tomography (CT) scan of the thorax.

Oscillometry techniques, such as impulse oscillometry (IO), have gained attention as a potential method for identifying early disease, while differentiating between obstruction in the proximal and distal airways, but also addressing some other limitations associated with spirometry. For instance, patients who suffer from shortness of breath may struggle to complete spirometry tests (Fazleen and Wilkinson, 2020). IO applies sound waves along the bronchial tree, typically at frequencies in multiples of 5 (between 5 and 35 Hz) and resistance is measured by a conducting tube in the mouth. Sound waves at smaller frequencies travel further, therefore high resistance measured at 20 Hz represents proximal airway resistance and increased measurements from 5 Hz soundwaves indicates obstruction of the distal airways (Lipworth and Jabbal, 2018). IO and other oscillometry techniques are not yet used routinely in practice as resistance values for COPD diagnosis are yet to be agreed upon.

1.1.3 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease epidemiology

Although COPD is a major health problem and burden on services, there is limited information available on COPD prevalence. High rates of underdiagnoses (Lamprecht et al., 2015) and misdiagnosis prevents the application of preventative and therapeutic measures in order to minimise the serious effects and high costs of COPD (Fernández-Villar et al., 2017). Misdiagnosis often occurs when differentiating COPD from other respiratory diseases such as asthma leading to improper treatment administration. This more frequently occurs in secondary care settings where healthcare professionals are less aware and familiar with COPD and diagnosis techniques (Hangaard et al., 2017, Fromer, 2011). In

Introduction

2015, the Global Burden of Disease Study estimated that 174 million people worldwide suffered from COPD, but other studies have reported numbers of sufferers to be as high as 380 million (Rabe and Watz, 2017). Not only are there regional differences in the prevalence of COPD but there are also differences in the increases in prevalence observed with the largest increases being observed in Eastern Mediterranean countries (112%) and Africa (102%) (Rabe and Watz, 2017). However, under and over diagnosis makes it difficult to gather accurate data on the prevalence of COPD (Lamprecht et al., 2015).

In a recent study, Snell and colleagues used the Health Intelligence Network database to estimate the prevalence and incidence rate of COPD in the United Kingdom (Snell et al., 2016). The authors estimated that 1.2 million people in the UK had diagnosed COPD, which was a 27% increase compared to the previous decade. This increase makes COPD the second most prevalent lung disease in the UK behind asthma (Snell et al., 2016). Specifically, mean prevalence of COPD is higher in the West of Scotland and Northern England. In a 2017 study, Blanco et al. (2017) used an inverse weighting interpolation technique to estimate the prevalence of COPD in Europe (Figure 1.2). Analysing data from 62 studies in 19 countries, the highest prevalence of COPD was found to be in Manchester (26%) with Glasgow closely following at 24%. Regional discrepancies in prevalence are likely a result of lifestyle choices and air pollution, two factors that have already been shown to influence the severity of disease and frequency of exacerbations (Peacock et al., 2011).

Figure 1.2: Geographical heatmap of COPD prevalence in Europe. Heatmap displaying the mean prevalence of COPD in Europe calculated using an inverse weighting interpolation technique, red indicates a high prevalence and blue indicates a low prevalence (Blanco et al., 2017).

1.1.4 Immunology and the immune response

Inflammation in COPD is heterogeneous and varies from patient-to-patient. Many cells produce inflammatory mediators in the COPD lung. Once established, the inflammatory process in COPD persists, even after smoking cessation. This is a product of a build-up of inflammatory mucus and an increase in bronchial wall tissue volume, which stems from immune cell infiltration (Hogg et al., 2004).

Inflammation in the COPD lungs is primarily driven by neutrophils, macrophages and T-cells, with lung epithelial cells producing a large amount of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Cytokine networks in COPD are complex in nature but key cytokines include interleukin (IL)-8, IL-6, IL-1 β and tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) (Barnes, 2009). These cytokines augment inflammation via activation of nuclear factor (NF)- κ B, resulting in the expression of inflammatory genes.

Despite the large presence of multiple types of immune cells, the presence of neutrophils in the airways of COPD patients and their production of elastase and other proteases has been identified as a key mediator of the tissue damage and declining lung function that are characteristic of COPD (Hoenderdos and Condliffe, 2013). Although neutrophil elastase (NE) plays a major role in bacterial and fungal killing, extracellular matrix components such as collagen and fibronectin are also NE substrates (Lungarella et al., 2008). Decreases in lung function as a result of neutrophils is a result of a dangerous chain reaction which begins with external stressors such as cigarette smoke or infection prompting an increase in the production of pro-inflammatory such as IL-8, which prompts and influx of neutrophils and increased production of NE. This increased NE in the airways disrupts the protease/anti-protease balance, resulting in increased tissue destruction.

Macrophages are commonly found in the pulmonary system with alveolar macrophages (AM) accounting for 90% of that cell population (van oud Alblas and van Furth, 1979). Activated by cytokines that are enriched in COPD such as IL-8 and TNF- α , macrophages have been reported to play a pivotal role in COPD pathogenesis and are found in significantly higher numbers in the lungs of COPD patients compared to healthy controls (Vlahos and Bozinovski, 2014). A positive correlation between emphysema and the presence of macrophages in the airways has been previously identified (Meshi et al., 2002, Vlahos and Bozinovski, 2014). A similar correlation has also been reported in COPD patients (Di Stefano et al., 1998). Exposure to COPD risk factors such as cigarette smoke can have detrimental effects on the activity of AM. For example, cigarette smoke can negatively influence actin polymerisation by hindering the activity of RhoA and Rac1, which are required for effective phagocytosis (Richens et al., 2009, Minematsu et al., 2011). This then results in cell phenotypes deficient in efferocytosis. Reduced efferocytosis has implications in the reduced clearance of exhausted neutrophils, resulting in an accumulation of NE, which as outlined above, can have serious implications within the airways. In addition to insufficient clearance of apoptotic neutrophils, AM in COPD display impaired phagocytosis of respiratory pathogens such as *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, contributing to persistent colonisation (Berenson et al., 2006, Berenson et al., 2013, Taylor et al., 2010).

Finally, the remaining major inflammatory cell type in COPD, T-cells, were first reported to be increased in COPD in 1995 by Finkelstein and co-workers who identified a correlation between the number of T-cells in the lung and emphysema severity (Finkelstein et al.,

1995). Since then, our understanding of T-cells in COPD has developed. T-cells in the lungs of COPD patients are fully activated, as though they have been presented with an antigen (Grumelli et al., 2004). Work has primarily focused on the involvement of CD8⁺ T-cells. For example, previous studies have shown that CD8⁻ mice do not develop emphysema following long-term cigarette smoke exposure (Maeno et al., 2007).

Despite the focus on CD8⁺ T-cells, CD4⁺ cells are also found in increased numbers in the COPD lung (although this increase is sometimes not as pronounced as that of CD8⁺) (Majo et al., 2001). IL-1- β has been shown to drive the differentiation of CD4⁺ cells into Th17 cells (Mailer et al., 2015). This overabundance of CD4⁺ cells, paired with increased production of IL-1- β , likely results in differentiation of CD4⁺ cells into Th17 cells within the COPD lung. The importance of Th17 cells in COPD is becoming increasingly recognised. With the ability to produce IL-17A, Th17 cells have been shown to promote the influx of macrophages and neutrophils into the lungs by activating bronchial fibroblasts and epithelial cells (Wong et al., 2010). An increase in the number of Th17 cells in the airways is associated with a higher abundance of bacteria commonly found in the oral cavity (Segal et al., 2016). This finding supports hypotheses stating that the oral microbiome has the ability to influence the progression of COPD.

1.1.5 Therapeutics in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

There exist several treatment options for managing COPD, which ultimately aim to reduce symptoms, reduce the risk of AECOPD and ultimately improve patient quality of life as much as possible. Treatments are provided based on symptom severity, history of AECOPD and exposure to risk factors. A patient's treatment regimen can differ based on symptom severity and with occurrence of AECOPD. Treatment options can be divided into 2 main groups: pharmacological and non-pharmacological (GOLD, 2021). Non-pharmacological treatment options include smoking cessation and surgical intervention whereas pharmacological options involve drug therapies such as antibiotic and steroid treatment regimens.

It is recommended at every opportunity to offer patients with COPD, treatment and support to stop smoking (NICE, 2018). This falls under the non-pharmacological treatment category along with surgery and others. Pharmacological therapies are common and include steroids, antibiotics and anti-inflammatory agents.

1.1.5.1 Treatment of stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

A myriad of pharmacological treatment options are available to patients and the chosen treatment largely depends on the patient's response and preference. Treatments during periods of stable COPD simply aim to maintain symptom stability and reduce exposure to risk factors (GOLD, 2021). Pharmacological treatments in stable COPD can reduce AECOPD risk and severity, reduce symptoms and increase ability to exercise. Most treatments are administered via inhalation, meaning proper technique is of high significance.

Guidelines recommend immediate prescription of short-acting beta-2-agonists (SABAs) for immediate relief of symptoms which are frequently prescribed in stable and exacerbated COPD (NICE, 2018, GOLD, 2021). These promote smooth muscle relaxation and dilation of bronchial airways through stimulation of beta-2-receptors on bronchial smooth muscle cells. SABAs effects take place quickly (within 15 minutes) with peak activity occurring after 2.5 hours (Ejiofor and Turner, 2013). This contrasts with long-acting beta-2-agonists (LABA), whose effects linger from 12 to 24 hours after rapid onset (Fuso et al., 2013). LABAs are generally administered if patients are still affected by symptoms but present with asthmatic features or have shown previous responsiveness to SABAs (NICE, 2018).

Although sometimes prescribed, monotherapy with inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) is not recommended as they have not shown to significantly improve lung function or reduce mortality (Yang et al., 2012). However, ICS and LABA have shown synergy when applied as a combination therapy with the proposition that ICS increases responsiveness to LABAs.

Over the years, a number of randomised control trials (RCT) have aimed to determine if the administration of antibiotics in stable COPD is of benefit and a number of meta-analyses have aimed to combine these findings (Ni et al., 2015, Zhang et al., 2017, Donath et al., 2013, Yao et al., 2013). These have generally focused on the effectiveness of macrolide antibiotics such as azithromycin and erythromycin. Meta-analyses performed on the literature report that prophylactic treatment with erythromycin or azithromycin significantly reduced the frequency of AECOPD, likely through their immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties. Unfortunately, from searching the literature there is no evidence of other meta-analyses investigating the efficacy of antibiotic prophylaxis in AECOPD with other causes such as viruses. Although it can be expected that such interventions would not reduce AECOPD frequency. However, such antibiotic regimens should be implemented with care as long-term prophylactic

treatments do not come without downfalls such as the risk of introducing macrolide resistance among other adverse effects.

1.1.5.2 Treatments for acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

When treating AECOPD, the aim is to reduce the consequences of the current exacerbation whilst reducing the risk of subsequent events. However, use of antibiotics in the treatment of AECOPD remains controversial. Evidence of bacterial infections should be collected prior to antibiotic prescription. Proof of infection includes increased sputum production, sputum colour or bacterial culture from sputum (Miravittles et al., 2012, Sethi et al., 2002). Currently, it is recommended that antibiotic therapy lasts from 5 to 7 days in AECOPD, but this guidance was given based on the administration of levofloxacin. AECOPD can be sub-categorised based on the severity of exacerbation with mild and moderate cases being handled in outpatient settings whereas severe cases of AECOPD require hospitalisation (GOLD, 2021).

The severity of exacerbation should be taken into account when considering the appropriateness of antibiotics. For example, there is less evidence for positive results when treating less severe cases of AECOPD with antibiotics (NICE, 2018). GOLD guidelines support the initial use of macrolides or tetracycline but state that antibiotics should be selected in line with local bacterial resistance patterns (GOLD, 2021). In a recent meta-analysis of studies investigating the effectiveness of antibiotics as an AECOPD therapy reported that the macrolide, dirithromycin possessed high clinical cure rates with a low frequency of adverse effects (Zhang et al., 2017). Other antibiotics with high clinical effectiveness included ciprofloxacin, ofloxacin and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. Long-term use of the azithromycin, although it is effective in reducing AECOPD risk, can result in loss of hearing (Albert et al., 2011). Although dirithromycin is of the same antibiotic class as azithromycin, it works by a different metabolic pathway, therefore it is unlikely to cause the same adverse effects (Zhang et al., 2017).

With respects to other treatment options, bronchodilators and corticosteroids are commonplace in AECOPD as well as in periods of symptom stability. However, there is no high-quality evidence from RCTs regarding the efficacy of bronchodilators in AECOPD (Crisafulli et al., 2018). There is also limited information regarding the most effective

bronchodilator delivery method. A 2016 review aimed to compare the use of nebulisers to pressurised metered-dose inhalers but found no significant differences in FEV₁ improvements (van Geffen et al., 2016).

The benefit of ICS in AECOPD is less clear as these rely heavily on the user's ability to administer them properly, something that may be difficult for patients suffering from AECOPD. However, there is large amounts of evidence supporting the use of systemic corticosteroids with studies reporting improvements in length of hospital stays, FEV₁, dyspnoea and risk of relapse (Wedzicha et al., 2017). Prednisone/prednisolone is the corticosteroid of choice in AECOPD with oral administration and short treatment durations being preferred over intravenous administration and long durations of treatment (Aaron et al., 2003, Leuppi et al., 2013, de Jong et al., 2007, Aggarwal et al., 2011, Walters et al., 2018). Oral administration is favoured due to similar rates of effectiveness and lower risk of systemic effects compared to intravenous administration.

1.2 Microbiology of the lungs

Due to our reliance on our ability (or lack thereof) to culture microorganisms from tissue samples, the lungs of healthy individuals were believed to be sterile and only became colonised by microorganisms during periods of disease. This ultimately led to the exclusion of the lungs from the human microbiome project. With increased access to culture-independent research methods the lungs of both healthy and diseased individuals are now well-documented as housing a variety of microorganisms and it is well-accepted that disruption of the delicate balance of a 'healthy' microbiome can lead to the development of disease (Bassis et al., 2015, Moffatt and Cookson, 2017, Nguyen et al., 2015).

The adapted island model is commonly utilised to study lung microbiome ecology. This is based on an ecology model of island biogeography by MacArthur and Wilson in 1963 (MacArthur and Wilson, 1963). This model uses microbe immigration and elimination rates to predict species richness within the lungs (Dickson et al., 2014a). Immigration occurs primarily through microaspiration from the oral cavity and inhalation of microbes from the surrounding air. Elimination of microbes arises through cough, ciliary clearance and via the immune system (adaptive and innate). Immigration and elimination rates can then be altered by a variety of factors such as the proximity to the oropharynx and increased microbial burden of the oropharynx leading to increased immigration rates whereas

impaired ciliary function and cough reflexes result in poorer elimination rates (Dickson et al., 2014a).

1.2.1 *The microbiome of the healthy lungs*

The microbiome of the lungs plays a similar role to the microbiomes of other body sites such as the oral cavity or the gastrointestinal tract by helping to shape the local immune response. Again, much like in the gastrointestinal tract, exposure to certain microbes in early life can be protective against certain respiratory disease (by reducing the risk of developing allergic airway inflammation later in life) and reduced exposure to microbes leads to insufficient priming of the immune system (Roduit et al., 2011, Taylor et al., 2010).

Although there is high importance on studying the roles of individual organisms in disease, this does not provide 'the full picture' when put into the context of disease. Answering the question of "who's the pathogen?" by distinguishing commensal from pathogen is, more often than not, unclear. In tandem with increased availability and decreasing costs, the need to answer these questions has led to an increase in the popularity of next generation sequencing (NGS) studies characterising the microbiome of disease sites. The microbiome can be simply defined as all of the organisms, and their genes, present in a habitat (Ursell et al., 2012) but is more commonly used to refer to bacteria. Other terms are now being employed with increasing regularity to characterise organisms within a space with more specificity such as mycobiome (fungi), virome (viruses) and archaeome (archaea).

In contrast to other, readily accessible sites such as the oral cavity, lung microbiome studies are lacking. We now know the lung microbiome is dominated by organisms that originate from the oral cavity (Bassis et al., 2015). In healthy lungs, much like the oral cavity, the most abundant bacterial genera are *Streptococcus* (Moffatt and Cookson, 2017, Zaura et al., 2009).

1.2.2 *The mycobiome of the healthy lung*

The ubiquitous nature of fungal spores in soil, water and air mean that we inevitably inhale anywhere from 1000 to 10 billion fungal spores each day (ASM, 2019). To date, only a small number of studies have characterised the mycobiome in the lungs of healthy

individuals. Most of our knowledge of the mycobiome in the healthy lung comes from healthy control cohorts in other studies (Bittinger et al., 2014, McTaggart et al., 2019, Charlson et al., 2012, van Woerden et al., 2013).

Fungal taxa such as *Candida*, *Aspergillus*, *Cryptococcus* and *Penicillium* are identified with the highest frequency in healthy lungs (McTaggart et al., 2019, Bittinger et al., 2014, Charlson et al., 2012). However, rate of occurrence and abundance levels fluctuate greatly within healthy lung mycobiomes. This suggests that the mycobiome of healthy individuals is a dynamic entity, which most likely stems from high levels of microbial clearance within the lungs.

1.2.3 The lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

The determinants of lung microbiome ecology as stated by the adapted island model all vary greatly between health and disease. However, similar to healthy individuals, the lungs of COPD patients are also dominated by *Streptococcus* spp. such as *S. pneumoniae*, *S. mitis* and *S. salivarius* (Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Mayhew et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016, Wang et al., 2020a). The microbiome of COPD patients has been reported to be significantly different to that of health individuals. It has also been documented to undergo compositional changes based on disease severity (GOLD status) as well as during periods of AECOPD when compared to stable COPD (Mayhew et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016, Sze et al., 2012b). As with the healthy lung, the COPD microbiome is largely comprised of oral-associated taxa such as *Streptococcus*, *Prevotella* and *Veillonella*. There also exists a considerable variety of potentially pathogenic microorganisms (PPMs) such as *Pseudomonas*, *Haemophilus*, *Staphylococcus* and *Moraxella* which are associated with respiratory infections in COPD patients (Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Huang and Boushey, 2015, Mayhew et al., 2018, Bafadhel et al., 2011).

Despite the diverse nature of the COPD lung microbiome, *Haemophilus influenzae* has received a large amount of attention and is considered the keystone pathogen in COPD (Brill et al., 2018, Murphy et al., 2004, Murphy et al., 2015, Sethi et al., 2004, Su et al., 2018). However, as mentioned above, several other PPMs are frequently identified in COPD lungs in periods of stability and exacerbation (Bafadhel et al., 2011, Papi et al., 2006, Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2015, Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2017, Mayhew et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2019). Despite their presence, the role of these organisms in the pathogenesis of COPD

is frequently overlooked in favour of *H. influenzae*. However, the argument can be made that no single organism is responsible for the progression of a disease, especially one as complex as COPD. Therefore, multi-omics studies are required to untangle the complex networks of interactions between organisms, proteins and metabolites within the lungs to provide a more complete understanding of the nature of the lung microbiome in COPD.

1.2.4 *The mycobiome of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*

As reported by Charlson *et al* in 2012, the lungs of healthy controls exhibited low levels of fungal amplification compared to that of lung transplant patients (Charlson *et al.*, 2012). Antibiotic treatments of the lung transplant patients are likely what caused an increase in fungal bioburden compared to healthy controls, supporting the idea that the bacterial microbiome and host immune system are responsible for limiting fungal colonisation in the lungs. As outlined above, in COPD, as with many respiratory diseases, the host immune system and the bacterial microbiome are both in a state of dysbiosis. It is then reasonable to presume that there would then be an overgrowth of fungi in the lungs of COPD patients compared to healthy individuals. Nevertheless, the presence of fungi is commonly noted as contaminants or innocent bystanders. There is now increasing amounts of data suggesting that fungi play a role in multiple diseases by actively driving infection or by promoting bacterial growth and virulence (Pendleton *et al.*, 2017).

To date there exists only a small number of studies defining the mycobiome in the lungs of COPD patients. Despite their limited number, these studies agree that *Candida*, *Aspergillus* and other filamentous fungi such as *Phialosimplex* and *Penicillium* dominate the COPD lungs (Tiew *et al.*, 2020, Su *et al.*, 2015, Liu *et al.*, 2021a). From these studies we are aware that the composition of the mycobiome in COPD during stability and AECOPD differs suggesting that the mycobiome plays a similar role to the microbiome (Tiew *et al.*, 2020). A recent study by Liu *et al.* (2021a) report that the mycobiome may be a differentiator for the frequent and non-frequent exacerbator phenotypes, with increases in *Candida* and *Aspergillus spp.* identified in frequent exacerbators. Dysbiosis of the lung micro- and mycobiome was also associated with increased inflammatory mediators in the sputa and the blood (Liu *et al.*, 2021a).

There are continuous developments in sequencing methods but there are still factors limiting mycobiome research. For example, the chosen extraction method can favour filamentous fungi or yeast (Fredricks *et al.*, 2005). There remain many unanswered

questions concerning the lung mycobiome therefore there is a need to follow in the footsteps of lung microbiome studies in order to highlight the role of fungi in COPD.

1.3 Biofilms

Biofilms are typically described as complex structures of microbial cells encased in a self-produced extracellular matrix (ECM). Microorganisms can form biofilms for a number of reasons which are normally a response to external stressors such as pH, temperature, nutrient availability and antimicrobial challenge (Muhammad et al., 2020). The first report of bacterial cells taking on an aggregating phenotype came from Anton van Leeuwenhoek in 1684 when he observed white matter between teeth, which is now known as dental plaque. Using a homemade light microscope, he drew pictures of strings of cocci (possibly *Streptococci*) and bacilli (possible *Fusobacteria* or *Actinomyces*) (Brown et al., 2019).

Biofilms typically exhibit a cyclical lifestyle which occurs in 3 distinct steps (as shown in Figure 1.3); attachment, development and detachment (López et al., 2010). A hallmark of biofilms is their recalcitrant nature towards antimicrobial drugs compared to their planktonic counterparts. In some instances, biofilms have been shown to be up to 1000-fold more tolerant to antimicrobial treatments than free-floating cells (Ramage et al., 2001). This decreased susceptibility to antimicrobials stems from multiple factors such as ECM production, varying levels of cell metabolism throughout the biofilm and cell-cell interactions occurring within the biofilm. A major role of the ECM is to provide biofilm cells with protection against external threats such as drugs and immune cells. The dense, complex nature of the ECM prevents large molecules from penetrating the biofilm (Lewis, 2001). Aside from providing protection from external stressors, the biofilm ECM also provides structure to the biofilm and provides a defined space for cell-cell interactions to take place within the biofilm where nutrients and quorum-sensing molecules can be transported throughout the biofilm (Flemming et al., 2016, Karimi et al., 2015).

Figure 1.3: The life cycle of biofilm cells. The cycle typically begins with initial, reversible attachment of cells to a surface (A) before stronger and more permanent adhesion allowing for multiplication and formation of ECM (B). Finally, cells actively disassociate from the main biofilm structure to set up a new infection site, beginning the cycle again (C). Cells coloured in pale purple depict cells with lower metabolic activity, a common trait in biofilms. Image was created using BioRender.com.

1.3.1 Fungal biofilms

Even to this day, biofilm studies primarily focus on bacteria but this caveat in our understanding of fungi in disease biology has been recognised in the literature and the number of fungal biofilm studies have been steadily increasing in recent years as seen in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Biofilm publications per year. The number of search results provided by PubMed for “Biofilm AND Bacteria” and “Biofilm AND Fungi” between 1980 and 2020 (search was performed December 2021).

Candida is the most commonly implicated genera in fungal infections and of this genus, *C. albicans* is the most frequently isolated species (Brown et al., 2012). However, in recent years, the prevalence of infections caused by other non-*albicans* *Candida* species has risen (Giacobbe et al., 2020). Of particular interest is *Candida auris*, an enigmatic yeast that was first described in 2009 and quickly established itself as a troublesome opportunistic pathogen which has displayed resistance to every class of antifungal (Du et al., 2020, Kean et al., 2020). Other fungal genera, primarily filamentous fungi are more widespread in the respiratory tract for the very reason outlined above in section 1.2.2. Unfortunately, there are still considerable gaps in our knowledge about the role and importance of fungal biofilms in COPD.

Another respiratory condition where the role of fungal biofilms is better understood is cystic fibrosis (CF). Bacteria remain the most common causative agent of CF infections, but the isolation of fungi is becoming more common (Delfino et al., 2019). Lower respiratory tract infections of the CF lung are often associated with biofilms due to a decrease in volumes of periciliary fluid and diminished mucus detachment (Singh et al., 2000, Høiby et al., 2010). Indeed, there are reliable studies reporting the importance of fungal biofilms as a critical component of these biofilm aggregates (Müller et al., 2011, Smith et al., 2015, Chotirmall and McElvaney, 2014). The loss of this innate clearance mechanism in the airways provides prime conditions for long-term colonisation. Spores formed by *Aspergillus*, one of the most abundant fungal species found throughout the environment (Paulussen et al., 2017), are

Introduction

readily inhaled, with *Aspergillus fumigatus* being the most common species identified in sputum cultures (Sabino et al., 2015).

Aspergillus is not the only fungal species identified from the lungs of CF patients. *Candida albicans*, is the most commonly isolated yeast and can be isolated from up to 75% of patients (Williams et al., 2016). As with *A. fumigatus*, co-isolation of *C. albicans* and *P. aeruginosa* from the same patient is associated with worse clinical outcomes (Dharmgaye et al., 2016). *P. aeruginosa* within these dual-species biofilms has displayed increased tolerance to meropenem compared to when in a mono-species biofilm. This increased tolerance is hypothesised to arise from secretion of fungal mannans and glucans into the ECM of the biofilm which is hypothesised to prevent effective diffusion of meropenem throughout the biofilm (Alam et al., 2020). This has been attributed to fungal mannans and glucans within the ECM of the biofilm. This trend of *C. albicans* protecting bacteria within a biofilm has been observed with other bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, another commonly found bacteria in CF, through production of ECM components such as glucans and extracellular DNA (eDNA) (Kean et al., 2017, Harriott and Noverr, 2009, Kong et al., 2016).

In cases where *A. fumigatus* colonises CF patients, the most commonly prescribed antifungals are triazoles such as voriconazole and itraconazole (Boyle et al., 2019). Voriconazole is also the recommended first-line treatment for fungal infections in COPD (Ader et al., 2009). The consensus regarding the efficacy of azoles in CF is clouded with several smaller, non-controlled, open-label studies reporting a benefit to azole treatments (Hilliard et al., 2005, Shoseyov et al., 2006, Coughlan et al., 2012). Whereas the only published RCT study investigating the efficacy of azoles in CF therapy reported no significant benefit in patients who were chronically colonised by *A. fumigatus* (Aaron et al., 2012). The chronic colonisation and ineffectiveness of azole interventions in this RCT points towards the presence of fungal biofilms which display high levels of azole resistance (Rajendran et al., 2011).

Unlike *A. fumigatus*, there is some controversy surrounding the treatment of *C. albicans* in the airways due to clouded lines distinguishing colonisation and active infection (Pendleton et al., 2017). However, a number of studies have identified an association with *Candida* colonisation and worsening FEV₁ in CF patients (Gileles-Hillel et al., 2015, Dharmgaye et al., 2016, Williams et al., 2016). Although *C. albicans* may not be actively causing infection, its interactions with certain bacteria indicate an indirect role in disease through protecting pathogenic bacteria and increasing their virulence (Dharmgaye et al., 2016, Kean et al.,

2017, Todd et al., 2019). This raises the question: Should *Candida* colonisation be addressed in order to improve patient outcomes? Although there is not a generally accepted treatment option for *C. albicans* in CF, azoles will likely prove to be ineffective due to high levels of azole tolerance in *C. albicans* biofilms, and the ease in which it develops resistance (El-Azizi et al., 2015, Kean et al., 2017, Rajendran et al., 2016). Although their use is largely limited to case studies, the use of echinocandins or polyenes may yield more promising clinical outcomes, particularly if nebulised to enhance delivery (Duckwall et al., 2019, Schwarz et al., 2018, Hayes Jr et al., 2010).

1.3.2 Interkingdom biofilms

Understanding the interactions between bacterial species is crucial in understanding their roles in disease. However, bacteria are not the only microbial inhabitants of the human body with the oral cavity and the respiratory tract harbouring a large variety of bacteria and fungi (Bassis et al., 2015, Dewhirst et al., 2010, Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Zaura et al., 2017). Our initial understanding and appreciation of polymicrobial biofilms and infection came from interactions within the oral cavity. Attachment of certain organisms to hard and soft tissue in the oral cavity provides the necessary substrate for other organisms to adhere. This process of sequential attachment of early, intermediate and late colonisers is often referred to as co-aggregation (Rickard et al., 2003).

Although co-aggregation is frequently associated with bacterial species, it has also been reported in interkingdom biofilms between *Candida albicans* and bacteria such as *Streptococcus gordonii* and *Streptococcus oralis* (Bamford et al., 2009, Pidwill et al., 2018, Souza et al., 2020). At times, these polymicrobial, interkingdom interactions can be competitive or detrimental to one species, they often lead to positive outcomes for both the fungi and bacteria (Delaney et al., 2018).

C. albicans has been shown to interact with a number of different bacteria such as *P. aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus* spp. and *Enterococcus faecalis* (Delaney et al., 2018). While the nature of interkingdom interactions between *C. albicans* and bacteria ranges from synergistic to antagonistic relationships, all of which can influence clinical outcomes, the interactions between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* will be discussed in further detail due to their direct relevance to later chapters.

1.3.2.1 *Candida albicans*-*Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms

Fungi such as *C. albicans* are known to interact with many different bacteria, with many of these interactions being beneficial to one or both organisms (Peters et al., 2012a). These interactions often lead to increased virulence and antimicrobial tolerance, which ultimately result in chronic or more severe infection. Earlier studies by El-Azizi et al. (2004) revealed increased adhesion and biofilm formation between *C. albicans* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, revealing possible synergisms in the relationship between both genera. Peters and colleagues built upon these findings in 2010, showing that *S. aureus* preferentially bound to *C. albicans* hyphae (Peters et al., 2010).

Polymicrobial biofilms containing both *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* have been implicated in conditions such as angular cheilitis, CF and diabetic foot ulcers (Peters et al., 2012a). These organisms interact directly, with *S. aureus* adhering directly to the fungal hyphae via the fungal adhesin agglutinin like sequence 3 (Als3) (Peters et al., 2012b, Kean et al., 2017). Previous studies indicated that this association favours the bacterium with recent work by Kong et al. (2016) and Todd et al. (2019) showing that *C. albicans* protects *S. aureus* whilst augmenting its virulence. This is achieved by *S. aureus* coating itself in the fungal ECM component B-1,3-glucan which provides protection against antibiotics. Kean et al. (2017) also reported increased virulence in dual-species infections of the *Galleria mellonella* infection model. The mechanism behind the documented increased virulence occurs via two mechanisms; the first is due to *C. albicans* penetrating host cells, aiding in bacterial invasion (which aids bacterial invasion in a manner similar to a needlestick injection) and the second is through upregulation of the *S. aureus* accessory gene regulator (*agr*) quorum-sensing pathway (Todd et al., 2019, Kean et al., 2017). Increased expression of this quorum sensing pathway leads to alpha-toxin production, ultimately resulting in a more virulent phenotype (Le and Otto, 2015).

In addition to interacting physically within biofilms, *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* interact indirectly through chemical mediators such as quorum sensing (QS) molecules. The best-characterised *C. albicans* QS molecule is farnesol, which regulates fungal yeast-to-hyphae switching and biofilm formation (Han et al., 2012, Ramage et al., 2002a). In high concentrations above 100µM, farnesol inhibits *S. aureus* adhesion and biofilm formation but in low concentrations, it can induce formation of *S. aureus* biofilms (Jabra-Rizk et al., 2006). Farnesol, in intermediate concentrations of 40µM, can also increase *S. aureus* drug tolerance through suspected upregulation of efflux pumps via the MgrA gene regulator

(Kong et al., 2017). Drug tolerance in *C. albicans* is also increased in dual-species biofilms as *S. aureus* increases production of eDNA which provides protection for both organisms against the dual-active antifungal, miconazole (Kean et al., 2017). Mechanisms behind the increased abundance of eDNA in these biofilms was recently unveiled through RNA-sequencing of the *S. aureus* transcriptome. Analyses revealed down-regulation of autolysis repression genes, causing increased release of bacterial intracellular components, including DNA, into the surrounding environment of the biofilm (Vila et al., 2021).

1.3.2.2 *Candida albicans*-*Porphyromonas gingivalis* biofilms

Studies investigating possible interactions between fungi and obligate anaerobes were sparked by the finding that *C. albicans* depletes extracellular oxygen to allow for anaerobic bacterial growth (Bradshaw et al., 1998). The anaerobic pathogen, *P. gingivalis* has been frequently isolated from periodontal pockets, as has *C. albicans*, suggesting a degree of synergism (Urzúa et al., 2008, How et al., 2016, Kigure et al., 1995). This can be confirmed where several oral bacteria, including *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, were shown to increase *C. albicans* germ tube formation (Nair et al., 2001). Compared to our understanding of modes of interaction between *C. albicans* and other bacteria such as *Streptococci* and *Staphylococci*, our understanding of the interactions between *C. albicans* and *P. gingivalis* is still in its infancy. Initial findings by Nair and colleagues in 2001 have been confirmed through the induced upregulation of hyphae specific genes such as hyphal wall protein 1 (*HWP1*) and *ALS3* (Bartnicka et al., 2019, Nair et al., 2001). Direct interaction between *C. albicans* and *P. gingivalis* occur between the fungal and bacterial adhesins, Als3 and InlJ, respectively (Sztukowska et al., 2018). Other studies have also found that the adhesive domain of the gingipain RgpA plays a role in fungal adherence (Bartnicka et al., 2019).

Recently the transcriptome of *P. gingivalis* in a dual-species biofilm with *C. albicans* was defined (Sztukowska et al., 2018). It was shown that *C. albicans* induces the upregulation of cell division and cell wall genes along with pathogenesis associated genes. These findings point towards *C. albicans* aiding in *P. gingivalis* growth and increasing its virulence through increased expression of type-9-secretion-system genes. Secretion systems are pathways by which bacteria release virulence factors but are also utilised in adhesion and nutrient acquisition (Lasica et al., 2017). Discovered in *P. gingivalis*, the type-9-secretion-system is involved in the secretion of gingipains (Sato et al., 2010). More

recently, *C. albicans* was shown to protect *P. gingivalis* from the host immune system, promoting a chronic infection phenotype (Bartnicka et al., 2020). However, despite our growing knowledge of how *P. gingivalis* responds to *C. albicans*, we are yet to unveil the effects the bacterial pathogen has on the fungi.

1.3.3 Biofilms in the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease lung

Patients with COPD are prone to chronic bacterial colonisation and repeated pulmonary infections (Matkovic and Miravittles, 2013). The environment created in the lungs of COPD patients is favourable for the formation of biofilms due to decreased ability of the host immune system to clear bacteria (Hoenderdos and Condliffe, 2013, Murphy et al., 2004). Biofilms in the lung differ significantly in structure compared to biofilms in the oral cavity. Rather than adopting the common 'mushroom-like' structure associated with biofilms, respiratory biofilms appear as smaller aggregates (Bjarnsholt et al., 2013). Despite large differences in structure, respiratory biofilms still possess the traits of traditional biofilms (as summarised in Figures 1.5 and 1.6) such as increased antimicrobial tolerance, micro-environments and nutrient gradients despite containing a lower number of cells (between 10^1 and 10^4 cells) (Darch et al., 2018, Sønderholm et al., 2017).

Figure 1.5: Nutrient gradients within biofilms. Levels of nutrients and cell metabolism vary within biofilm aggregates, typically decreasing from the surface of the biofilm towards the biofilm base. Image was created using BioRender.com.

Although, there is extensive evidence of biofilms in respiratory infections such as CF, they are underappreciated in COPD. Despite this under appreciation there is growing amounts of data to suggest they play a role in the pathogenesis of COPD (Ahearn et al., 2017, Short et al., 2021, Murphy et al., 2005, Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2017). In the airways, biofilms may act as reservoirs of bacteria, which can trigger the reoccurrence of lower respiratory infections and contribute to frequent exacerbator phenotypes in COPD (Sethi, 2010). They are characterised by changes in cell behaviour, such as differential gene expression and ECM production which, in turn, can lead to increased virulence, antimicrobial tolerance and decreased susceptibility to killing from immune cells (Singh et al., 2017). In a 2017 study, *P. aeruginosa* strains isolated from COPD patients were shown to possess a range of biofilm forming capacities (Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2017). Colonisation with a high biofilm forming strain of *P. aeruginosa* was found to be associated with an increase in abundance of other bacterial genera such as *Fusobacterium*.

Introduction

However, from the limited number of studies investigating the role of biofilms in COPD, the majority have focused on *H. influenzae*. In a study by Murphy and colleagues the formation of biofilms by clinical isolates of non-typeable *H. influenzae* (NTHi) was found to be dependent on the production of a 30-kDa protein identified as peroxiredoxin-glutaredoxin (pdgX). PdgX levels were significantly increased in NTHi biofilms compared to planktonic growth and 44% of study participants, who were diagnosed with COPD, displayed considerably higher levels of antibodies to pdgX (Murphy et al., 2005). As well as being crucial for effective biofilm production, pdgX provides protection against oxidative stress induced by neutrophil extracellular traps (Juneau et al., 2015).

Figure 1.6: Mechanisms by which biofilms interact with the host and antibiotics in COPD. Biofilms utilise a number of mechanisms to persist in the host. Production of a robust ECM aids in the resistance to neutrophils and neutrophil extracellular traps (1) and immunoglobulin A proteases on the matrix surface cleave IgA (2). The thick ECM also prevents phagocytosis by blocking macrophage access to biofilm cells (3). Pairing this with lowered cell metabolism and protein synthesis the activity of antibiotics (4) on biofilm cells is minimal. Another important mechanism of resistance is eDNA that is incorporated into the biofilm matrix that binds β -defensin (5), reducing its antimicrobial properties. Finally, likely as a stress response, β -lactams and other antibiotics induce biofilm formation in many bacterial species (6). Flat-headed arrows indicate an inhibitory effect whereas pointed arrows indicate a stimulatory effect. Image was created using BioRender.com.

Most of our understanding of biofilms containing traditional COPD pathogens comes from otitis media (OM) as organisms such as *H. influenzae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *M. catarrhalis* have also been isolated from the middle ear (Bair and Campagnari, 2020). However, what is unclear is if these organisms behave in a similar manner within the considerably different environment of the COPD lungs. This highlights the current caveats in our understanding of the role of biofilms in COPD pathology.

1.4 Oral-lung axis

While the oral cavity and the lungs are often viewed as separate entities, they represent the beginning and end of the respiratory tract, respectively (Figure 1.7). The anatomical connection between the oral cavity and the respiratory tract provides plenty of opportunity for the oral microbiome to influence that of the lungs. The ability of the oral microbiota to take on a probiotic role is demonstrated by the ability of *Streptococcus salivaris*, an abundant oral commensal organism, to produce bacteriocins capable of inhibiting the respiratory pathogen *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Santagati et al., 2012). Recent studies have begun to describe a relationship between the oral cavity and the lungs in health and disease (Bassis et al., 2015, Pragman et al., 2019). The microbiome of the healthy oral cavity, as mentioned above, is dominated by genera such as *Streptococcus* and *Veillonella* (Zaura et al., 2009) which have also been shown to dominate the lung microbiome (Bassis et al., 2015). In 2011, Charlson *et al* showed that the lungs and oral cavity were homogenous with sequences recovered from the lungs being almost indistinguishable to those from the upper respiratory tract (Charlson et al., 2011). Despite these findings, oral contamination has been frequently identified as a limiting factor in accurately defining the lung microbiome. A study by Yu et al. (2016) overcame this issue by acquiring lung tissue samples during surgery on patients and compared these to healthy controls. Their findings suggest that the oral cavity and lungs had two distinct microbiomes. However, their study compared samples from patients with lung cancer which creates different microenvironments in the lungs, explaining microbiome variances (Liu et al., 2018).

Figure 1.7: The human respiratory tract. The human respiratory tract contains the lungs and the oral and nasal cavities. The openings to the respiratory tract are the oral and nasal cavities, which then lead to the trachea. The trachea then divides into two bronchi that further divide into multiple bronchioles before terminating in the alveoli. Image was created using BioRender.com.

Dysbiosis of the oral microbiome has been linked to oral disease (Zaura et al., 2017) which has also been shown to impact respiratory health. This supports theories that oral health has multiple systemic effects. For example, respiratory pathogens have been identified on dentures and in dental plaque (Didilescu et al., 2005, O'Donnell et al., 2016). Poor oral health impacts other conditions such as cardiovascular disease and arthritis (Li et al., 2000). The systemic effect of poor oral health can arise from several factors such as the spread of bacteria and their toxins (via microaspiration or through access to the circulatory system) or systemic inflammation caused by injury to in the oral cavity (Nazir, 2017). There is also the possibility that metabolites produced in the upper respiratory tract are transported into the lungs which also help to shape the lung microbiome.

Microorganisms can travel from the oral cavity to the lower respiratory tract with microaspiration and salivary flow being two major contributors to this microbe migration. Microaspiration transports airborne organisms as well as those in dental plaques into the

lungs. Healthy individuals possess the defence mechanisms necessary to minimise the adverse effects that may be caused by the inhalation of microorganisms. However, these are compromised in COPD sufferers, which decreases the likelihood of effective clearance of the airways (Beasley et al., 2012). It has been shown that the nasal microbiome has fewer similarities to the lung microbiome than the oral cavity (Bassis et al., 2015); suggesting microaspiration and salivary flow are majorly responsible for the similarities observed.

Segal and colleagues in 2016 described the significance of the oral-lung axis and how the migration of microbes from the oral cavity to the respiratory tract can influence inflammation in the lungs (Segal et al., 2016). Authors describe that lungs dominated by oral associated taxa present an inflammation phenotype dominated by Th-17 lymphocytes. The role of Th-17 cells in COPD is still under some debate due to conflicting findings but its role is becoming more apparent. However, common risk factors such as smoking result in the upregulation of Th-17 associated cytokines (Montalbano et al., 2015). Segal et al. (2016) attributed the increase in oral taxa found in the lung to microaspiration, a mechanism that occurs with increased regularity in lung diseases, including COPD (Segal et al., 2016, Cvejic et al., 2011). Based on the inconsistent findings of previous studies, at present it can be hypothesised that Th-17 cell upregulation may be present in a sub-population of COPD patients whose lung microbiome possesses a higher abundance of oral associated taxa.

1.5 OMICs in health and disease

With rapid advancements in the power, accuracy and availability of sequencing technologies, we can now answer previously unanswered questions in disease biology. However, these developments come with a production of substantial amounts of data that cannot be processed using past approaches. Therefore, to sieve through these large data sets, methodologies that are more appropriate must be employed. This method is known as bioinformatics, which utilises aspects of computer science, mathematics and biology to analyse and understand data produced via sequencing (Lederberg and McCray, 2001). Bioinformatics tools can be used as a high throughput and non-biased approach to provide an insight to complex biological processes using genomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics and proteomics. Due to the highly heterogeneous nature of COPD, patients with similar lung function impairment may respond differently to the same treatment regimen.

Therefore, using omics techniques to study disease mechanisms in fine detail can lead to the development of more efficacious treatment plans and better patient outcomes.

1.5.1 *Illumina sequencing*

Since the closing of production of Roche 454 pyrosequencers, Illumina sequencing platforms have been the main player in the world of NGS. Illumina sequencing platforms amplify at a shorter read length (approximately 350 bp) compared to others such as PacBio (approximately 40 kb). Based on a technique called ‘bridge amplification’, Illumina sequencing firstly immobilises sample DNA to a solid phase (glass coverslip) and generates up to 1000 copies in the near vicinity. Then using fluorescently labelled nucleotides (A, C, G and T), one base is added at a time then lasers excite the newly added bases and the sample is imaged using different filters, which can identify the newly added bases (Slatko et al., 2018). Illumina sequencing platforms can be applied to a range of different tasks including genomics and transcriptomics.

Currently the most used Illumina sequencing platforms are HiSeq and MiSeq with the latter being for smaller scale experiments and more financially viable for smaller research groups. Other platforms such as NovaSeq and NextSeq can be applied to more intensive tasks such as whole-genome and metatranscriptome sequencing. All Illumina sequencers possess high accuracy rate that has improved with each generation.

1.5.2 *Microbiome sequencing*

One of the most common applications of NGS technologies in disease biology in previous years has been sequencing the microbiome of a specific disease site. This can either be achieved through amplicon sequencing which amplifies highly conserved regions of DNA or through metagenomics which uses a ‘shotgun’ approach to sequence the entire DNA of a sample. Amplicon sequencing uses specific primers to sequence specific strands of DNA, most commonly DNA from the 16S ribosomal subunit hypervariable region (when detecting bacteria). These 16S regions are conserved among bacteria but vary enough to allow for discrimination between different genera and sometimes species. However, using mock bacterial communities, it has been shown that amplification of various regions along the 16S hypervariable region can result in the introduction of bias when identifying bacterial communities due to varying lengths of hypervariable regions which can influence the ability to correctly classify each sequenced read (Cai et al., 2013). Increasing read depth

could avoid this bias however this comes with the issue of increased error rates (Tan et al., 2019). Increased error rates occur as during sequencing, each newly introduced base is accompanied with an error rate that it could be an incorrect base (approximately 0.1% per base). Therefore, as the read length increases so does the likelihood that an incorrect base will be read during sequencing (Pfeiffer et al., 2018). Rather than amplifying specific DNA targets, shotgun metagenomics shears all extracted DNA from a sample into small fragments that are independently amplified. These fragments can then be aligned to a myriad of reference genomes to determine what is present in the sample (microbes and non-microbes alike).

Although powerful, both methods of microbiome sequencing come with their downsides. For example, compared to amplicon sequencing, data produced from metagenomics studies are large, complex and this can make it hard to determine what genome a fragment was derived from. While amplicon sequencing can address this issue, it is thought of as less accurate than metagenomics in that it cannot reliably identify microbiome members down to species-level (Liu et al., 2021b). As discussed in section 1.2.3 above, the microbiome in COPD has been investigated in several studies and genera such as *Haemophilus*, *Streptococcus* and *Moraxella* dominate (Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Mayhew et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2020b).

1.5.3 Transcriptomics

The transcriptome of a cell is defined as all of the mRNA transcripts within a cell and their quantity. This captures a snapshot of how a cell may be behaving at a certain developmental time point in a certain condition (Wang et al., 2009). The main aim from studies using transcriptomics is to compare a cell under controlled conditions to another in a 'disease like' state to identify changes in transcripts that may lead to development of a specific disease phenotype. Each cell type has its own distinct transcriptome, making the correct choice of cell for transcriptome sequencing experiments crucial (Consortium, 2015). Many transcriptome studies of COPD patients have highlighted the heterogeneity of the disease, failing to report a typical expression profile (Ghosh et al., 2016).

Transcriptomic studies on COPD patients focus on the host transcriptome, ignoring microbes. A limited number of studies, however, have aimed to characterise the metatranscriptome of the lung microbiome in COPD (Lee et al., 2016a, Ren et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2020b). Despite the infancy of metatranscriptomics as a technique, these studies have yielded promising results. The transcriptionally active portion of the lung

microbiome is shown to be considerably different to that of the total composition. For example, where microbiome sequencing identifies a low abundance of *Porphyromonas*, *Staphylococcus* and *Fusobacterium* whilst showing a dominance of *Prevotella*, metatranscriptomics reveals the opposite (Lee et al., 2016a).

1.6 Summary and aims

The information discussed in this general introduction outlines our current understanding of the clinical symptoms and microbiological factors behind COPD. The agreement in the literature is that the lung microbiome in both healthy individuals and those with COPD contains a degree of similarity to that of the oral cavity, implying that oral health may influence lung health and COPD presentations. Although there is a lack of agreement regarding this with conflicting findings in the literature, larger meta-analyses on the matter report that the oral health does affect COPD sufferers. There is also a consensus throughout the literature that concerning the lung microbiome in COPD, there is a substantial gap in our knowledge regarding its functionality that should be addressed.

The aims of this thesis were to firstly investigate current trends in the COPD literature relating to the microbiome, which allows for identification of past and current research trends, predict future trends but also identify current gaps in the literature than need to be addressed. Secondly, an *in silico* approach to characterising the lung microbiome in COPD and in health and identifying the areas in which they differ. These data can also be utilised to create a functional profile of the microbiome to identify potential driving mechanisms behind how the microbiome can influence COPD progression. Findings from this *in silico* analysis can then be used to inform the development and characterisation of a multi-species biofilm model. In short, the aim of this thesis was to: utilise *in silico* methodologies to inform the development of a biofilm model that is representative of the lungs in COPD which can be used to interrogate microbial interactions in the lung.

2 Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

2.1 Introduction

The microbiome of the lungs in health and disease continues to gain traction as an important area of research. However, compared to other body sites such as the oral cavity, the lungs can be difficult to acquire samples from (especially in healthy individuals) as the process of obtaining sputum or bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) is much more invasive than collecting oral swabs and rinses. Despite these hurdles, it is important to continue to study the importance and role of the lung microbiome in conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), as our understanding of this disease compared to others such as cystic fibrosis (CF) and asthma is still in its infancy. Since the first study on the lung microbiome in COPD in 2010, there has been a rapid influx of data and information into the public domain on this topic. However, the large amounts of data that accompany microbiome studies can make the task of collating results extremely difficult.

For example, the number of publications available in electronic format has increased dramatically in previous years, increasing from 27 million in 2017 (Koci et al., 2018) to over 33 million in 2021 (as advertised on PubMed.com as of December 2021). With this exponential increase in volume of scientific literature, it is becoming more difficult to stay up-to-date with the current literature in any field of research and effectively synthesise study findings. Therefore, it is important to develop methods by which we can manage the data that comes with this novel problem. Bibliometric and ontology-driven analyses have been described since the 1980s (Broadus, 1987). Now with improvements in technology and programming, we now have the ability to analyse large datasets of publications *in silico*, which would not have been previously possible. Ontologies are defined as a set of concepts or categories within a subject area and ontology-driven analyses provide a means by which to quantify and analyse the frequency that certain ontology terms occur within a certain field of research (Koci et al., 2018). Bibliometric analysis takes a similar approach to that of ontology-driven analysis but gives more emphasis to study metrics within an area of research. Study metrics of interest include, number of articles per year, average number of citations and collaboration networks (Lim and Buntine, 2016).

Ontology-driven analyses have become more popular methods to sieve through electronic data, especially in the domain of biological sciences (Bodenreider and Stevens, 2006).. There exist several ways by which one can analyse bibliometric data such as goldi (Cole et al., 2016), RISmed (<https://github.com/skoval/RISmed>) and seqenv (Sinclair et al., 2016).

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

However, the R package RISmed does not provide any ontological term extraction or analysis. Ontology based and bibliometric can be extremely useful analysis tools as the researcher can not only appreciate the history of a research area by identifying past trends in the literature but this information can also be used to predict future trends in this area. Approaches such as this provide the ability to examine large numbers of studies at once in a time efficient manner.

2.2 Aims and hypothesis

The microbiome of COPD has been an increasingly popular area of research in the past decade. This has led to reports of the composition of the lung microbiome changing throughout the course of COPD (e.g. during AECOPD) which indicate that the microbiome plays a role in disease progression. Therefore, this chapter aimed to:

- Use bioinformatic approaches to determine current and future trends in the lung microbiome literature concerning COPD, CF and asthma using bibliometric and ontology-driven approaches

It is expected that there will be considerably less microbiome studies in the field of COPD and that each disease group will favour separate, or groups of organisms. This bias is then expected to be reflected in the usage of select organism names.

This chapter has been written as a strategy to mitigate the impact that successive lockdowns during the COVID-19 pandemic had on access to laboratories.

2.3 Methods

2.3.1 Data collection

Searches using key words to find studies related to the COPD, Cystic fibrosis and Asthmatic lung microbiomes were performed. Search terms used and results are outlined in Table 2.1. Disease specific terms were linked to “microbiome” using the “and” Boolean term. Searches were performed on Clarivate Analytics Web of Science™ (WoS) for bibliometric analysis. All meta-data relating to each study was exported to plain text files. In the case where search results numbered over 500, search results were exported in batches of 500 and merged to create one master file. Final files were then imported into RStudio (version 1.2.5033) for analysis and visualisation.

For ontology-based analysis using pyTag, PubMed was utilised for data acquisition using the same search terms as before. After each search, all results were imported into separate EndNote (version 20.0.0.14672) libraries where citations were subsequently exported as BibTex files (which contained the article PubMed ID [PMID] and accession numbers, which are the required input information for the pyTag software).

Searches on both search engines returned articles related to the microbiome in asthma, CF and COPD spanning from 2004, 2008 and 2010, respectively to 2021. No start date in either literature search was specified. Each start year was the year of the earliest search result for each lung condition.

2.3.2 Bibliometric analysis

To carry out bibliometric analysis, the exported plain text files from WoS were imported into RStudio and analysed using the Bibliometrix package (version 3.1.4) (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017). Firstly, the `convert2df` function converts the exported plain text file to a data frame containing all study information such as authors, journal, total citations and author affiliations to name a few. This data frame was used as the basis for further analyses. Additional built-in functions of the Bibliometrix package were used to normalise and visualise data. Plots were then passed to the package `ggplot2` (version 3.3.5) for further manipulation. An outline of the bibliometric analysis pipeline is depicted in Figure 2.1.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

Figure 2.1: Bibliometric analysis pipeline by the Bibliometrix web application. An online database of the user's choice (which include PubMed, Scopus and Clarivate Analytics Web of Science, as shown in the figure) is used to identify studies of interest which are then exported from the database and imported to RStudio for normalisation, analysis and visualisation. (Aria and Cuccurullo, 2017).

2.3.3 *pyTag* annotation

Each BibTex file was processed using the *pyTag* software which can identify words in each study abstract using EXTRACT 2.0 (Pafilis et al., 2017). EXTRACT 2.0 identifies words related to 9 ontologies (Biological Process, Tissue, Chemical Compound, Disease, Genes/Proteins, Organism, Molecular Function, Cellular Component and Environment). *PyTag* extracts ontological terms from abstracts using PubMed IDs from a given directory and returns an abundance table of all identified terms from the desired ontologies and their associated search criteria. This abundance table can then be imported to RStudio for data visualisation and statistical analysis. Terms with a frequency below 5 were removed before analysis as done so previously (Koci et al., 2018). The *pyTag* workflow is described in Figure 2.2.

2.3.4 *Statistical analysis*

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

All graph production and statistical analysis was performed in RStudio. For ontology-driven analysis, term frequency was normalised to the number of articles for each condition in that specific year to correct for variations in the number of research articles published. Permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) and Kruskal-Wallis tests with Dunn's post-hoc comparisons tests were performed using the Vegan package and base functions in R, respectively, to identify terms that were significant between diseases and years. Difference between means was declared as significant when $P < 0.05$.

Figure 2.2: Comprehensive ontology-based analysis pipeline using pyTag software. Search results are first exported from the PubMed database to the citation manager EndNote and are then converted to BibTeX files. From these files, the pyTag software can extract the relevant information to download the relevant article abstracts and apply functions from the EXTRACT 2.0 software. This creates a two-dimensional abundance table containing all key ontology terms which can subsequently be imported into RStudio for data analysis and plotting (Koci et al., 2018).

2.4 Results

2.4.1 Initial search

All search terms were designed to query the trends and relevance of the microbiome in COPD and compare it to that of other relevant lung diseases in asthma and CF. In each disease, WoS returned more search results than the same search using the PubMed search engine. Search terms used and the number of articles returned are provided in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Search terms used to identify articles from the PubMed and Clarivate Analytics Web of Science™ databases.

Search Terms	Number of WoS Articles	Number of PubMed Articles
(COPD) AND (microbiome) NOT (Review)	283	227
(Cystic fibrosis) AND (microbiome) NOT (Review)	522	441
(Asthma) AND (microbiome) NOT (Review)	1249	773

2.4.2 Annual growth rates

Analysis of the annual growth rate of COPD and CF lung microbiome studies revealed a steady increase from 2010 and 2008, respectively, up until 2021 (Figure 2.3). A similar trend was observed for microbiome studies in asthma, but the increase was more dramatic with an average of 2 research articles per year published between 2004 and 2009. However, this increased considerably at the turn of the last decade, with an average of 72 articles published per year between 2010 and 2021. Despite none of the study areas of interest presenting a peak in scientific output in 2020/2021, outputs will undoubtedly increase in coming years based on the observed trends.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

Figure 2.3: Number of research articles per year. Number of articles published in the fields of COPD (blue), CF (purple) and asthma (yellow) microbiome research between 2004 and 2021.

2.4.3 Contribution to the field by country

To analyse contribution to the respective fields of interest by country, the country of the corresponding authors' affiliated institution was tallied (Figure 2.4). This revealed that studies predominantly originated from European, Asian, Oceanic, North, and South American countries that are denoted by the darker blue colouring in Figures 2.4A, 2.4C and 2.4E. A smaller proportion of studies originated from institutions in Africa which are represented by lighter blue shadings. More in depth analysis showed that although USA was the highest contributing nation, 79%, 77%, and 84% of outputs were single country publications (SCP; meaning only American institutions contributed to the work) for COPD, CF and asthma (Figures 2.4B, D and E), respectively. Similar trends were observed for all of the top contributing countries in all disease areas. However, for COPD outputs, all 3 of Ireland's outputs were multiple country publications (MCP), and 59% and 78% of publications from the UK and the Netherlands were published in collaboration with another country.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

Figure 2.4: Scientific contribution per country. Contribution per country towards lung microbiome research in COPD (A), CF (C) and asthma (E). Darker blue represent high levels of contribution whereas light blues indicate a smaller contribution towards scientific outputs. Contributions per were further broken down and classified as single or multiple country publications (SCP or MCP, respectively) for COPD (B), CF (D) and asthma (F).

2.4.4 *Identifying the top contributing authors*

Next, the contributions of individual authors to their respective fields were investigated by taking into account the number of research articles published per year and also the total number of citations they received each year (Figure 2.5). The size and colouring of each data point on the graphs correspond to the number of publications and total citations (TC) where larger and darker coloured data points represent a high number of publications and citations whereas small, lightly shaded data shows the inverse. In the area of COPD research (Figures 2.5A) the most productive author was Brightling CE who published 16 research articles that averaged 26 citations per article between 2015 and 2021. Although Brightling CE published the highest number of COPD microbiome papers, Huffnagle GB received the highest number of citations, receiving 1201 between 2010 and 2021, which corresponded to 133 citations per article. This indicates that trends in the COPD microbiome literature may stem from Huffnagle GB publications. Rogers GB and Lynch SV both published the highest number of articles in the fields of CF and asthma lung microbiome research (17 and 30, respectively).

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

Figure 2.5: Most productive authors over time. The contributions of authors in the fields of COPD (A), CF (B) and asthma (C) microbiome research were shortlisted. The nodes (circles) span from the first to most recent publishing year and are sized and coloured by the number of articles published and total citations (TC), where larger nodes represents higher numbers of articles published and a darker blue shading relates to more citations for the corresponding year.

2.4.5 Identifying literature trends by article keywords

To assess the content of the published research articles the most common keywords were extracted from each publication to observe their grouping and correlations (Figure 2.6). Node size is related to the number of related keywords and keyword themes that occur together frequently are grouped closer together. Each theme can be determined by the frequency of keywords as described by Aria and colleagues (Aria et al., 2022). In brief, 'basic' terms are those which occur frequently and consistently across the literature whilst 'motor' themes occur frequently with high density (i.e. large number of mentions in a short period of time). 'Niche' and 'emerging or declining' themes contain keywords that represent developed areas of interest and those that are not fully developed (which can either be attributed to them losing popularity or gaining popularity), respectively. Keywords in each theme are taken from the keywords provided by the authors when publishing manuscripts and nodes are named by the bibliometrix software.

'COPD' was identified as a 'basic' theme in the COPD literature that included keywords such as 'microbiome' and 'chronic obstructive pulmonary disease' which occurred 63 and 53 times, respectively (Figure 2.6A). The majority of remaining themes were classified as 'motor' or re-occurring themes which included 'infection', 'lymphocytes' and 'periodontal disease'. Keywords associated with 'infection', the largest of the motor themes include 'infection', 'antibiotics' and 'cytokines'. The theme 'biomass fuel' contained keywords that were split between basic and motor themes such as 'motor vehicle exhaust' and 'particulate matter'. As expected, basic themes identified in CF were 'cystic fibrosis' and 'lung microbiome' which contained keywords such as 'cystic fibrosis', 'dysbiosis' and 'microbiome'. In the CF literature, both 'bronchiectasis' and 'airway microbiome' were recognised as 'emerging or declining' themes but both contained keywords more closely related to infections such as 'biofilm', 'polymicrobial', 'bacteria' and 'fungi' (Figure 2.6B). The 'niche' themes 'microbiota' was found to contain many less commonly used keywords such as 'mycobiota', 'proteomics' and 'fungal infection' suggesting these themes are underrepresented in the CF microbiome literature. A similar trend was observed for asthma microbiome studies in that disease-specific keywords were classified under the basic theme, 'asthma' (Figure 2.6C). Another basic theme identified was 'inflammation', which included the keywords 'inflammation immunity' and 'cytokines'.. Finally, 'biomarkers' and 'bacteria' were branded as 'niche' and 'emerging or declining' themes, indicating their more infrequent use throughout the literature. Findings from Figure 2.6 help identify current trends in the literature and in all cases, there exists an expected and consistent use of disease and microbiome-specific keywords. There was also

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

a common trend of using keywords relating to individual organisms that were classed as emerging or declining themes. However, this does not specify if the frequency of these terms are increasing or decreasing.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

Figure 2.6: Most frequent key words in lung microbiome research in COPD, CF and asthma. Thematic map showing common keywords used in lung microbiome research articles relating to COPD (A), CF (B) and asthma (C). Node size and clustering is based off the co-occurrence of keywords and their frequency, respectively.

2.4.6 *Keyword analysis using pyTag*

Using Bibliometrix, trends were observed in the literature with regards to the use of keywords, but this analysis method was limited. Therefore, a more specialised software for keyword analysis was employed. The software pyTag provides a more in-depth appreciation for trends in the literature. This software extracts key words from article abstracts and divides them into 9, pre-defined, distinct categories: disease, environment, organism, tissue, biological process, molecular function, cellular component, chemical compound and genes/proteins. Of 1441 studies, 1236 abstracts were available and annotated. After processing and normalisation, 1607 terms were identified across all 9 ontologies. Using non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plots to view the distribution of studies based on use of all ontological grouping terms showed separation between COPD and CF studies from asthmatic lung microbiome studies (Figure 2.7). As done so previously, studies were split by year into early and late studies (Koci et al., 2018). Studies that were published between 2004 and 2014 were classified as early studies (ES; smaller nodes) and those published between 2015 and 2021 were categorised as recent studies (RS; larger nodes). Figure 2.7 shows a trend based on study publication year with RS grouping together. This suggests that there are now more common themes being explored in lung microbiome literature now than there has been in previous years.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

Figure 2.7: NMDS scaling reveals clustering of recent lung microbiome studies. Data points represent microbiome studies published in a single year with focus on one of three diseases. Point size corresponds to publication year, which is divided into early and recent studies (ES and RS, respectively). Early studies were published between 2004 and 2014 and recent studies range from 2015 to 2021.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

2.4.7 'Organism' related keyword quantification

Variance between data was seen to be significantly influenced by disease by PERMANOVA ($P = 0.001$). To investigate the underlying differences between these groups, the occurrence of individual ontology terms was quantified (Figure 2.8). Terms classified under the organism ontology was of high interest to the microbiome. The most frequently used terms in the organism ontology were 'human', 'bacteria' and 'mice', which were most commonly referred to in the CF and asthma literature. Despite their increasingly recognised importance in respiratory disease, the term 'fungi' only occurred once in the CF and COPD microbiome literature. Unsurprisingly, all mentions of '*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*' occurred in the CF search results. In the COPD literature, bacterial genera such as '*Streptococcus*', '*Lactobacillus*', '*Prevotella*' and '*Veillonella*' were frequently mentioned, indicating a strong influence of the oral microbiome on that of the COPD lung.

Figure 2.8: Most commonly used 'organism' ontology terms. The top 20 most commonly used terms in the 'organism' ontology classification across all years and disease searches.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

2.4.8 'Organism' related terms whose frequency differed between disease groups

More in-depth analysis of organism related ontology terms revealed significant differences in the use of some terminologies between diseases (Figure 2.9). As expected, the frequency of use of '*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*' and '*Staphylococcus aureus*' was significantly higher in CF than in COPD ($P < 0.0001$ and $P < 0.01$, respectively). Although the mention of 'fungi' was not significant between groups ($P > 0.05$), the mention of specific fungal genera was (*Candida albicans*; $P < 0.05$ and *Aspergillus fumigatus*; $P < 0.01$) with each keyword occurring significantly more frequently in both asthma and CF (in the case of '*Aspergillus fumigatus*' and in CF only (in the case of '*Candida albicans*'). There were no organisms in the COPD literature that were referred to more than in CF or asthma studies, indicating possible bias towards certain organisms in these diseases.

Figure 2.9. Barplots indicate the normalised frequency of each 'organism' ontology term in each disease. Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn's post-hoc test was used to compare the frequency of each term in cystic fibrosis and asthma to that of COPD (*; $P < 0.05$, **; $P < 0.01$, ***; $P < 0.001$, ****; $P < 0.0001$).

2.4.9 Temporal changes in 'organism' ontology terms

After correcting for the number of article published each year, it remains evident that the CF microbiome literature favours *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* (Figure 2.10). In recent years, there is an increase in the number of references to the gut microbiome in COPD and asthma microbiome articles. Based on these data, it is expected that the number of articles with focus on the gut microbiome in the fields of COPD and asthma research will increase in coming years. The same can also be said of *P. aeruginosa* in the CF literature. However, the frequency of *S. aureus* in CF microbiome literature decreased in 2021, signifying a favouring of *P. aeruginosa*.

Figure 2.10: Temporal changes in the use of 'organism' ontology terms. Line plots show the changes in the rate of use of keywords that fall under the 'organism' ontology between 2004 and 2021. Asthma; yellow line, Cystic fibrosis (CF); purple line and Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD); blue line.

2.4.10 Quantification of ontology terms related to biological processes

A key aspect of investigating the role of the microbiome in health and disease is also revealing the functionality of the microbiome. Therefore, the frequency of ‘biological process’ ontology terms was also investigated (Figure 2.11). The most commonly used term is ‘pathogenesis’ which was mentioned 78 times. Key terms such as ‘immune response’, ‘inflammatory response’ and ‘cytokine secretion’ are most commonly seen in microbiome studies of asthmatic patients (which are mentioned with a frequency of 46, 22 and 13, respectively). Even though the issue of chronic and long-term bacterial colonisation in COPD patients is well documented, ‘biofilm formation’ is only mentioned in the CF literature 9 times and not at all in COPD studies. From Figure 2.11 it is clear that the use of biological process ontology terms in the COPD microbiome literature are noticeably lacking and the majority these terms are identified in CF or asthma microbiome studies.

Figure 2.11: Most commonly used ‘biological process’ ontology terms. The top 20 most commonly used terms in the ‘biological process’ ontology classification across all years and disease searches.

2.4.11 'Biological process' related terms that can differentiate disease groups

Further analysis of 'biological process' ontology terms revealed only significant differences in some microorganism pathogenesis and host response pathways (Figure 2.12). Virulence associated processes such as 'biofilm formation', 'quorum sensing' and 'virulence' were mentioned more in CF microbiome research than in COPD ($P < 0.001$, $P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.0001$, respectively). Although the occurrence of 'virulence' was higher in asthma research than in COPD ($P < 0.001$), 'quorum sensing' was mentioned significantly more in COPD microbiome articles ($P < 0.01$). As expected, the frequency of terms such as 'sensitisation' and 'hypersensitivity' were significantly higher in asthma microbiome research ($P < 0.0001$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively).

Figure 2.12: Comparison of the use of "biological process" ontology terms between disease groups. Barplots indicate the normalised frequency of terms in the 'biological process' ontology in each disease. Kruskal-Wallis was performed with Dunn's post-hoc comparison. The frequency of each ontology term in cystic fibrosis and asthma groups were compared to the frequency of the same term in the COPD group (*; $P < 0.05$, **; $P < 0.01$, ***; $P < 0.001$, ****; $P < 0.0001$).

2.4.12 Temporal changes in ‘biological process’ ontological terms

When taking the same look at ‘biological process’ ontology terms (Figure 2.13), there are no clear trends in the literature apart from the number of occurrences of ‘growth’ which tended to increase over time in the CF literature. A recent and steep increase in the frequency of ‘sensitisation’ in asthma microbiome articles also indicates a possible future trend in the literature. All other terms increased and decreased regularly, demonstrating interest in areas lung microbiome research related to ‘cytokine secretion’, ‘quorum sensing’ and other varies regularly. Taken together, findings from Figures 2.8 to 2.13 indicate that, unlike in CF, the COPD and asthmatic lung microbiome literature does not favour a particular organism and that there is a gap in the lung microbiome literature regarding the functionality of the microbiome and that more interest is given to host-microbiome interactions.

Figure 2.13: Temporal changes in the use of ‘biological process’ ontology terms. Changes in the rate of use of ‘biological process’ keywords from 2004-2021. Asthma; yellow line, Cystic fibrosis (CF); purple line and Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD); blue line.

2.5 Discussion

Due to continuous decreases in price of NGS, the ability for more and more research groups to undertake these types of studies is increasing. Therefore, we now find ourselves in a unique situation where there is almost an overabundance of information on a myriad of research subjects. Although having access to large amounts of data and information is of benefit, it can be difficult at times to keep up-to-date with current trends and to avoid the introduction of bias when reading singular research articles at a time. Using bibliometric and ontology-based analyses can help minimise these downfalls. The analysis of this chapter aimed to use these analysis methods to identify how COPD microbiome research has matured since the first publication in 2010 and compare these findings to that of other respiratory diseases.

Assessing the increase of overall scientific production of literature pertaining to COPD, CF and asthmatic lung microbiome research between 2004 and 2021 showed a steady increase in the number of COPD microbiome articles between 2010 and 2021 as shown by Figure 2.3. A similar rate of increase was seen for asthma microbiome studies with a sharp increase in production rates between 2014 and 2021. This is likely a result of multiple factors such as decreasing sequencing costs, leading to increase accessibility to NGS technologies. In the field of COPD microbiome research, although Huffnagle GB had not published the highest number of articles, they were undoubtedly the highest cited and had been publishing in the field regularly since 2010. This indicates that articles published by Huffnagle GB and their research group and collaborators may well be responsible for setting trends in the COPD microbiome literature. A reason for this could be that Huffnagle GB was the corresponding author on the first true, microbiome research article on the COPD lung, leading to views that their research group are ‘trendsetters’ in the COPD microbiome literature (Erb-Downward et al., 2011).

Bibliometric analysis can also provide insights to keyword usage. Taking findings from Figure 2.6, COPD specific terms such as ‘chronic obstructive pulmonary disease’ were the most widely used but also those relating to ‘bacterial infection’. These keywords are more specific to singular bacterial pathogens such as ‘*Haemophilus influenzae*’ and ‘*Moraxella catarrhalis*’. However, it is not clear whether these are emerging or decreasing trends. Similar findings were observed in the CF and asthma search results where both showed high frequency of disease specific keywords with other themes containing keywords related to individual pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Keywords related to

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

'biomass fuel' were also identified due to links between COPD progression and exacerbation with air pollution (Doiron et al., 2019). The oral microbiome has been a frequent subject of debate relating to its importance in respiratory disease such as COPD, leading to the identification of 'periodontal disease' as a re-occurring theme (Gaeckle et al., 2020, Segal et al., 2013, Öztekin et al., 2014). Although there is still some work to be done to solidify the claims that periodontal disease can aggravate COPD symptoms, two early pilot studies and a recent RCT described a significant reduction in exacerbation frequency and improvement in lung function following periodontal therapy (Zhou et al., 2014, Sundh et al., 2021, Kucukcoskun et al., 2013). Segal and colleagues in 2016 also reported an increase in Th17-mediated inflammation in patients with a microbiome dominated by oral associated bacteria, a trait commonly seen in COPD patients (Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Pragman et al., 2012, Segal et al., 2016, Silva et al., 2020). These findings highlight the importance of understanding the role of the oral cavity as a reservoir of infection in COPD patients.

A limitation of using the Bibliometrix package for analysing the use of keywords is that it does not clarify if key terms are parts of current or previous trends. Therefore, a tool more suited to this type of analysis was used. Using pyTag, the entire abstract of each identified study was interrogated and words relating to one of 9 separate categories were listed for analysis. As shown in Figure 2.7, when taking keywords from all ontology terms, distribution of studies published before 2014 (referred to as early studies) is more widespread and recent studies, regardless of disease, cluster closer together. This indicates there is a relative consensus on research themes throughout the lung microbiome research community. Similar findings have also been reported by Koci *et al* who observed the same clustering of recently published articles in gastrointestinal disease (Koci et al., 2018).

Using microbiome related ontology terms such as 'organism' and 'biological process' the most frequently used terms across all disease types were listed as shown in Figures 2.8 and 2.9. After the general terms 'human', 'bacteria' and 'mice', the most commonly used term was '*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*' which was unsurprisingly used solely in the CF literature. *P. aeruginosa* has long been implicated as the dominant pathogen in CF infections (Malhotra et al., 2019). The gut-lung axis in respiratory disease has been a topic of interest in recent years, particularly in COPD, explaining why 'gut microbiome' is more frequently mentioned in COPD microbiome studies.

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

It is becoming increasingly apparent that we must now be asking questions regarding the functionality of the microbiome in health and disease and not just listing the inhabitants. Therefore, as mentioned above, the top 20 keywords in the 'biological process' ontology were quantified. However, commonly used terms such as 'immune' and 'inflammatory response' indicate that studies tend to favour host-microbiome interactions compared to assessing the microbiome functionality. There exists some mention of terms that can be applied to bacterial processes such as 'biofilm formation', 'quorum sensing' and (although it is a general term) 'pathogenesis'. Despite their mention, terms such as these are more commonly used in the realm of CF and asthma than in COPD signifying a current gap in our understanding of the microbiome in COPD patients.

As shown in Figures 2.10 and 2.12 there are no 'organism' ontology terms that occur more frequently in COPD microbiome studies than in CF or asthmatic studies. This is somewhat surprising considering the attention normally given to opportunistic respiratory pathogens such as *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Moraxella catarrhalis* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* in the COPD literature as key pathogens in both stable and exacerbated COPD (Sethi et al., 2002, Sethi and Murphy, 2001, Huang and Boushey, 2015). A small number of mentions of *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* was observed in the COPD literature beginning in 2014 and leading into 2021, however this only peaked at 2 mentions per annum. Comparing the frequency of 'organism' ontologies in COPD microbiome studies to that of asthma or CF indicates the possibility of more interest being placed on the identification of individual organisms in the microbiomes of CF or asthma patients. Additionally, due to previous beliefs that fungi were nothing more than innocent bystanders in the COPD lungs (Pendleton et al., 2017), the frequency at which '*Aspergillus fumigatus*' (and 'fungi' for that matter), is expectedly low. However, recently the lung mycobiome in COPD has been identified as being dominated by *Candida* and filamentous fungi such as *Aspergillus* and plays a key role in influencing patient morbidity and mortality (Tiew et al., 2020). Therefore, with this finding it is probable that the rate at which fungal related keywords in the COPD microbiome literature will increase in coming years.

Other than the noticeable increase in the mentions of '*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*' and 'gut microbiome' in the CF and asthma microbiome literature, from Figures 2.12 and 2.13 it is difficult to make predictions on future trends in lung microbiome research. However, it should be noted that the mention of many terms in both the 'organism' and 'biological process' ontology classes in the COPD literature was blatantly absent. Although placing favouritism on a particular organism in microbiome studies may not be advisable as it may

Bibliometric and ontology-based analysis of the COPD microbiome literature

overshadow novel findings, a more focused approach to characterising the functionality of the microbiome but also investigating the host-microbiome interactions in COPD should be attempted in the following years.

Overall, the data presented above describes bias towards certain organisms in lung microbiome studies, as well as highlighting caveats in COPD microbiome studies to date. This shows that COPD microbiome studies largely focus on documenting the members of the lung microbiome rather than investigating how those members are behaving. Some studies have begun to address this issue using meta-transcriptomics, which demonstrate the transcriptionally active portion of the lung microbiome in COPD can be vastly different to results returned by metagenomics (Lee et al., 2016b, Wang et al., 2020b).

2.6 Key findings:

- The use of bibliometric and ontology-driven analyses should not be overlooked in disease biology. It can not only be a useful tool in identifying current and future trends in the literature but also indicate caveats in the current landscape of the field.
- Compared to the CF microbiome, articles published on the COPD microbiome do not place favouritism on individual bacterial genera or species.

Future COPD microbiome studies should aim to replicate what has been done in the fields of CF and asthma lung microbiome research and begin to investigate the functionality of the lung microbiome.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

3 Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

3.1 Introduction

Typically, a research project begins with the conceptualisation of a research question or hypothesis, followed by securing funding and finally, data collection and analysis.

However, an alternate research method is the analysis of publicly available data, also referred to as secondary data analysis (Ruggiano and Perry, 2019). Though it does not come without its disadvantages, secondary analysis of publicly available data is becoming a more popular method for maximising outputs from every aspect of research. The obvious advantage of secondary data analysis is decreased cost. Analysing pre-gathered data cuts out data acquisition steps, which can often be expensive and laborious. Multiple, similar data sets can also be combined to strengthen findings of past studies or answer questions that were previously unanswered such as in the case of meta-analyses. However, normally the researchers who are performing the secondary analysis are not the ones who took part in the original study, meaning they are unaware of any issues that may have arose in the initial study which could be vital to proper analysis (Cheng and Phillips, 2014). Clear record keeping from the original study is also vital to effective secondary analysis which may not always be the case and therefore limits the analysis depth of the secondary researchers.

With the ever-increasing ease of access to next generation sequencing (NGS) methods, any researcher with experience in genetic research will have interacted with the sequence read archive (SRA). The SRA is housed and maintained by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ). Data from published NGS studies is deposited with the SRA, making it publicly available to download for secondary data analysis. These data can be used for other studies that will have a bigger impact than the initial study and can only lead to the advancement of our understanding of the subject of interest.

As the third most common cause of death worldwide (WHO, 2020) it is crucial that we understand the role of the microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). This creates an opportunity to utilise publicly available COPD microbiome data to shine a light on the role of the microbiome in the pathogenesis of the disease. Several studies have been published that have sought to define the microbiome of COPD patients. The findings of these studies agree and report compositional changes in the microbiome of COPD patients to healthy controls (Cameron et al., 2016, Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Wang et al., 2019, Pragman et al., 2012). Differences in microbiome have also been

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

observed when comparing stable and exacerbated COPD (Wang et al., 2016, Williams et al., 2018, Jubinville et al., 2018). These findings suggest that the airway microbiome plays a key role in the pathogenesis of COPD. The role that the microbiome plays in the progression of COPD is multifactorial as it can influence host susceptibility to infection as well as airway inflammation and immune system regulation (Wang et al., 2017, Dickson et al., 2014b). The microbiome of the healthy lungs resembles that of the oral cavity (Bassis et al., 2015). This remains consistent in COPD (Erb-Downward et al., 2011), however, there is also an increase in abundance of genera associated with respiratory infections such as *Haemophilus*, *Moraxella*, *Staphylococcus* and *Pseudomonas* (Cameron et al., 2016, Wang et al., 2017, Wang et al., 2016, Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2015).

Despite our current understanding of the COPD microbiome growing, there are still some caveats to our knowledge. This is exemplified by contradicting findings regarding bacterial diversity in the lungs. Erb-Downward et al. (2011) reported decreased diversity in the lungs of mild and moderate COPD patients. However, other studies have noted an increase in bacterial diversity in comparison to health (Sze et al., 2012a). Analyses from the previous chapter identified caveats in the current literature in that published studies are severely lacking in functional analyses of the microbiome. A limited number have investigated the metatranscriptome of the lung microbiome however, this technique is in its initial stages (Lee et al., 2016a, Ren et al., 2018). Studies to date have been limited by geographic location combined with no existing standardised analysis methods for microbiome data. This has complicated the task of testing hypotheses across all studies and homogenising data on a large scale.

Meta-analysis has previously shown its potential to identify consistencies across studies as well as identifying disease specific microbiome signatures, furthering our understanding of the role the microbiome plays in health and disease at an unprecedented rate (Duvall et al., 2017, Wirbel et al., 2019). The continuously increasing amount and availability of COPD microbiome datasets creates a unique opportunity to combine our existing knowledge to explore, in more detail, the potential mechanisms of involvement of the microbiome in disease progression.

3.2 Aims and Hypotheses

The lung microbiome is an increasingly popular area of research. Therefore, the aim of this chapter was to gain a more in-depth understanding of the composition of the lung microbiome in COPD.

Therefore, this chapter aimed to:

- Download raw 16S sequencing data from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and re-analyse it using a standardised pipeline. ENA was selected as their servers are located closer to secondary analysis location, therefore allowing for quicker download speeds.
- Characterise the lung microbiome in COPD and how it differs from that of the lung microbiome in healthy individuals
- Address the gaps in the literature that were reported in the previous chapter by identifying the functional signature of the microbiome in COPD to reveal potential mechanisms that may reveal its role in disease progression

It is hypothesised that this chapter will identify the ‘typical’ lung microbiome in COPD. This can, following further analyses, provide a complex of genera that can be used to aid diagnosis of COPD or in the identification of patients who may be at risk. Additionally, it is expected that functional analyses will reveal enriched bacterial pathways that would indicate mechanisms behind how the microbiome contributes towards inflammation in COPD. An overview of the workplan is summarised in Figure 3.1.

Work from this chapter has been presented at the following conferences:

BREATH Annual conference, July 2021 (Virtual; oral presentation)

British Thoracic Society Winter Meeting, November 2021 (Virtual; oral presentation)

Title: “Comparison of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and in health: an in silico study”

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Figure 3.1: Graphical abstract of meta-analysis pipeline. Firstly, a literature search was performed to identify potential studies (A). Raw data from relevant studies were downloaded and subjected to standardised quality control measures before being mapped to a taxonomic database at 97% confidence (B). After OTU picking, analyses were then performed to identify differences in OTU diversity (C), functional profiles (D) and ability to distinguish between COPD and control microbiomes using machine learning approaches (E).

3.3 Materials and methods

3.3.1 Search criteria and study collection

Keyword searches were performed on PubMed as done in previous meta-analyses (Bisanz et al., 2019, Duvallet et al., 2017), which are provided in Table 3.1. Search results were filtered to exclude any study published before 2012, and remaining studies were exported to the reference manager EndNote (version X8). 2012 was selected as a cut-off point with the intentions of only including studies that contain sequencing data of a high enough quality that would allow for secondary analysis. Search terms used aimed to firstly select for microbiome and NGS studies and then additional search terms were added using the “AND” function to further narrow search results down to those performed on the lungs in healthy patients and in those suffering from COPD.

Table 3.1: Keyword searches performed to identify lung microbiome studies focusing on COPD and healthy lung.

Condition	Search Used
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	((microb* OR bacteri* OR archea* OR fung* OR mycob*) AND (structure OR composition OR diversity OR community) AND (sequencing OR metabarcoding OR amplicon OR metagenom* OR 16S OR “ITS”)) AND ((lung) AND (COPD) OR (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) NOT (review))
Healthy lung	((microb* OR bacteri* OR archea* OR fung* OR mycob*) AND (structure OR composition OR diversity OR community) AND (sequencing OR metabarcoding OR amplicon OR metagenom* OR 16S OR “ITS”)) AND ((lung) AND (health*) NOT (review))

3.3.2 *Study inclusion and exclusion criteria*

All PubMed search results were exported to EndNote and upon exportation, study titles and abstracts were screened for relevance and shortlisted. Studies were excluded if they were not related to the lungs in health or in COPD or if they were not NGS studies (i.e. did not target the entire genome or 16S rRNA/ITS region).

Shortlisted studies were interrogated in the style of a scoping review and relevant information related to shortlisted studies was recorded. This relevant information included study details which may influence the microbiome or downstream data analysis such as sampling method, number of cases, number of controls, GOLD status, smoking status, additional cohorts, DNA extraction method, next-generation sequencing platform, primer sequences and region of 16s rRNA/ITS targeted. We also included the data accession number and DOI, where possible, for further data retrieval. Shortlisted articles were then subjected to a scoring system where they could earn up to 5 points. A study was awarded one point if the answer was 'yes' to these questions: Is the sequencing data available? Is basic meta-data available (i.e. healthy or COPD sample)? Can the basic meta-data be mapped to the individual sequencing runs? Is additional patient meta-data available (i.e. age, GOLD status, smoking status and sex)? And can the additional meta-data be mapped to the individual sequencing runs? These parameters were designed to quickly and effectively classify studies which provide sufficient data of a high enough quality to be included in the final analysis.

Minimum requirements for studies to be included in final analyses was for sequencing data to be available and for basic patient meta-data to be mappable to the sequencing data. Authors were contacted to request sequencing data accession numbers in the cases it was not provided and were given 1 month to respond before excluding the study from final analysis.

3.3.3 *Data retrieval and processing*

Available data were downloaded directly from the ENA database using SRA accession numbers as identifiers before quality control protocols were carried out using a standardised pipeline in Qiime2 (Bolyen et al., 2019). Primers and barcodes were removed

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

from reads where possible using cutadapt before trimming poor quality reads to a minimum length of 100bp. Paired end reads were merged when possible if the overlap was >50 bases and reads were assigned to operational taxonomic units (OTUs). OTU clustering was performed via the closest referenced method using the usearch function available through vsearch within the QIIME2 environment. Reads were clustered using the Silva and GreenGenes databases at 97% confidence, subsequently the GreenGenes OTUs were copy number normalised before Picrust was utilised to infer the metabolic potential.

Individual runs, which are individual samples from each of the studies retrieved, were discarded if the total read depth was below 500 reads. Features were then filtered if they appeared less than 10 times in less than 4 studies.

OTUs were normalised by centre log2 ratio (CLR) transformation of OTUs for further analysis. Filtered reads were utilised for alpha diversity measures.

Dr Christopher Delaney from the University of Glasgow performed data retrieval and processing whilst providing valuable help and insight into further analyses.

3.3.4 Microbiome diversity and composition analyses

Analyses were performed on all studies collectively and on a per-study basis. The built-in estimate_richness function in the phyloseq package (v1.30.0) was used to calculate Shannon and Simpson diversity indices and Chao1 estimates (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). Alpha diversity metrics were then visualised in ggplot2. The base function aov was used to perform a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test for statistical significance between presence of COPD and alpha diversity matrix. ANOVA results were viewed using the TukeyHSD function.

Beta-diversity distances were calculated using the distance function to calculate Jensen-Shannon, Bray-Curtis, Jaccard, Euclidean distance measures while the built-in phyloseq::UniFrac function was used to determine weighted and un-weighted Unifrac measures. Beta-diversity distance matrices were arranged as principle coordinate analysis (PCoA) plots using the ape (analyses of phylogenetics and evolution) package in RStudio (Paradis and Schliep, 2018). PCoA plots were then visualised using ggplot2.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Average OTU abundance was calculated in RStudio by calculating abundance as a percentage of total OTUs. The nine most abundant phyla and genera were shortlisted and the remaining phyla and genera were listed as 'other'.

3.3.5 *Random forest classifiers and linear discriminant analysis*

For random forest classifiers, 3 case-controlled studies were selected as training datasets and the test set was comprised of the remaining studies. OTUs at varying depths as well as CLR normalised OTUs using two different normalisation methods were used as predictor variables for healthy/disease cases. Random forest models were built using the randomforest package and receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curves were built based on random forest models using pROC and ggROC packages (Breiman, 2001, Robin et al., 2011). The most important features were extracted from random forest models by ranking mean decrease gini scores and plotted using ggplot2. To determine the metabolic potential of the lung microbiome of COPD patients, important CLR normalised OTUs from the PICRUSt database were matched to the KEGG database to inform on the functionality of microbiome datasets. Important features were identified by their gini scoring from the random forest models as described above. Enriched metabolic pathways were drawn using the clusterProfiler package in R (Wu et al., 2021).

Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) was performed in the microbial package (<https://github.com/guokai8/microbial>) in RStudio using the ldamarker function. LDA scores were plotted using the plotLDA function in the same package using a cut-off score of 4 to determine important genera.

3.3.6 *Statistical analysis*

All statistical analyses and graph production were performed using the appropriate functions in R (version 4.1.2) unless stated otherwise. Statistical significance was determined when $P < 0.05$.

3.4 Results

3.4.1 Study collection and characteristics

Firstly, search terms described in Table 3.1 were used to search for relevant studies. Terms were used to search for microbiome studies and then filter for publications specific to COPD or healthy lungs. These searches returned 189 COPD and 498 healthy lung studies which were then assessed for relevance. 621 studies were excluded due to not being relevant to study aims. This included excluding review articles, animal studies and any non-NGS studies, leaving a total of 66 studies (50 COPD and 16 healthy lung studies). Of the 66 relevant studies, 52 either didn't provide access to raw sequencing data or insufficient patient meta-data. Following interrogation, 14 studies provided sufficient patient meta-data to be included in final analyses. Of these 14 studies, 11 were COPD and 3 were healthy lung microbiome studies. After the gathering of relevant COPD and healthy lung microbiome studies relevant study information was noted (Figure 3.2 and Table 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Study acquisition pipeline. Searches returned a total of 687 results, of which only 14 studies met the inclusion criteria.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

All studies produced an adequate read depth per sample following quality assurance (Figure 3.3). Despite differing in study design, all COPD studies produced, on average, between 1000 and 100,000 reads per sample, excluding Cameron *et al* 2016 (a metagenome study) which left ~200 reads per sample. Generally, studies focusing solely on the healthy lung produced between 10 and 150 reads per sample.

Figure 3.3: Average number of reads per sample. The average number of identified reads per sample in each study were quantified from the 'raw' and unfiltered OTU tables.

1 Table 3.2: Shortlisted study characteristics

Study ID	Condition	Controls	N Controls	Cases	N Cases	Extraction Method	Platform	Region	Data Score
Aguirre, 2015	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	19	ND	454	V1-V3	0
Bouquet, 2020	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	200	Zymobiomics	MiSeq	V4	0
Cabrera-Rubio, 2012	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	8	Qiagen	454	V1-V3	2
Cameron, 2016	COPD	Healthy Smokers	10	COPD	8	FastDNA	HiSeq	NA	4
Cui, 2015	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	56	Phenol/Chloroform	Ion Torrent	18s, ITS	3
Diao, 2018	COPD	Healthy	19	COPD	40	Qiagen	454	V3-V5	0
Dicker, 2018a	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	99	AllPrep	MiSeq	V3-V4	3
Dicker, 2018b	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	141	AllPrep	MiSeq	V3-V4	3
Diver, 2020	COPD	Asthma	63	COPD	78	ND	454	V4-V5	0
Einarsson, 2016	COPD	Healthy	19	COPD	18	FastDNA	MiSeq	V1-V2	3
Engel, 2017	COPD	Healthy	9	COPD	16	AllPrep	454	V6-V9	2
Erb-Downward, 2011	COPD	Healthy	10	COPD	4	MagNA	454	V1-V3	0
Filho, 2019	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	112	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	3
Garcia-Nunez, 2014	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	17	Qiagen	454	V1-V2	1

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Garcia-Nunez, 2017	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	21	Qiagen	454	V1-V3	0	
Huang, 2015	COPD	COPD Stable	12	AECOPD	12	ND	NA	16S	0	
Huang, 2014	COPD	COPD Stable	12	AECOPD	12	ND	MiSeq	V4	0	
Jubenville, 2018	COPD	COPD Stable	9	AECOPD	9	MO BIO	454	V6-V8	2	
Kim, 2017	COPD	Healthy	26	COPD	13	PowerWater	454	16S	0	
Lee, 2016	COPD	COPD (GOLD 2)	4	COPD (GOLD 3)	4	Phenol/Chloroform	Next Seq	V4	3	
Liu, 2020	COPD	Healthy	26	AECOPD	41	Total Nucleic Acid	Ion Torrent	V4	0	
Lopez Caro, 2019	COPD	COPD Stable	55	AECOPD	55	MagNA	MiSeq	V3-V4	0	
Mac-Aogain, 2020	COPD	Healthy	13	COPD	41	PowerWater	HiSeq	WGS	1	
Mayhew, 2018	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	101	MagNA	MiSeq	V4	3	
Mika, 2018	COPD	Healthy	10	COPD	32	Qiagen	454	V3-V5	1	
Millares, 2014	COPD	COPD	14	AECOPD	15	Qiagen	454	V1-V3	1	
Millares, 2015	COPD	COPD	8	AECOPD	8	Qiagen	454	V1-V3	1	
Millares, 2019	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	72	Qiagen	MiSeq	V3-V4	1	
Molyneaux, 2013	COPD	Healthy	17	COPD	14	Qiagen	454	V3-V5	0	
Navratilova, 2016	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	126	PathogenFree	PyroMark	V1	0	
Pragman, 2012	COPD	Healthy		COPD	22	Phenol/Chloroform	454	V3	0	
Pragman, 2019a	COPD	COPD (IE)	11	COPD (FE)	11	PowerSoil	MiSeq	V4	0	

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Pragman, 2019b	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	15	PowerSoil	MiSeq	V4	2	
Qi, 2020	COPD	Non-Eosinophilic AECOPD	31	Eosinophilic AECOPD	26	PowerSoil	HiSeq	V3-V4	0	
Ren, 2018	COPD	Healthy	9	COPD	25	ND	HiSeq	V3-V4	5	
Rutebemberwa, 2014	COPD	Healthy and Cystic Fibrosis	9	COPD	26	Qiagen	454	V1-V2	1	
Segal, 2017	COPD	Placebo	10	Treatment	10	ND	MiSeq	V4	1	
Sinha, 2018	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	4	PowerSoil	MiSeq	V3-V4	1	
Su, 2015	COPD	NA	NA	AECOPD	6	Forensic Extraction Kit	HiSeq	V4, ITS	2	
Sun, 2020	COPD	AECOPD	15	AECOPD Recovery	15	Qiagen	454	V4-V5	3	
Sze, 2012	COPD	Healthy	24	COPD	8	Qiagen	454	V1-V3	0	
Sze, 2015	COPD	Healthy	4	COPD	5	ND	454	V3-V5	1	
Sze, 2016	COPD	NA	NA	COPD	21	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	3	
Tangedal, 2017	COPD	Induced Sputum	30	Spontaneous Sputum	30	FastDNA	MiSeq	V3-V4	1	
Tangedal, 2019	COPD	COPD	36	AECOPD	36	FastDNA	MiSeq	V3-V4	0	
Wang, 2016	COPD	COPD	87	AECOPD	87	Qiagen	454	V3-V5	3	
Wang, 2018	COPD	COPD	281	AECOPD	281	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	4	
Wang, 2019	COPD	Healthy	16	COPD	43	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	4	
Williams, 2018	COPD	COPD	127	AECOPD	127	MagNA	MiSeq	V4	0	
Xu, 2018	COPD	HIV Negative	48	HIV Positive	28	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	3	

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Bassis, 2015	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	28	PowerSoil	454	V3-V5	3	
Beck, 2015	Healthy	Healthy	86	HIV Positive no lung disease	56	ND	454	V1-V3	0	
Bittinger, 2014	Healthy	Healthy	35	Lung Transplant	55	PowerSoil	454	ITS1, ITS2	2	
Charlson, 2011	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	6	PowerSoil	454	V1-V2	0	
Charlson, 2012a	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	6	PowerSoil	454	V1-V2	0	
Charlson, 2012b	Healthy	Healthy	6	Lung Transplant	23	PowerSoil	454	V1-V2, ITS	0	
Dickson, 2015	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	15	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	2	
Dickson, 2017	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	8	ND	MiSeq	V4	3	
Ibironke, 2020	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	6	Phenol/Chloroform	MinION	ND	3	
Lee, 2019	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	24	Roche	MiSeq	ND	3	
Martin, 2013	Healthy	NA	NA	NA	NA	ND	NA	ND	0	
McTaggart, 2019	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	89	PowerSoil	MiSeq	ITS1, ITS2	3	
Morris, 2013	Healthy	Non-smokers	45	Smokers	19	ND	454	V1-V3, V3-V5	0	
Rylance, 2016	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	44	Qiagen	454	V1-V3	3	
Segal, 2016	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	49	Qiagen	MiSeq	V4	1	
Wang, 2019	Healthy	NA	NA	Healthy	115	PowerSoil	HiSeq	V4	0	

1 Rows ending in red indicate the study was not included in the final analysis whereas rows ending in green denote studies that were included.

2 COPD; chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, AECOPD; acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, NA; not applicable, ND; not disclosed, IE; infrequent
3 exacerbator, FE; frequent exacerbator, HIV; human immunodeficiency virus.

4

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Relevant information of the remaining studies was collected which gave 3372 samples. This showed that study design varied greatly from study-to-study, including sequencing platform, DNA extraction method and 16S target region (Figure 3.4). The V4 region was the most commonly targeted region of the 16S hypervariable region. Although most samples were sequenced using the Illumina MiSeq platform, Roche 454 pyrosequencing was the most used platform throughout studies as shown above in Table 3.2. Samples predominantly came from across the UK, USA and Canada.

Figure 3.4: Study characteristics. Samples were broken down by country of origin, study type, extraction method used, sequencing platform and 16S target region.

3.4.2 Microbial diversity within the COPD microbiome

Following sequencing data being downloaded from the ENA database and data processing, OTUs were clustered on 97% similarity using the Silva database. Following this, beta diversity was measured which can be used to visualise the similarities and distances between samples. Data points showed substantial amounts of variation based on author and 16S sequencing region. The observed variance can be attributed to study specific effects (Figure 3.5). As done so by previous studies, analyses were performed at the genus level to alleviate these effects (Duvall et al., 2017, Wang et al., 2020b). No clear separation of data points based on disease status was observed (Figure 3.5A). However, when coloured by 'Study ID', data points clustered more closely together based on the study (Figure 3.5B). Other aspects of study design such as country, extraction method and 16S target region displayed a degree of grouping but not to the same degree as 'Study ID' (other beta-diversity measures are provided in Appendix i).

Figure 3.5: Principle co-ordinate analysis of microbiome samples by disease status and study. Data points are coloured by disease status (A) or by study (B) provides evidence for study specific factors influencing the outcome of lung microbiome studies.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Next, the alpha-diversity of the microbiome, a subject of debate in recent years, was assessed (Figure 3.6). Alpha-diversity of microbiomes were measured using Shannon, Simpson and Chao1 diversity indices. The Shannon and Simpson diversity indices reflect OTU richness and evenness, respectively (as the number of OTUs increase so does the Shannon index and the Simpson index increases when OTUs are more evenly distributed) (Shannon, 1948, Simpson, 1949). The Chao1 index estimates the total number of OTUs in a sample based on the low abundance of OTUs (Chao, 1984). From this analysis it is clear that changes in alpha-diversity is not consistently altered in COPD. 289 (283 to 295) OTUs were observed in COPD compared to 281 (261 to 301) in healthy controls ($P > 0.9$). Additional measures of alpha-diversity (Shannon, Simpson and Chao1 indices) were also calculated but revealed no significant differences. Shannon (3.3 [3.2 to 3.4] vs 2.7 [2.7 to 2.8], $P = 0.1$) and Simpson (0.88 [0.87 to 0.89] vs 0.8 [0.79 to 0.81], $P = 0.06$) indices showed slight but not statistically significant decreases in species evenness and richness between health and disease. No significant differences in the Chao1 index between COPD and healthy patients was observed (411 [403 to 419] vs 381 [355 to 406], $P = 0.08$).

Figure 3.6: A α -diversity of the healthy and COPD lung microbiomes. The number of observed OTUs as well as Chao1, Shannon and Simpson diversity indices were calculated, demonstrating a decrease in microbiome richness and evenness in COPD. No statistical significance was observed when comparing healthy and diseased samples following one-way ANOVA and Tukey's *post hoc* test. Upper and lower horizontal lines represent the upper and lower quartiles, respectively. Horizontal lines in the middle of the boxes represent the mean, whiskers (vertical lines outside each box) show data distribution beyond the upper and lower quartiles and individual dots represent outlier datapoints.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

3.4.3 Community composition in the COPD lung

The relative abundances of the most prevalent phyla and genera were then quantified (Figure 3.7). On average, Firmicutes were the most abundant phylum accounting for over 75% of the microbiome in some COPD cases (Figure 3.7A). This was followed by Proteobacteria (increased in COPD) and Bacteroidota (increased in health). *Veillonella* is the most abundant genera across all samples followed by *Streptococcus* (Figure 3.7B and Figure 3.8). There was also a noticeable increase in the abundance of *Haemophilus* in COPD samples when compared to healthy. A considerable amount of 'other' genera comprise a large percentage of the total composition which is representative of the increased (but not significant) alpha diversity in healthy cohorts.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Figure 3.7: Relative abundances of the most abundant phyla and genera in COPD and healthy patients. The abundances of the top 9 most abundant phyla (A) and genera (B) are presented as a percentage of the total counts. All other phyla and genera that were not in the top 9 were listed as 'Other'. Sample are split by presence of COPD where 'Yes' corresponds to the presence of COPD whereas 'No' means the absence of COPD.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Figure 3.8: Summary of most abundant genera in COPD and in health. The top 5 most abundant genera in health (represented in the 'No' column, referring to no COPD) compared to COPD (represented by the 'Yes' column).

3.4.4 *The lung microbiome as a predictor of COPD*

To investigate whether the lung microbiome could be used as an alternative method of diagnosing COPD, random forest analysis was performed (Figure 3.9). Random forest classification was performed using the silva database using two methods of CLR OTU normalisation (OTUs, and OTUs_2), confined to genus and species-level (Genus and Species) and using the KEGG orthologies (KO). Random forest modelling is a machine learning technique which utilises many decision trees to predict the grouping of unlabelled samples which is therefore more accurate than individual decision trees (Denisko and Hoffman, 2018). Three case-controlled studies were selected as training datasets and the remaining studies were used to test the finalised model. Using each method, the model was able to correctly predict disease status 100% of the time (area under the curve [AUC] = 1.0). When testing the remaining data, using KO and the first CLR normalisation method proved to be the least effective (AUC = 0.58 and 0.64, respectively). This was in contrast to confining data to the genus level which resulted in the a prediction success rate of 86% (AUC = 0.86). All AUCs from random forest methods are summarised in Table 3.

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Figure 3.9: Receiver operator characteristic curves in the classification of lung microbiomes. Curves built at genus-level (Genus), using KEGG orthologies (KO), CLR normalisation of Genera (OTUs and OTUs_2) and as species-level (Species) are represented by red lines. Probability of chance (AUC = 0.5) is represented by the grey dashed line.

Table 3.3: Area under the curve produced by each set of random forest test data

Method	AUC (training data)	AUC (test data)
Genus	1.00	0.86
KO	1.00	0.58
OTUs	1.00	0.64
OTUs_2	1.00	0.74
Species	1.00	0.74

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Several genera were identified as being important in the models based on Gini scoring which is a quantifiable measure of how important each variable is to the accuracy of the model (Figure 3.10). Genera of note which are commonly implicated in respiratory infections were *Streptococcus*, *Haemophilus* and *Moraxella*. *Haemophilus* and *Streptococcus* had the highest Gini scores of 0.95 and 1.45, respectively which corresponds to a higher importance in the random forest modelling.

Figure 3.10: Most important genera use in classifying COPD and healthy lungs. The most influential OTUs on the outcome of the random forest analysis as shown by their mean decrease gini score across all healthy and COPD datasets.

Despite the identification of important genera, solely relying on Gini scores does not provide insight into the direction of their importance (i.e. do they occur more often in healthy patients or in those with COPD?). Therefore, LDA was performed to clarify this (Figure 3.11). LDA is a dimension reduction tool which focuses on identifying variables that maximise the separability between two groups. This identified all genera which had an LDA score above 4 or below -4 (LDA cutoff scores of 4 and -4 were chosen to identify highly important features in distinguishing healthy microbiomes from that of COPD

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

patients). Negative scores indicate a genera was more enriched COPD patients whereas enriched genera in health were given positive scores. Opportunistic pathogens such as *Haemophilus* and *Moraxella* were enriched in COPD along with *Streptococcus*. Genera such as *Pseudomonas*, *Staphylococcus*, *Porphyromonas* and *Prevotella* were all enriched in healthy samples.

Figure 3.11: Linear discriminant analysis displaying the genera that best classify health and disease. Cut-off points of -4 and 4 were set to identify the genera that were most enriched in health and disease. COPD enriched bacteria (blue) are designated negative values and health enriched bacteria (yellow) are given positive scores.

3.4.5 Functional annotation of the COPD microbiome

As identified in the previous chapter, functional analyses of the microbiome in COPD is lacking. Therefore, to address this OTUs from the PICRUSt database were matched to their corresponding KEGG orthologies (Figures 3.12 and 3.13). This revealed highly significant enrichment of bacterial two-component systems, indicating a microbiome that is highly responsive to its surrounding environment ($P < 0.005$). Two other pathways of note that were highly enriched were bacterial secretion systems and biofilm formation in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ($P < 0.005$). Biofilm formation was also found to be associated

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

with two-component system enrichment, pointing towards the possibility that biofilm formation is in response to the lung environment.

Figure 3.12: Significantly enriched pathways in the lung microbiome. Enriched functional pathways that can be matched to key members of the lung microbiome. All pathways presented were significantly enriched ($P < 0.05$).

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Figure 3.13: Network displaying connectivity of significantly enriched pathways. Enriched pathways are shown as nodes (circles) and nodes of related function are connected via edges (lines). Central pathways are coloured in red and related pathways are coloured in blue and labelled with associated KEGG identifier.

3.5 Discussion

This chapter presents one of the first meta-analyses performed on the lung microbiome in COPD. The theory that the lung microbiome plays a role in the progression of COPD is becoming more widely accepted, meaning that there is now a need to understand this microbiome in more detail. This chapter sought to do just this by performing a large-scale meta-analysis on publicly available lung microbiome data from COPD patients, using healthy lung microbiome studies as control patients.

Initial findings from literature searches identified large variances in study design, likely contributing to the large-scale data heterogeneity observed in Figure 3.5. To account for these variances analyses were limited to the genus-level. However, at present, there are no methods to effectively account for study specific batch effects in NGS studies. To best mitigate these effects, analyses were largely confined to the genus level as done so in previous studies (Bisanz et al., 2019, Duvallet et al., 2017, Wang et al., 2020b).

As shown by Figures 3.4 and 3.5, the studies analysed within this chapter varied greatly in design. The Illumina MiSeq platform was the most used sequencer across all samples. This comes down to the age of the studies included in the final analysis. The oldest study included was from 2015 while production of Roche 454 pyrosequencers halted in the same year and support for the platforms ended in 2016. While the V4 region of the 16S hypervariable region was the more frequently targeted across all samples, multiple other regions were also targeted. Variability in other aspects of study design such as extraction method was also identified. Different extraction methods have previously shown to bias certain bacteria and the same can also be said of 16S target region (Cai et al., 2013, Han et al., 2019). This variability appeared to contribute considerably towards the distribution of data points in Figure 5. When coloured by the 'Study ID', data points from the same study grouped more closely together compared to the grouping observed when coloured by individual variables (e.g. extraction method and 16S region. Data shown in appendix). This points towards a combination of study specific attributes influencing the outcome of COPD lung microbiome studies and not one specific factor such as 16S target region as previously stated (Wang et al., 2020b, Bisanz et al., 2019).

Although no statistical significance was observed in Figure 3.6, the microbiome of COPD patients was seen to be less diverse than that of healthy individuals with Simpson and Shannon diversity index values slightly decreasing compared to healthy controls. This

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

decrease in alpha-diversity has been reported in other COPD microbiome studies and suggests the introduction of new bacteria but also the overgrowth of others as a result of poorer bacterial clearance mechanisms (Wang et al., 2019, Einarsson et al., 2016). This decrease in species richness and evenness is a trait that is also reported during gut disease (Mosca et al., 2016). Findings reported by Einarsson et al. (2016) and Wang et al. (2019) suggesting that the composition of the microbiome in COPD differs to that in health were confirmed in Figures 3.7 and 3.8. These findings showed that genera such as *Veillonella* and *Prevotella* dominated the healthy lung microbiome as well as that of COPD patients. While the relative abundance of *Veillonella* remained high, the abundance of *Prevotella* decreased, likely providing an opportunity for opportunistic respiratory pathogens such as *Haemophilus* and *Moraxella* to increase. The abundance of *Streptococci* also increased in COPD. This is likely a shift at the species level with a decrease in commensal *Streptococci* spp. such as *S. mitis* and an increase in more virulent species such as *S. pneumoniae* (Wang et al., 2020a).

As reported previously by Bassis and Segal, the oral cavity plays an important role in shaping the lung microbiome and its inflammatory response (Bassis et al., 2015, Segal et al., 2013, Segal et al., 2016). Results presented above support these findings by showing high abundances of both commensals and PPMs associated with the oral cavity. As there is a wide range of PPMs that can be identified in the lungs of COPD patients this highlights the need to study the roles of other PPMs in COPD other than the classic trio of *Haemophilus*, *Moraxella* and *Streptococcus*.

Although lacking significant differences in alpha-diversity and no distinct clustering, there are clear compositional differences in healthy and COPD microbiomes. These compositional differences provided enough information to effectively classify healthy and diseased microbiomes with up to 86% accuracy, indicating the possibility of using the microbiome as a diagnostic tool in the future. Several genera were identified as having a larger influence on the outcome of the random forest classification than others. The functional profile of these important features did point towards mechanisms that could drive host inflammation as well as chronic bacterial colonisation in the COPD lung. *P. aeruginosa* biofilm formation pathways were significantly enriched which could drive long-term persistence within the lung while acting as a reservoir for repeat infection. In Figure 3.13, this was connected to the two-component system pathway, a method by which bacteria can sense and interact with the external environment (Tiwari et al., 2017). This suggests bacteria in the COPD lung actively respond to the surrounding environment and

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

likely form biofilms as a response. The pathway corresponding to bacterial secretion systems was also significantly enriched. Secretion systems in bacteria are commonly implicated in virulence and can be used to inject/secrete toxins and virulence factors into adjacent cells and the surrounding environment (Depluvere et al., 2016, Green and Meccas, 2016). This indicates a mechanism by which the lung microbiome can drive inflammation in COPD.

Although the identification of important features through random forest classifiers sheds a light on key genera in the lung microbiome, it does not provide information regarding whether these genera are more commonly found in COPD or in health. Therefore, the LDA performed in Figure 3.10 helps answer this question. This can be used to determine what features are enriched in each condition and which provide the largest amount of separation between the two groups. This analysis showed that not only are oral-associated bacteria such as *Prevotella* and *Porphyromonas* enriched in health but so are opportunistic pathogens such as *Staphylococcus* and *Pseudomonas*. Whilst these are enriched in health, it is important to note that they are also found in the COPD lungs as previously reported (Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2015, Millares et al., 2019, Bafadhel et al., 2011). Findings from the same figure also reinforce findings from previous studies that *Haemophilus*, *Moraxella* and *Streptococcus* are enriched in the COPD lung. Taken together, findings from Figures 3.9, 3.10 and 3.11 show that the use of the entire microbiome to aid in the diagnosis of COPD may be of relevance. This proved more accurate than using a smaller panel of genera as Wang *et al* whereby they used a panel of 12 genera including *Haemophilus*, *Prevotella*, *Porphyromonas* and *Streptococcus* produced a random forest model (Wang et al., 2020b).

The data presented above shows that differences in individual study design likely contribute considerably to the outcome of the analyses performed above. Therefore, in future, researchers should carefully consider experimental design before embarking on a microbiome study of the COPD lungs. This will allow for data to be more accurately combined in future meta-analyses. This chapter also indirectly shows the importance of more closely regulating the data deposition from NGS studies. This is highlighted by the number of studies, in both health and disease searches that had to be excluded from final analyses due to insufficient meta-data or simply due to authors not providing data access. Although recently journals have been policing this more closely, the issue persists. Those in the scientific community must therefore hold each other accountable to ensure data is deposited to relevant online repositories and is done so to a suitable standard. This can then allow for future meta-analyses to be performed, which have previously been shown

Meta-analysis of the lung microbiome in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

to have the potential to considerably improve our understanding of the microbiome in disease biology.

In conclusion, this chapter has provided an accurate and in-depth account of the microbiome in COPD and described compositional differences between health and disease in the absence of significant differences in overall diversity. This chapter has also assigned a functional signature to the COPD microbiome which highlights mechanisms that could be interrogated in future studies to further our understanding of how the microbiome influences the outcome of COPD patients.

3.6 Key Findings

- NGS data deposition should be closely monitored in future to improve the quality of future meta-analyses
- A combination of study-specific factors contributes to data clustering rather than disease status
- An in-depth analysis of the COPD microbiome identifying no significant differences in alpha-diversity
- The COPD microbiome is dominated by genera associated with the oral cavity
- The functional signature of the COPD microbiome reveals mechanisms that would contribute to the inflammatory profile within the lungs

Developing an informed biofilm model

4 Developing an informed biofilm model

4.1 Introduction

COPD is a chronic condition affecting the respiratory system. It is characterised by the progressive decline in lung function and airflow (Su et al., 2015). COPD is estimated to affect over 200 million people worldwide and 2% of the UK population (roughly 2 million people). COPD has recently become the 3rd leading cause of mortality worldwide (WHO, 2018) as a result of continued exposure to risk factors such as cigarette smoke and an aging and increasing population (Mathers and Loncar, 2006).

Pathogenic biofilms are often associated with chronic disease and often complicate treatment strategies due to their recalcitrant nature (Bjarnsholt, 2013). At present, there is a considerable lack of biofilm-orientated studies in the field of COPD despite evidence in the literature pointing towards their presence. This was confirmed in previous chapters where there was no mentions of biofilms in the COPD microbiome literature despite studies indicating the presence of biofilms in COPD and others reporting long-term bacterial colonisation (Murphy et al., 2004, Murphy et al., 2005). Most pathogenic organisms identified in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) such as *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Moraxella catarrhalis* are also implicated in otitis media and the majority of knowledge of bacterial biofilms in COPD has been extrapolated from this (Bair and Campagnari, 2020, Hall-Stoodley et al., 2006, Thornton et al., 2011). However, these biofilms are not grown under COPD-specific conditions, therefore results should be translated into the context of COPD with caution.

Due to relying on culturing techniques to identify microbiological inhabitants of the human respiratory tract, healthy lungs were considered to be sterile and only during disease would they harbour bacteria. Now, with recent and rapid advances in culture independent techniques, it is now known that the bronchial tree is not a sterile site during health or disease and that the oral cavity is a major source of lung associated microbes (Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Bassis et al., 2015). Among other potentially pathogenic microorganisms (PPMs), oral pathogens have previously been identified in bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) and sputum samples of healthy individuals (Segal et al., 2016, Ibrinke et al., 2020) which is referred to as a pneumotype with high levels of supraglottic taxa. This pneumotype is also associated with inflammation of a Th17-lymphocyte phenotype. Increased presence of oral taxa may provide insight into the mechanisms behind increased levels of Th17 cells in COPD patients (Xu et al., 2019). Organisms migrate from the oral cavity to the lower respiratory tract via microaspiration, meaning genera such as *Streptococcus* can be found readily within the lungs of most individuals. Due to the

Developing an informed biofilm model

importance of the oral cavity in influencing inflammation within the lung and its microbiome, *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* were of particular interest based on findings from the previous chapter. *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis*, have both been commonly identified together in the oral cavity as well as within the lung microbiome of COPD patients (Wang et al., 2020b). The former is associated with increased hospital stays and worse clinical outcomes for COPD patients, while the latter is increased in COPD lungs exhibiting eosinophilic inflammation (Narewski et al., 2015, Wang et al., 2021, McCormack et al., 2015).

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Lung microbiome studies largely focus on the bacteria that inhabit the lungs and exclude the fungal microbiome (mycobiome). The inhalation of fungal spores is unavoidable (Chotirmall et al., 2013) and other fungi such as *Candida* species have been identified in several body sites such as the oral cavity and the respiratory tract (O'Donnell et al., 2015, Peters et al., 2012a). As mentioned previously, microorganisms regularly migrate from the oral cavity and through the respiratory tract. *Candida* was recently reported as the most dominant fungal genera in the COPD lungs (Tiew et al., 2020). Fungi and bacteria readily interact with one another in several disease sites such as *Aspergillus* and *Pseudomonas* in cystic fibrosis or *Candida* and *Streptococcus* in dental caries (Peters et al., 2012a). These interactions often result in increased tolerance to antimicrobials, increased virulence and biofilm formation resulting in chronic colonisation and infection.

Despite several studies reporting on the composition of the lung microbiome in COPD, there remains some disagreements regarding this topic. Data presented in Chapter 3 address this issue and shows bacteria associated with the oropharyngeal space tend to dominate the COPD lungs. This includes bacteria such as *Prevotella*, *Veillonella*, *Porphyromonas*, *Streptococcus* and *Staphylococcus* which play a key role in distinguishing healthy from COPD microbiomes. Therefore, it is important to understand how the interactions between fungi and these bacteria within the COPD lung can affect patient outcomes.

4.2 Aims and hypotheses

Despite evidence in the literature pointing towards the presence of biofilms in the COPD lung, there is a distinct lack of publications concerning this. Most knowledge with regards to biofilms formed by COPD pathogens is taken from the context of otitis media. On top of this, even though the lungs are described as having a diverse mycobiome, the role of fungi in COPD is often overlooked. Therefore, this chapter aimed to:

- Develop a multi-species biofilm model containing fungi and bacteria that is informed by findings of the previous chapter and COPD mycobiome studies
- Characterise the biofilm model and assess susceptibility to commonly used COPD antimicrobials
- Determine how antimicrobial therapies alter the immunogenicity of the biofilm

From our understanding of biofilms, it is hypothesised that antimicrobial therapies will not eradicate all biofilm cells but merely lower the biomass. Multi-species biofilms are expected to elicit an immune response in epithelial cells. This immune response is then predicted to be exacerbated following antimicrobial treatments as when antibiotics are ineffective at killing bacteria, they can respond via the production of immunomodulatory factors or by forming biofilms.

Work from this chapter has been presented at the following conference:

BREATH annual conference, July 2019, Belfast, Northern Ireland

Title: "Developing a multi-species biofilm to study COPD"

4.3 Materials and methods

4.3.1 Microbial storage and standardisation

Candida albicans SC5314, *Staphylococcus aureus* NCTC 10833, and *Porphyromonas gingivalis* W83 were used in this study. *C. albicans*, *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* were grown on Sabourauds Dextrose (SAB) agar (Thermo Fisher, UK), Columbia blood agar (CBA; Thermo Fisher), and fastidious anaerobe agar (FAA; E&O laboratories, UK) respectively and stored at 4 °C.

To prepare overnight broths of each microorganism, one colony of *C. albicans* was suspended in Yeast Peptone Dextrose (YPD) media (Thermo Fisher) and incubated in an orbital shaker at 200 rpm and 30 °C. *P. gingivalis* was propagated in Schaedler's media (Thermo Fisher) and incubated overnight in anaerobic conditions. Luria Bertani broth (LB, Thermo Fisher) was used to grow overnight broths of *S. aureus* at 37 °C. Overnight cultures were washed by centrifugation and subsequent re-suspension in Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS, Sigma-Aldrich, UK). Anaerobic bacteria were adjusted to 0.2 OD₅₅₀ and *S. aureus* were diluted to 0.6 OD₆₀₀, respectively. *C. albicans* cells were counted on a haemocytometer and all organisms were diluted to desired concentration in assay specific media.

4.3.2 Media preparation

Todd Hewitt broth (THB, Sigma Aldrich) was prepared and supplemented with 10 µM menadione and 4 mg/mL hemin (Thermo Fisher) and mixed 1:1 with RPMI (Sigma-Aldrich, referred to sTHB from herein).

4.3.3 Biofilm growth and analysis

Following counting of fungus and standardisation of bacteria, all cells were added to sTHB media to give a final concentration of 1×10⁶ CFU/mL. All biofilm assays were carried out in accordance with the minimum information guidelines for growth of biofilms in microtiter plates (Allkja et al., 2020). Biofilms were grown by adding 200 µL of inoculated growth media to desired wells of a microtiter plate and incubating the plate at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ for 24 h. Following the incubation step, biofilms were washed with PBS. Biofilms were then stained with 0.05% crystal violet (CV) to quantify total biofilm biomass. CV stain was incubated on biofilms for 20 min at room temperature and excess dye was removed with H₂O. Bound dye was released using 100% ethanol and absorbance of the ethanol was

measured at 570 nm. Single and multi-species biofilms were imaged using an EVOS cell imaging system (Thermo Fisher) at 40x magnification.

4.3.4 DNA extraction and purification

Multi-species biofilms were grown on polymer coverslips before removing biomass in an ultrasonic water bath at 35 kHz for 15 min in 1 mL PBS (Fisher Scientific, UK). The Qiagen DNA mini-kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) was used to extract DNA from biofilm cells. Firstly, cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 13,000 rpm for 10 min and the pelleted cells were suspended in 180 μ L ATL buffer and 20 μ L of 20 mg/mL proteinase K and incubated for 1 h at 56 °C. Each sample was then transferred to 1.5 mL screw-cap tubes containing 0.5 mm sterile glass beads. Samples were mechanically lysed in a 24-sample BeadMill (Fisher Scientific) set to perform 3 x 30 second cycles at 4000 rpm with a 1 min break between each cycle. Samples were incubated with 200 μ L AL buffer for 10 min at 70 °C. 200 μ L ethanol was then mixed with each sample before adding to the QIAmp spin columns. To bind DNA to the spin columns, the samples were incubated at room temperature for 5 min before centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 1 min, flow-through was discarded and the spin column was placed in a new collection tube. 500 μ L of wash buffer AW1 was added to the spin columns, which were centrifuged for 1 min at 7000 rpm and the flow-through was discarded. Again, the spin-columns were placed in new collection tubes, before adding 500 μ L AW2 buffer to each, which were centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 3 min. To ensure the spin column filters were dry, spin-columns were added to new collection tubes and centrifuged again at the same speed for 1 min. The lids of 1.5 mL DNase free tubes were removed to hold the spin columns and 50 μ L AE buffer was added directly on to the column filter. Samples were allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 min before centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 1 min to elute the DNA. To maximise DNA recovery, the previous step was repeated with a second 50 μ L aliquot of fresh AE buffer. DNA samples were stored at -20 °C until required.

4.3.5 Biofilm composition analysis

Quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) was used to quantify the number of fungal and bacterial cells within each biofilm. Briefly, DNA was extracted from biofilm cells as described above and 1 μ L of extracted DNA was added to a PCR mastermix containing Fast SYBR Green Master Mix, 10 μ M species-specific forward and reverse primers (sequences provided in Table 4.1) and nuclease free H₂O. qPCR was then carried out using a Step-One

Developing an informed biofilm model

plus real time PCR machine (Life Technologies, Paisley, UK). The following thermal profile was used: 50 °C for 2 min, 95 °C for 2 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95 °C for 3 s and 60 °C for 30 s. Colony forming equivalents (CFE) were calculated compared to a standard curve of serially diluted DNA of each species as previously described (O'Donnell et al., 2016).

Table 4.1: Primers used to identify biofilm organisms and measure gene expression

Target Organism	Forward Sequence (5' - 3')	Reverse Sequence (5' - 3')	Reference
<i>Candida albicans</i>	GAGCGTCGTTTCTCCCTCAAACCG CTGG	GGTGGACGTTACCGCCGCAAGCAA TGTT	(Kean et al., 2017)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	ATTTGGTCCCAGTGGTGTTGG GTAT	GCTGTGACAATTGCCGTTTG TCGT	(O'Donnell et al., 2016)
<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	GGAAGAGAAGACCGTAGCACA AGGA	GAGTAGGCGAAACGTCCATCA GGTC	(Sherry et al., 2016)
<i>IL8</i>	CAGAGACAGCAGACACACAA	TTAGCACTCCTTGCCAAAAC	(Ramage et al., 2012)
<i>GAPDH</i>	CAAGGCTGAGAACGGGAAG	GGTGGTGAAGACGCCAGT	(Ramage et al., 2012)

4.3.6 Visualisation of inter-kingdom biofilm interactions

C. albicans was standardised to 1×10^6 cells/mL as described above and biofilms were grown in chamber slides (Thermo Fisher) for 2 h at 37 °C to induce hyphal formation. Bacteria were standardised to approximately 1×10^8 cells/mL, stained with 1.5 mM hexidium iodide (Fisher Scientific) and incubated at 37 °C for 1h. Bacterial cells were pelleted by centrifugation and washed twice with PBS. *Candida* biofilms were washed with PBS following initial incubation. Bacterial cells at 5×10^7 cells/mL and 1.5 mM calcofluor white were added to the chamber slide for a further hour at 37 °C. Biofilms were then washed twice with PBS and imaged using an EVOS cell imaging system. Calcofluor white (CFW) and hexidium iodide fluorescence was detected at excitation/emission wavelengths of 357/447 and 531/593 nm, respectively before overlaying the images.

4.3.7 Visualising multi-species biofilms

Biofilms were grown for 24 h in 8-well chamber slides (ibidi, Martinsried, Planegg, Germany). Each well of the chamber slides was coated with poly-D-lysine for 20 min at 37°C and washed with PBS before addition of the biofilm inoculum. Following biofilm growth, cells were washed with PBS and stained with a fungal specific probe for 2 h at 37°C. The fungal probe was removed before adding a mixture of two bacterial probes (one specific for Gram-positive bacteria and another specific to Gram-negative bacteria) for 10 min at 37°C (Akram et al., 2018, Mills et al., 2021, Baibek et al., 2021). The fluorescent probes were removed and 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) was used to fix the biofilms for 20 min. PFA was removed and 200 µL PBS was added to each well and biofilms were imaged using a confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM; Leica DMI 8). The final concentration of each probe was 10 µM.

Microbe-specific probes were synthesised by Ms Assel Baibek of the University of Edinburgh.

4.3.8 Antimicrobial compounds

Voriconazole and amoxicillin were dissolved in 100% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) as 10 mg/mL and 25 mg/mL stocks, respectively and both were stored at -20°C. Erythromycin stock solutions were prepared in 100% ethanol to a concentration of 50 mg/mL and stored at -20°C.

4.3.9 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of single and multi-species communities

Planktonic minimum inhibitory concentrations (PMIC) were determined using the CLSI broth microdilution method by testing relevant organisms in single species suspensions and as a triple-species inoculum (CLSI, 2021). Concentrations of all antimicrobial drugs ranged from 32-0.0633 µg/mL. The point where no growth was observed was listed at the PMIC. Due to its fungistatic properties, the concentration where voriconazole inhibited 50% of microbial growth was deemed the PMIC. This was assessed by measuring the absorbance of treatment wells and comparing it to that of untreated controls at 570 nm.

Sessile minimum inhibitory concentrations (SMIC) were established for single and multi-species communities. To test for SMICs biofilms of single species biofilms, biofilms were grown as described above and treated with serially diluted drugs of interest (erythromycin and amoxicillin; 64-0.125 µg/mL and voriconazole 128-0.25 µg/mL) alone and in

Developing an informed biofilm model

combination for 24 h. Following treatment, biofilms were incubated with resazurin diluted to 0.001% in sTHB as described above. The minimum concentration of antimicrobial required to reduce the metabolic activity of the biofilm to 20% or less of the untreated control was recorded as the $SMIC_{80}$. When treating dual and tri-species biofilms, all drugs were diluted to 128 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as done so in a previous study of a similar nature and sTHB containing 0.001% resazurin was used to determine the reduction in biomass compared to untreated biofilms of the same composition (Townsend et al., 2017). Biofilms were incubated with the resazurin sodium salt for 2 h.

4.3.10 Oral epithelial cells exposed to biofilm supernatants

Frozen stocks of TR146 cells were seeded at 1×10^5 cells/mL in keratinocyte serum-free medium (KSFM) in 75 cm^3 cell culture flasks (Corning, New York, USA). KSFM was supplemented with 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin, 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ bovine pituitary gland extract, 0.2 ng/mL epidermal growth factor and 0.4 mM CaCl_2 and incubated at 37°C with 5% CO_2 . Cells were maintained until 70-80% confluency was achieved. Upon reaching desired confluency levels, cells were passaged using 0.05% trypsin.

After passaging, cells were counted and seeded in 24-well microtiter plates at 1×10^5 cells/mL and incubated under the same conditions until they reached 70-80% confluency at which point cells were washed gently with pre-warmed PBS three times. Cell-free supernatants from mature multi-species biofilms +/- antimicrobial treatments were mixed 1:1 with supplemented KSFM and added directly to TR146 cells. Negative controls contained KSFM only.

4.3.11 Gene expression in epithelial cells

RNA from TR146 cells was extracted using the RNeasy Mini Kit following exposure to spent biofilm supernatants harvested from treated and untreated biofilms (Qiagen, Crawley, UK). TR146 cells that weren't exposed to biofilm supernatants were also extracted from as negative controls. Firstly, cell media was removed and cells were suspended in 350 μL RLT lysis buffer supplemented with 0.01% (v:v) β -2-mercaptoethanol (β 2ME) for 30 secs. An equal volume of 100% ethanol was then added to the lysed cells. 700 μL of sample was then added to RNeasy spin columns and centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 15 secs. Flow-through was discarded and 700 μL RW1 buffer was added to each sample before centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 15 secs. Flow-through was discarded and 500 μL of RPE buffer was added

before centrifuging again for 15 secs at 7000 rpm. The previous step was then repeated with an extended centrifugation step of 2 min. RNA was then eluted from the spin column into an RNase-free 1.5 mL tube using 50 µL RNase-free H₂O by centrifuging at 7000 rpm for 1 min. RNA was stored at -80 °C.

Extracted RNA was quantified using a NanoDrop 1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher) and 100-250 ng of RNA was transcribed using a high capacity RNA-to-cDNA kit (Applied Biosystems, Warrington, UK). Samples were prepared for cDNA synthesis in 20 µL reactions as per manufacturers instructions. A master mix was created using kit contents which included reverse transcription (RT) buffer, RT enzyme mix and nuclease-free H₂O (volumes per reaction are provided in Table 4.2). 9 µL of RNA sample was used in each reaction and cDNA was synthesised using the following thermal profile; 25 °C for 10 min, 37 °C for 2 h and 85 °C for 5 min. cDNA was stored at -20 °C until PCR analysis. qPCR reactions were set up and performed as done so in section 3.3.5. Expression of interleukin-8 (*IL8*) was measured (as it is found in significantly higher levels in COPD patients compared to healthy controls (Zhang et al., 2011)) in relation to the house-keeping gene *GAPDH*. Primer sequences are provided in above in Table 4.1.

Table 4.2: Volume of each component to create reverse transcription reactions

Reaction Component	Volume (µL per reaction)
RT enzyme	1
RT buffer	10
RNA sample	9

RT; reverse transcription

4.3.12 Epithelial cell protein release

Spent cell supernatants were harvested and used to measure IL-8 production using Human IL-8 ELISA kits (biotechne, Abingdon, UK) as per the manufacturer's instructions. 100 µL of capture antibody was added to each well of a 96-well microtiter plate and incubated at room temperature overnight. The plate was then washed three times with 400 µL wash buffer before adding 300 µL of blocking buffer. The plate containing blocking buffer was incubated for 1 h before washing another 3 times with 400 µL wash buffer. 100 µL of sample and provided standards were added per well. An adhesive strip was used to cover the plate which was incubated at room temperature for 2 h. Samples and standards were removed from respective wells and washed with 400 µL wash buffer three times. 100 µL of

streptavidin-horseradish peroxidase was added to each well and incubated at room temperature in the dark for 20 min before washing a further 3 times with wash buffer. 100 μ L substrate solution was then added to each well. The plate was incubated in the dark at room temperature for 20 min before adding 50 μ L of stop solution to each well. Well contents were mixed by gently tapping the plate before reading well absorbance at 450 nm.

4.3.13 Immunofluorescence

Following cell stimulation with biofilm supernatants as described above, cells were washed twice with pre-warmed PBS and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde for 10 min. Epithelial cells were permeabilised with triton X-100 (Sigma Aldrich) for 15 min. To prevent any non-specific binding, cells were incubated with 2% Bovine serum albumin (BSA) for 15 min. To stain any released IL-8, cells were incubated with 8 μ g/mL anti-IL-8 monoclonal antibody diluted in 0.1% BSA for 2 hours at room temperature. Next, cells were incubated for 45 min at room temperature with Alexa Fluor goat anti-mouse IgG was diluted 1:2000 (final concentration of 1 μ g/mL [Thermo Fisher]) in 0.1% BSA. Actin within the epithelial cells was then stained with Alexa fluorophore 488 (Thermo Fisher) for 30 minutes at room temperature. Finally, to stain cell nuclei, DAPI (Thermo Fisher) was diluted 1:1000 (to give a final concentration of 10 μ g/mL) in warm PBS can incubated with cells for 3 mins at room temperature. Between each incubation step, cells were washed gently 3 times with warm PBS. Cells were then imaged on an EVOS cell imaging system as described above. Cell actin, nuclei and IL-8 were fluoresced at excitation/emission wavelengths of 470/525, 357/447 and 531/593 nm, respectively.

4.3.14 Statistical analysis

All graph productions and subsequent analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism (version 7, La Jolla, California, USA). Non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney *t*-tests were used to compare means of corrected raw data of biofilm and epithelial cell stimulation assays. Dunn's post-hoc test for multiple comparisons was performed following Kruskal-Wallis tests. Differences between means were deemed significant where $P < 0.05$. All experiments were performed in triplicate on separate occasions. Biofilm experiments contained 8 technical replicates and epithelial cell experiments contained two technical replicates.

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Multi-species biofilm growth

Firstly, a simple biofilm model was developed to investigate microbial dynamics within the COPD lung. The model contained three organisms with the first being the fungi *C. albicans*, and the Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis*. All bacteria selected were poor biofilm formers, which is shown by low levels of CV staining (Figure 4.1). As expected, *C. albicans* formed thick, robust biofilms and an additional 1.75-fold increase in biomass occurred from *C. albicans* only biofilms to the multi-species model, indicating synergism between organisms ($P < 0.01$). Both of these bacteria have previously been shown to directly interact with *C. albicans* (Delaney et al., 2018). Bacteria were further confirmed as poor biofilm formers through visual analysis (Figure 4.2). However, the thickness of the multi-species biofilm prevents detailed analysis of the biofilm structure using standard light microscopy.

Figure 4.1: *Candida albicans* is required for effective multi-species biofilm formation. Single and multi-species biofilms of *C. albicans* (Ca), *S. aureus* (Sa) and *P. gingivalis* (Pg) were grown in 96-well microtitre plates for 24h. Non-adherent cells were removed by washing with PBS and each biofilm was stained with 0.05% crystal violet for 20min. Excess dye was removed and bound dye was released using 100% ethanol. Absorbance of the ethanol was measured at 570nm. Experiments were performed three times on separate occasions. Symbols show statistical significance when compared to Ca only biofilms (#, $P < 0.05$; \$ = $P < 0.01$).

Figure 4.2: Bacteria visually confirmed as being poor biofilm formers. Single and multi-species biofilms of *C. albicans* (Ca), *S. aureus* (Sa) and *P. gingivalis* (Pg) were grown in 24-well microtitre plates for 24h. Biofilms were washed with PBS to remove any non-adhered cells and biofilms were then imaged using an EVOS live cell imaging microscope at x40 magnification

4.4.2 Bacteria bind to *Candida albicans* hyphae with high affinities

Previous studies have shown several species of bacteria possess a high affinity for binding to *C. albicans* hyphae (Pidwill et al., 2018, Kean et al., 2017). Therefore, early biofilms of *C. albicans* were grown for 2h stained before staining with CFW. Bacteria pre-stained with hexidium iodide were incubated with fungal biofilms for a further hour to visualise any inter-kingdom interactions (Figure 4.3). *S. aureus* can be seen forming aggregates of cells adhered to *C. albicans* hyphae (Figure 4.3A). *P. gingivalis* both showed an ability to adhere to fungal hyphae although this did not appear to be as common as binding between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* (Figure 4.3B). Despite high levels of fungal-bacterial binding, bacteria were still capable of growing independently of *C. albicans*. Additional images were captured and the number of bacteria bound to individual hyphae were counted (Figure 4.4). *S. aureus* displayed the highest amount of binding to *C. albicans* with 100% of hyphae had at least one bacteria adhered to the cell wall. *P. gingivalis* showed differing levels of binding to fungal hyphae with 79% of *C. albicans* possessing one or more bound bacteria.

Figure 4.3: Bacteria adhere directly to *Candida albicans* hyphae in dual-species biofilms. *C. albicans* biofilms were grown for 2h in 8-well chamber slides before the addition of *S. aureus* (A) or *P. gingivalis* (B). All bacteria were pre-stained with 1.5mM hexidium iodide and bacterial inoculums contained 1.5mM CFW. Bacteria were incubated with fungal biofilms for a further 1h to allow for binding and fungal staining. Biofilms were washed twice with PBS before imaging using an EVOS live cell imaging microscope. CFW and hexidium iodide fluorescence was detected at excitation/emission wavelengths of 357/447 and 531/593, respectively. Scale bars represent 100 µm.

Figure 4.4: *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* have a high binding affinity for one another. Forty fields of view of dual-species biofilms containing *C. albicans* and either *S. aureus* (Sa) or *P. gingivatis* (Pg) were captured and the number of bacteria adhered to each individual hyphae were counted. Red lines represents the mean number of bacteria bound to each hyphae.

4.4.3 Visualisation of direct fungal-bacterial interactions in a mature biofilm

In order to view the complex nature of mature, multi-species biofilms, cells were labelled with smart probes that can distinguish between fungi, Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Each probe localised on the bacterial and fungal membranes. The hypothesis that bacteria adhere to hyphal filaments in a mature biofilm were confirmed using CLSM (Figure 4.5) where bacteria can be seen adhering to *C. albicans* hyphae in a multi-species biofilm model.

Figure 4.5: Microbe specific labelling of organisms shows cell-cell interactions taking place within complex multi-species biofilms. Multi-species biofilms of *C. albicans*, *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* were grown in 8-well chamber slides for 24h. Biofilms were washed with PBS and fungi (red), *S. aureus* (green) and *P. gingivalis* (pink) were labelled with 10 μ M of their respective probes. Biofilms were incubated with the fungal probe first for 2h before removal and addition of bacterial probes for 10min. Following labelling, 4% paraformaldehyde was used to fix the biofilms before imaging using a confocal laser-scanning microscope. Blue, yellow and white arrows point towards *C. albicans*, *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis*, respectively.

4.4.4 Single and multi-species biofilms tolerate antimicrobial challenge

Biofilms are notoriously more resistant to antimicrobial therapies than planktonic cells. This is evident from Table 4.2, which describes the PMIC, SMIC and the associated fold increase in SMIC of single species biofilms compared to PMIC of the same organism. Both *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* were both susceptible to erythromycin and amoxicillin with PMICs under the resistance cut-offs described by the CLSI guidelines (CLSI, 2020, CLSI, 2021). Breakpoints for erythromycin, amoxicillin and voriconazole are <2, <2 and <0.5 μ g/mL, respectively. *C. albicans* was susceptible to voriconazole in suspension (PMIC = 0.5 μ g/mL). As expected, erythromycin and amoxicillin had no effect on planktonic or sessile

Developing an informed biofilm model

C. albicans cells but were effective against planktonic *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* (PMIC = 0.5 and 0.25 µg/mL, respectively). Both erythromycin and amoxicillin also displayed activity against *S. aureus* (SMIC₈₀ = 16 and 0.5 µg/mL, respectively) and *P. gingivalis* (SMIC₈₀ = 8 and 0.25 µg/mL, respectively). As predicted, each antimicrobial was less potent towards biofilms with no activity observed in the treatment of *C. albicans* biofilms (SMIC₈₀ = > 128). A similar trend was observed in multi-species biofilms where antibiotic and antifungal therapies did not effectively reduce biofilm activity. The most effective treatment was amoxicillin however this only reduced multi-species biofilm viability by 23% (Figure 4.6).

Table 4.3: Biofilms display decreased susceptibility to antimicrobials compared to planktonic counterparts

Organism	Erythromycin			Amoxicillin			Voriconazole		
	PMIC	SMIC	FC	PMIC	SMIC	FC	PMIC	SMIC	FC
<i>C. albicans</i>	> 32	> 32	0	> 32	> 32	0	0.5	> 128	≥ 256
<i>S. aureus</i>	0.5	16	32	0.5	0.25	2	> 32	>128	≥ 4
<i>P. gingivalis</i>	0.125	8	64	< 0.063	0.25	> 4	> 32	>128	≥ 4
3-species	> 32	> 64	≥ 2	> 32	> 64	≥ 2	> 32	> 128	≥ 4

PMIC; planktonic minimum inhibitory concentration, SMIC₈₀; sessile minimum inhibitory concentration (80%) and FC; fold change. All concentrations are displayed as µg/mL.

Figure 4.6:Antimicrobial therapies are ineffective against multi-species biofilms. Multi-species biofilms were grown for 24 h and treated for a further 24 h with erythromycin, amoxicillin or voriconazole. Viability of treated biofilms are presented as a percentage of untreated controls and error bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

As neither treatment was able to prevent growth in a multi-species inoculum or kill a pre-formed biofilm, the efficacy of antimicrobial combinations against dual and multi-species biofilms was tested (Figure 4.7). It is evident from the heatmap that even in combination; all three drugs were unable to kill a pre-formed biofilm. Dual-species biofilms of *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*, and biofilms containing all 3 organisms showed minimal responses to all treatment options with metabolic activity remaining similar to that of untreated biofilms. Dual-species biofilms containing *C. albicans* and *P. gingivalis* were more susceptible to treatments with combination therapy with both antibiotics and voriconazole reducing biofilm activity by 56%. As was to be expected, dual-species biofilms containing *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* were highly susceptible to treatments containing antimicrobials. Each of which lowered biofilm viability by up to 35%. The presence of *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* in the biofilm greatly increased biofilm tolerance to each treatment.

Figure 4.7: Current antimicrobials used in the management of COPD are ineffective in killing pre-formed biofilms. Biofilms were grown for 24 h before being treated with antimicrobial drugs alone or in combination at 128 µg/mL (in combinational treatments, all drugs were diluted to 128 µg/mL). Biofilms were treated for a further 24 h before measuring the metabolic activity of the cells using resazurin sodium salt. Results are presented as a fold change in metabolic activity compared to untreated biofilms. Experiments were repeated three times on separate occasions.

4.4.5 Biofilm composition changes with antimicrobial challenge

Antibiotic treatments *in vivo* have previously been shown to be defective in treating biofilm infections by merely reducing total biomass rather than clearing the present microbes (Townsend et al., 2017). Herein, a similar trend is shown to occur *in vitro* (Figure 4.8). Biofilms that have not been exposed to antimicrobial agents are dominated by *S. aureus* (78%), followed by *C. albicans* and *P. gingivalis* (16% and 6%, respectively). Following treatments, all biofilms remained dominated by *S. aureus* and the total number of CFEs remained constant throughout (Figure 4.8A). Although not significantly, combined treatment with ERY and AMX resulted in a decrease in *S. aureus* (Figure 4.8B). Antifungal therapy reduced the proportion of *C. albicans* in the biofilm, giving *P. gingivalis* appropriate conditions to continue its growth.

Figure 4.8: Antibiotic treatments induce compositional shifts in multi-species biofilm composition. Multi-species biofilms were grown on coverslips in 24-well microtitre plates for 24h before treatment with antibiotics or antifungals for another 24h. Biofilm cells were removed by sonication after gentle washing with PBS. Samples were split in half, one was treated with propidium monoazide and the other was left untreated. DNA was then extracted from all samples to determine the total and live CFEs. Biofilm CFEs are presented as percentages of total biofilm composition (A) and true CFEs (B). ERY; erythromycin, AMX; amoxicillin, VORI; voriconazole. Experiments were carried out in triplicate on three separate occasions.

4.4.6 Immunogenicity of multi-species biofilms

Although antimicrobial therapies do not fully remove biofilm biomass the ability of the biofilm to elicit an immune response was subsequently assessed. TR146 epithelial cells were exposed to cell-free supernatants of multi-species before and after treatment with erythromycin, amoxicillin, voriconazole or a combination of all three. To assess the immune response, the production of the key pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-8 was measured (Figure 4.9). Firstly, the presence of IL-8 was measured in the cell supernatant by ELISA (Figure 4.9A) which showed no significant differences between untreated epithelial cells and those exposed to biofilm supernatants. The concentration of IL-8 produced by epithelial cells under each condition ranged from 268 to 498 pg/mL. However, expression of IL-8 mRNA was noticeably higher in biofilm supernatant treated cells compared to that of the negative control however this did not reach statistical significance. *IL8* expression in epithelial cells exposed to the supernatant of biofilms treated with erythromycin and the triple therapy were 4.2 and 4.4 fold higher than untreated epithelial cells, respectively. This increased *IL8* expression in the same samples was also 1.9 and 2 fold higher than what was observed in epithelial cells exposed to the supernatants of biofilms which had not been treated with antimicrobials. Findings from Figure 4.9 that suggested an increase (although not a significant increase) in immunogenicity following the biofilms exposure to erythromycin, amoxicillin and voriconazole were visually confirmed by fluorescently labelling IL-8 secreted from epithelial cells (Figure 4.10). This suggests that if antimicrobial therapies do not remove biofilm biomass, this may exacerbate inflammation in the lungs.

Figure 4.9: IL-8 production in stimulated epithelial cells. Cell-free supernatants from mature untreated multi-species biofilms or those treated with erythromycin, amoxicillin, voriconazole or a combination of all three (triple therapy) was mixed 1:1 (v:v) with KSM. TR146 cells were exposed to the supernatant and media mixture for 4 h before the production of IL-8 was measured by ELISA (A) and by qPCR (B). NC datapoints represent cells that have only been exposed to KSM and not biofilm supernatants.

Developing an informed biofilm model

A

B

C

Figure 4.10: Immunofluorescent staining of epithelial cells stimulated with biofilm supernatant. After reaching confluency, epithelial cells were stimulated with biofilm supernatants for 4 h before actin (green) and nuclei (blue) of epithelial cells along with secreted IL-8 (red) were fluorescently labelled and imaged. Unstimulated epithelial cells which were only exposed to KSFM (A), and those stimulated with supernatant from untreated biofilms (B) and those exposed to the combination treatments of erythromycin, amoxicillin and voriconazole (C) are shown above. White arrows point towards IL-8 production by epithelial cells. Actin, nuclei and IL-8 were imaged using excitation/emission wavelengths of 470/525, 357/447 and 531/593 nm, respectively. Scale bars in each image represent 150 μ m.

4.5 Discussion

This chapter set out to develop and characterise a multi-species biofilm model, containing organisms selected from the previous chapter, and subsequently test effectiveness of clinically relevant treatments. This newly developed biofilm model supports high levels of microbial growth and this complex structure increases tolerance to antimicrobials frequently employed in COPD therapies. Overall, the most effective treatment options for mature, multi-species biofilms were either a combination of amoxicillin and voriconazole or amoxicillin only. Although these were the most effective treatments they were unable to significantly reduce levels of cell metabolism or cell number.

The presence of biofilms in the lungs is becoming increasingly accepted. Despite this, the number of studies investigating the role of biofilms in COPD is severely lacking. A number of studies have reported on the composition of the microbiome in COPD patients (Cabrera-Rubio et al., 2012, Erb-Downward et al., 2011, Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2015, Garcia-Nuñez et al., 2017, Mayhew et al., 2018, Wang et al., 2016). However, these merely describe the microbial inhabitants of the lungs without any functional assays. As shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2, *C. albicans* is a 'keystone' member of the observed biofilms, allowing for effective bacterial growth. This is in line with findings by Young et al. (2020) who reported similar findings in more complex biofilm consortia. This close association between the fungal pathogen, *C. albicans* and bacteria, such as *Streptococcus* spp. in oral disease, is not uncommon with additional bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Streptococcus gordonii* displaying a propensity for complex interactions (Pidwill et al., 2018, Haiko et al., 2019, Bamford et al., 2009). These close associations between *C. albicans* and bacteria often result in chronic and more severe infections (Peters et al., 2012a).

Both *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* interact with *C. albicans*, via Als3 (Peters et al., 2012b, Sztukowska et al., 2018) with other studies reporting that *C. albicans* hyphae act as a biofilm substrate for *S. aureus* to aid its growth (Kean et al., 2017). Similar findings have shown that *C. albicans* augments the growth of *P. gingivalis* through upregulation of cell division genes (Sztukowska et al., 2018). However, as both bacteria are in competition for Als3 binding receptors, paired with the slower rate of growth of *P. gingivalis* compared to *S. aureus* can explain the lower numbers of anaerobic bacteria identified in the multi-species biofilms in Figure 4.7 (Grenier et al., 2001, Missiakas and Schneewind, 2013).

Developing an informed biofilm model

Additional data shown in Figure 4.7 shows what may be expected from a multi-species biofilm capable of tolerating treatments by exhibiting a dynamic composition. For example, the use of antibiotics such as erythromycin resulted in lowering the total number of bacteria, resulting in the relative abundance of *C. albicans* increasing. *C. albicans* has been known to provide protection to bacteria against antibiotic treatment. For example, *S. aureus* coats itself in ECM components produced by *C. albicans* to protect itself from macrolide treatment. Even the combination of antifungals and antibiotics lacks the ability to kill multi-species biofilms as total biofilm CFEs remain largely unchanged when treated with erythromycin, amoxicillin and voriconazole. *C. albicans* biofilms have previously shown high levels of recalcitrance towards azole therapies (Kean et al., 2017). These findings support claims of previous meta-analyses performed to assess the efficacy of antimicrobial therapies in the management of COPD (Yao et al., 2013, Ni et al., 2015). These studies suggest that antibiotics are more effective as a prophylaxis which reduces AECOPD risk. Results from Figure 4.7 show that the presence of both *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* is likely responsible for the increase in antimicrobial tolerance. These interactions have previously been shown to achieve this through increased bacterial ECM production and through *S. aureus* coating itself in *C. albicans* ECM components to protect against antibiotics (Kong et al., 2016, Vila et al., 2021)

Results taken from Figure 4.9 shows that the described biofilm can elicit an immune response in epithelial cells. Detection of IL-8 proteins in spent supernatants was unaltered compared to negative controls however an increase in IL-8 expression was observed. *P. gingivalis* produces highly effective gingipains that cleave cytokines such as IL-8 which would counteract the stimulatory effect caused by *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* (Stathopoulou et al., 2009). The immune stimulatory effect likely arises from increased toxin production by *S. aureus*. In 2019, Todd and colleagues showed that *C. albicans* increased the expression of the *S. aureus agr* quorum sensing pathway (Todd et al., 2019). This quorum sensing system is responsible for a number of virulence associated mechanisms, namely the production of a number of enterotoxins such as enterotoxin B. This particular toxin has shown an ability to induce the secretion of IL-8, even in sub-toxic concentrations (O'Brien et al., 2006).

As mentioned above, the majority of biofilm studies focus on single bacterial species. However, this cannot provide accurate information on how bacteria, or fungi, behave *in vivo* whilst in the presence of other organisms. The use of multi-species biofilms

Developing an informed biofilm model

containing other relevant organisms identified in the disease site of interest are one-step closer to mimicking disease conditions. However, despite our best efforts to replicate disease environments as accurately as possible, it cannot replace *in vivo* conditions (Cornforth et al., 2018). From searching the literature, this chapter presents the first report of a multi-species biofilm model that can be used to study microbiological aspects of COPD patients. The developed biofilm model was able to tolerate all treatment methods used, highlighting the importance of timely administration of appropriate antimicrobial therapies to effectively combat these infections.

There are some limitations to this chapter. Firstly, although findings report a multi-species model it is still not fully representative of the COPD microbiome which is home to on average 289 different bacterial species as shown in the previous chapter. Therefore, it still does not provide a complete picture on how the microbiome is affected by antimicrobial therapies. However, it could be expected that as biofilm complexity increases so does antimicrobial tolerance.

In conclusion, this chapter is the first report of a multi-species biofilm model that is representative of the lung microbiome. This addresses a large gap in the current literature as at present there exist no multi-species biofilm models that can be applied to study disease in the respiratory tract. Combining the ineffectiveness of antimicrobial therapies with the subsequent increase in cytokine production explains reasoning behind why antimicrobials show limited effectiveness in COPD therapy. The opportunity for repeat infection therefore remains. This indicates that future studies should seek to apply novel anti-biofilm therapies to the treatment of COPD with the aims of reducing the possibility of repeat infection and risk of chronic colonisation.

4.5.1 Key findings

- *C. albicans* plays a central role in multi-species biofilm formation. This occurs through fungal hyphae acting as a scaffold to support bacterial growth
- Antibiotics currently used in the management of COPD somewhat alter the composition of established, multi-species biofilms and do not effectively kill these biofilms
- The combined presence of *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* drives the biofilm tolerance
- Multi-species biofilms elicit an immune response from epithelial cells which is increased following exposure to antibiotic. Pairing this with the ineffectiveness of antibiotic therapy could exacerbate inflammation within the COPD lung

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

5 Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by
Staphylococcus aureus

5.1 Introduction

Candida albicans is typically found as a commensal organism at mucosal and barrier sites, such as the oral cavity, respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts. Under certain conditions such as a compromised host immune system or sub-inhibitory concentrations of antifungal drugs, *C. albicans* is capable of causing opportunistic infections, ranging from superficial to systemic disease, making it one of the most common fungal infections (Brown et al., 2012). The mechanism behind the opportunistic nature of this pathogen lies in its ability to transition from a budding yeast cell to a highly invasive and filamentous hyphal cell, which are typically associated as being commensal and pathogenic phenotypes, respectively (Brown et al., 2012, Lu et al., 2014). Whether acting as a commensal or pathogen, *C. albicans* frequently co-exists with various bacterial species at mucosal sites, and the clinical significance of polymicrobial infections is becoming more apparent (Delaney et al., 2018). Interactions that take place within these infections can be synergistic, leading to traits such as increased drug resistance, virulence and biofilm formation (Kean et al., 2017, Harriott and Noverr, 2011). However, antagonistic interactions can occur between *C. albicans* and bacteria such as *Enterococcus faecalis* which inhibits hyphal formation (Alshanta et al., 2022).

C. albicans is commonly implicated in polymicrobial infections with bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. epidermidis* or *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Prevalence of these polymicrobial infections range from 27-56% (Klotz et al., 2007a, Pulimood et al., 2002). A considerable amount of infections involving *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* have been linked to biofilms (Tsui et al., 2016). Polymicrobial biofilms containing *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* have been implicated in periodontitis, cystic fibrosis and diabetic foot ulcers (Peters et al., 2012a).

The relationship between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* appears to be beneficial for the bacterium, which utilises the fungi to augment its own virulence and resistance capabilities. *S. aureus* has been reported to coat itself in the *C. albicans* extracellular component, β -1,3-glucan in order to increase tolerance to vancomycin (Kong et al., 2016). Our group has also demonstrated that *C. albicans* increases the virulence of *S. aureus* in the *Galleria mellonella* infection model (Kean et al., 2017). Similar increases in virulence in animal infection models have also been shown (Todd et al., 2019, Peters and Noverr, 2013). Indeed, in a murine infection model, *C. albicans* was shown to have an ability to augment the *agr* quorum sensing system of *S. aureus*, resulting in increased alpha- and delta-toxin production, bacterial

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

burden and mortality rates (Todd et al., 2019, Otto, 2014, Wang et al., 2007). Moreover, because the bacteria adhere directly to the fungal hyphae, *S. aureus* can more readily invade host cells through its close association with the invasive hyphae, which is akin to a needle-stick injection. In the context of complex multispecies communities, *C. albicans* has been described as a ‘keystone commensal’, suggesting it plays a critical physical role in promoting and maintaining biofilm stability in complex communities (Young et al., 2020, Janus et al., 2016).

When interacting with *C. albicans*, *S. aureus* preferentially adheres to the agglutinin like sequence 3 protein (Als3) (Peters et al., 2012b), which is highly expressed during early stages of *C. albicans* filamentous growth (Sherry et al., 2014). The Als3 protein plays multiple roles in the *C. albicans* infection cycle. These include the initial adhesion to host epithelial cells which subsequently induces its own endocytosis (Phan et al., 2007). As well as binding to host tissues, Als3 mediates self-adherence as well as *Candida*-bacteria binding as deletion of *ALS3* results in sparse and disorganised biofilms (Nobile et al., 2006a, Peters et al., 2012b). These *Candida*-bacteria interactions may be reciprocal, as it has been reported that *C. albicans* Als3 shares over 80% homology with *S. aureus* collagen binding factor (Sheppard et al., 2004). Several other genes including, but not limited to, hyphal wall protein 1 (*HWP1*), enhanced filamentous growth protein 1 (*EFG1*) and extent of cell elongation 1 (*ECE1*) have been described as being crucial to *C. albicans* pathogenesis, and appear to be co-expressed alongside *ALS3* (Ramage et al., 2002b, Nobile et al., 2006b, Moyes et al., 2016). Of these genes, and arguably one of the most important, is *ECE1*, which encodes a 29 kDa cytolytic protein (named candidalysin) that is essential for virulence and epithelial cell damage in *C. albicans* infections. Cells lacking *ECE1* show no identifiable morphological differences, do not trigger epithelial cell danger response and are avirulent in animal infection models (Moyes et al., 2016). Recent work has revealed that the global repressor Tup1 and transcription factor Ahr1 are both required for expression of *ALS3* and *ECE1* (Ruben et al., 2020). Together these data highlight the importance of gene networks controlling pathogenicity, but we are still unclear on how these are controlled in dual-species interactions. Therefore, more in-depth analyses of these interactions are required.

Previous studies investigating the role of gene products such as Als3 have focused on the effect that deleting or over expressing, the desired target has on *C. albicans* behaviour (Peters et al., 2012b, Zhao et al., 2006). However, it can be argued that these studies failed to capture ‘the big picture’, which would show the downstream affects that manipulating *ALS3* expression has on *C. albicans* behaviour. Caveats in these studies result

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

from limited access to more powerful sequencing technologies. Continuous and rapid advances in sequencing technologies has helped address these needs and has resulted in the production of unprecedented amounts of data. The need to analyse and understand these large data sets can be addressed using bioinformatics. Bioinformatics combines mathematics, computer science and biology techniques in the management of these data. A branch of bioinformatics that can be used to understand cell behaviour is transcriptomics. The transcriptome of a cell is defined as all of the mRNA transcripts within a cell and their quantity. This captures a snapshot of how a cell may be behaving at a certain developmental time point in a certain condition (Wang et al., 2009). The main aim from studies using transcriptomics is to compare a cell under controlled conditions to another in a 'disease like' state to identify changes in transcripts that may lead to development of a specific disease phenotype. Each cell type has its own distinct transcriptome, making the correct choice of cell for transcriptome sequencing experiments crucial (Consortium, 2015). Using transcriptomics to study cell-cell interactions between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* could be extremely beneficial in unveiling the effects that *S. aureus* has on fungal behaviour.

The effects of these polymicrobial interactions are becoming increasingly well characterised with respects to *S. aureus*, however the effect on *C. albicans* remains somewhat enigmatic. *C. albicans* is typically more adept in biofilm formation and cell invasion than *S. aureus* (Kean et al., 2017), which presents difficulties in identifying any increase in these traits that are induced by *S. aureus*. Therefore, this chapter sought to investigate these interactions in depth by exploring any changes in the *C. albicans* transcriptome that are induced by *S. aureus*.

5.2 Aims and hypotheses

In the previous chapter, a multi-species biofilm containing *C. albicans*, *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* was shown to elicit an immune response in epithelial cells. In addition to this, the combined presence of *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* aided in driving biofilm tolerance towards antimicrobial therapies. Therefore, the aims of this chapter were

- To use RNA sequencing to characterise the relationship between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* within a polymicrobial biofilm
- Investigate the effects of *S. aureus* on the transcriptome of *C. albicans* to identify potential fungal mechanisms that could drive increased antimicrobial tolerance and immunogenicity observed in the previous chapter
- Interrogate if the key biofilm genes *ALS3* and *ECE1* play a role in modulating these interactions

Based on findings of previous studies it is hypothesised that *S. aureus* will induce the upregulation of genes that benefit *C. albicans* in biofilm formation when able to bind to Als3 in the wild type (WT) and *ece1* Δ/Δ strains. Due to limited knowledge of the downstream effects of *ECE1* deletion, it is difficult to predict how this will affect *C. albicans* behaviour. However, deletion of the key adhesin gene *ALS3* is likely to reduce the number of interactions occurring between each organism and therefore lessening the response from *C. albicans*.

Work from this chapter has been presented at the following conference:

BREATH annual conference, July 2020 (Virtual)

Title: "Influence of *Staphylococcus aureus* on *Candida albicans* transcriptome"

Work from this chapter has been published in *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*:

Short B, Delaney C, McKloud E, Brown J L, Kean R, Litherland G J, Williams C, Martin L S, MacKay W G and Ramage G. Investigating the Transcriptome of *Candida albicans* in a Dual-Species *Staphylococcus aureus* Biofilm Model. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*. 2021 Nov doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2021.791523.

5.3 Materials and methods

5.3.1 Microbial storage and standardisation

Candida albicans SC5314, *C. albicans als3Δ/Δ* (gifted by Prof Lois Hoyer, University of Illinois), *C. albicans ece1Δ/Δ* (gifted by Dr Julian Naglik, Kings College London) and *Staphylococcus aureus* NCTC 10833 were used in this study. *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* were grown on Sabourauds Dextrose (SAB) agar (Thermo Fisher, Paisley, UK) and Luria Bertani (LB) agar (Thermo Fisher), respectively and stored at 4 °C. All organisms were stored long-term in glycerol at -80 °C.

To prepare overnight broths of each microorganism, one colony of *C. albicans* was suspended in Yeast Peptone Dextrose (YPD) media (Thermo Fisher) and incubated in an orbital shaker at 200 rpm and 30 °C. Luria Bertani broth (LB, Thermo Fisher) was used to grow overnight broths of *S. aureus* at 37 °C. Overnight cultures were washed by centrifugation and subsequent re-suspension in Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS, Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK). *S. aureus* cells were diluted to 0.6 OD₆₀₀ (approximately 1x10⁸ cells/mL). *C. albicans* cells were counted on a Neubauer haemocytometer and all organisms were diluted to desired concentration in assay specific media.

5.3.2 Media preparation

Todd Hewitt broth (THB, Sigma Aldrich) was prepared and supplemented with 10 μM menadione and 4 mg/mL hemin (Thermo Fisher) and mixed 1:1 with RPMI (referred to as 1:1 broth from herein).

5.3.3 Biofilm growth and analysis

Following counting of yeast cells and standardisation of bacteria, all cells were added to sTHB media to give a final concentration of 1x10⁶ CFU/mL. All biofilm assays were carried out in accordance with the minimum information guidelines for growth of biofilms in microtitre plates (Allkja et al., 2020). Biofilms were grown by adding 200 μL of inoculated growth media to desired wells of a microtitre plate and *Candida* was incubated with or without the presence of each bacteria for 4 or 24 h to assess biofilm formation at early and late timepoints of biofilm maturation. Following the incubation step, biofilms were washed with PBS.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Biofilms were then incubated with 100µL of XTT (2,3-bis(2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulfo-phenyl)-2*H*-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide) sodium salt with 1µM menadione (Thermo Fisher) for 1h at 37°C. Absorbance of XTT liquid was measured at 492nm. Biofilms were washed twice more using PBS to remove residual XTT staining and then incubated with 0.05% crystal violet (CV) to quantify total biofilm biomass. CV stain was incubated on biofilms for 20 min at room temperature and excess dye removed with H₂O. Bound dye was released using 100% ethanol and absorbance of the ethanol was measured at 570 nm. Single and multi-species biofilms were imaged using an EVOS cell imaging system (Thermo Fisher) at 40x magnification.

5.3.4 DNA extraction and purification

Early and mature biofilms of *C. albicans* mutants with and without bacteria for 4 and 24 h were grown on polymer coverslips before removing biomass via sonication at 35kHz for 15 min in 1 mL PBS using an ultrasonic water bath (Fisher Scientific, UK). DNA was extracted from biofilm cells using the Qiagen DNA mini-kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). Cells were pelleted by centrifugation at 13,000 rpm for 10 min. Cells were suspended in 180 µL ATL buffer and 20 µL of 20 mg/mL proteinase K and incubated for 1 hour at 56°C. Each sample was then transferred to 1.5mL screw-cap tubes containing 0.5mm sterile glass beads. Samples were mechanically lysed in a 24-sample BeadMill (Fisher Scientific). Bead beating was carried out in 3 x 30 second cycles at 4000 rpm with a 1 min break between cycles. Each sample was incubated with 200 µL AL buffer for 10 min at 70°C. After this incubation, samples were mixed with 200 µL ethanol before adding to QIAmp spin columns. To bind DNA to the spin column, it was centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 1 min, flow-through was discarded and the spin column was placed in a new collection tube. 500 µL of wash buffer AW1 was added to the spin columns, which were centrifuged for 1 min at 7000 rpm. Again, the flow-through was discarded and spin-columns were placed in new collection tubes. The second wash step was carried out by adding 500 µL AW2 buffer to each spin column, which were centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 3 min. Spin-columns were added to new collection tubes and centrifuged again at the same speed for 1 min to ensure no buffers remained in the spin-columns. Spin columns were added to DNase free 1.5 mL tubes with the lids removed and 50 µL AE buffer was added directly on to the column filter. Samples were allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 min before centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 1min to elute the DNA. To maximise DNA recovery, the previous step was repeated with another 50 µL aliquot of fresh AE buffer. DNA samples were stored at -20°C until required.

5.3.5 Biofilm composition analysis

Quantitative PCR (qPCR) was then used to determine the total number of cells within each biofilm. Briefly, DNA was extracted from biofilm cells as described above and 1µL of extracted DNA was added to a PCR mastermix containing Fast SYBR Green Master Mix, 10 µM species-specific forward and reverse primers (sequences provided in Table 1) and water. qPCR was then carried out using the Step-One plus real time PCR machine (Life Technologies, Paisley, UK). The following profile was used: 50°C for 2 min, 95°C for 2 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 3 s and 60°C for 30 s. Colony forming equivalents (CFE) were calculated compared to a standard curve of serially diluted DNA of each species as previously described (O'Donnell et al., 2016).

Table 5.1: Species specific primers used to identify *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*.

Target Organism	Forward Sequence (5' - 3')	Reverse Sequence (5' - 3')	Reference
<i>Candida albicans</i>	GAGCGTCGTTTCTCCCTCAAACCG CTGG	GGTGGACGTTACCGCCCAAGCA ATGTT	(Kean et al., 2017)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	ATTTGGTCCCAGTGGTGTGGG TAT	GCTGTGACAATTGCCGTTTG TCGT	(O'Donnell et al., 2016)

5.3.6 Visualisation of inter-kingdom biofilm interactions

C. albicans was standardised to 1×10^6 cells/mL, as described above, and biofilms grown in chamber slides (Thermo Fisher) for 2h at 37°C to induce hyphal formation. Bacteria were standardised to approximately 1×10^8 cells/mL, stained with 1.5 mM hexidium iodide (Fisher Scientific) and incubated at 37°C for 1h. Bacterial cells were pelleted by centrifugation and washed twice with PBS. *Candida* biofilms were washed with PBS following initial incubation. Bacterial cells at 5×10^7 cells/mL and 1.5mM calcofluor white were added to the chamber slide for a further hour at 37°C. Biofilms were then washed with PBS and imaged using an EVOS cell imaging system (Thermo Fisher). Calcofluor white and hexidium iodide fluorescence was detected at excitation/emission wavelengths of 357/447 and 531/593nm, respectively, before overlaying the images.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

To quantify fungal-bacterial interactions, a method similar to Pidwill et al. (2018) was used. Initially, 40 random fields of view were captured. The total number of bacteria adhered to individual hyphae were counted and hyphae were placed into one of four groups based on how many bacteria were present. Groups were classified as follows; group 1 had zero bacteria bound, group 2 had between 1 and 5 bacteria bound, group 3 had from 6 to 19 bacteria bound and finally, group 4 had more than 20 bacteria bound.

5.3.7 RNA extraction and sequencing

Dual-species biofilms of *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* were grown for 4 and 24h in 1:1 broth in T-75 cell culture flasks (Corning, UK). At each time point, media was removed and PBS was used to remove any non-adherent cells. Biofilm biomass was removed using a cell scraper and stored in 1 mL RNA later (ThermoFisher). Extractions were performed using RiboPure RNA Extraction Kits (ThermoFisher) following the manufacturer's instructions. A schematic of the experimental protocol is summarised in Figure 1. RNA quality and quantity was assessed using a Bioanalyser (Aligent, USA), where a minimum RNA integrity number (RIN) of 7.0 and a minimum quantity of 2.5 µg was achieved for each sample. RNA was sequenced by Edinburgh Genomics (genomics.ed.ac.uk) using a NovaSeq 6000 platform to provide 100bp paired end reads.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.1: Experimental pipeline for RNA extraction. Organisms were mixed 1:1 in growth media before growing as a biofilm for 4 or 24h in a T75 cell culture flask. Following biofilm growth, biomass was removed in RNA later for extraction. Extractions were performed following manufacturers protocols. Firstly, biofilm cells were lysed using ice cold zirconia beads, RNA was then bound to spin columns provided and any potential contaminants were removed using buffers included in the extraction kit. Finally, RNA was eluted in 100µL nuclease free water. Image was created using BioRender.com.

FastQC was used to assign quality scores to the produced reads and Illumina adaptors and poor quality reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic. HISAT2 was then used to align the resulting reads to a reference *C. albicans* genome (candidagenomedatabase.org) before the number of sequences that were aligned to each gene were counted using HTSeq. The counted genes were subsequently imported to RStudio (version 3.6.3) and the DESeq2 package was used to analyse the differentially expressed genes. The bioinformatics pipelines is summarised in Figure 2.

Dr Christopher Delaney (University of Glasgow) performed quality control, sequence trimming and read alignment and enumeration.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.2: Bioinformatic pipeline use in the analysis of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome. Schematic showing the bioinformatics pipeline used for the analysis of the RNA-seq data acquired from dual-species *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* biofilms. Firstly, high quality reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic, reads were aligned to a reference *C. albicans* genome, and the number of genes aligned to each gene were counted. Following these steps, differentially expressed genes were analysed and visualised using the DESeq2 package in RStudio.

5.3.8 Statistical analysis

Figures depicting differential gene expression between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* biofilms were created using the DESeq2 package in RStudio. Gene interaction networks were created using the ClueGO application in Cytoscape (cytoscape.com). All other graphs and analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism (version 7, La Jolla, California, USA). Non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to compare means of corrected raw data following biofilm assays followed by Dunn's test for multiple comparisons. Differences between means were deemed significant were $P < 0.05$.

5.4 Results

5.4.1 *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* form robust dual-species biofilms

Several staphylococci species have displayed an ability to interact synergistically with *C. albicans*. While there have been detailed studies to delineate these interactions using a conventional molecular approach, there is little understanding of the pleiotropic effects that co-aggregation has upon *C. albicans* (with and without specific adhesins). Therefore, studies are still required to decipher the effects these inter-kingdom interactions have on *C. albicans*. Firstly, to begin characterising the relationship between these organisms, the basis of these interactions were measured in a biofilm. *S. aureus* has previously shown an ability to adhere to *C. albicans* hyphae throughout all stages of biofilm formation (Kean et al., 2017). The chosen strain of *S. aureus* has also been shown to have a biofilm defective phenotype (Beenken et al., 2003). Mono- and dual-species biofilms were quantified at early (4 h) and late (24 h) time points using CV and XTT to assess total biomass and biofilm viability respectively (Figure 5.3). *S. aureus* produced a poor biofilm following 4 and 24 h growth which was determined by low absorbance following CV staining ($OD_{570nm} < 0.3$). The presence of *S. aureus* resulted in significant increases ($P < 0.0001$) in dual-species biofilm biomass when able to adhere to Als3 (Figure 5.3A and B). No significant changes in biomass was observed in *als3Δ/Δ* regardless of biofilm maturity. In all instances, dual-species biofilms were more metabolically active than *Candida* only biofilms ($P < 0.0001$; Figure 5.3D and E). However, this was an additive effect where combination of metabolic activity readings from single species *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* were no longer statistically significant compared to dual-species biofilms. Contrary to previous findings, little significant differences were observed between WT and mutant biofilms (Peters et al., 2012b, Hoyer et al., 2014). This may be due to the use of different biofilm growth media.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.3: Loss of ALS3p significantly affects *Candida-Staphylococcus* biofilm interactions. Single and multi-species biofilms containing *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* (SA) were grown for 4h and 24h. Biomass of 4 h (A), 24 h (B) and *S. aureus* only (C) biofilms was quantified by staining using 0.05% crystal violet. Viability of 4 h (D), 24 h (E) and *S. aureus* (F) biofilms was also measured using XTT sodium salt. Experiments were performed on three separate occasions and error bars represent standard deviation of the mean (*; $P < 0.05$, **; $P < 0.01$, ***; $P < 0.001$, ****; $P < 0.0001$).

5.4.2 *Candida albicans* promotes the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Next, the total number of microorganisms in each biofilm was quantified. To do this the total number of cells in each biofilm was quantified using qPCR (Figure 5.4). The number of *C. albicans* cells in 4 h biofilms remained approximately 4×10^5 cells/mL regardless of presence or absence of *S. aureus* (Figure 5.4A). The average number of *C. albicans* WT and *ece1Δ/Δ* in 24 h biofilms increased to 2×10^6 and 1.6×10^6 cells/mL, respectively. As expected, there was significantly less *C. albicans als3Δ/Δ* cells compared to the other *C. albicans* strains ($P < 0.05$; Figure 5.4B). Although there were differences in the total number of *C. albicans* cells in each biofilm, the presence of *S. aureus* did not affect the number of fungal cells in any biofilm.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Based on this evidence there must be an increase in *S. aureus* colonising the biofilm, which was confirmed when quantifying the total bacterial cells in dual-species biofilms. In early dual-species biofilms, the number of *S. aureus* cells in biofilms with *C. albicans als3Δ/Δ* was 100 and 345-fold lower than the WT and *ece1Δ/Δ* strains, respectively ($P < 0.05$; Figure 5.4C). A similar trend was observed at 24 h (Figure 5.4D), where the concentration of *S. aureus* recovered from biofilms grown with WT and the *ECE1* null mutant was significantly higher than that of *als3Δ/Δ* ($P < 0.05$).

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.4: *Candida albicans* Als3 is required for *Staphylococcus aureus* mycofilm formation. Biofilm biomass was removed via sonication, DNA was extracted and the total number of cells in each biofilm was quantified using qPCR. The total number of *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* cells of 4 h (A and C, respectively) and 24 h biofilms (B and D, respectively) are presented as colony forming equivalents per mL (CFE/mL). Experiments were repeated three times on three separate occasions. *S. aureus* CFEs of *C. albicans* SC5314 and *ece1Δ/Δ* dual-species biofilms were compared to that of *als3Δ/Δ* (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$).

5.4.3 Ece1 does not influence staphylococcal binding to *Candida albicans*

The binding affinity *S. aureus* had for each *C. albicans* strain was visualised and quantified using a similar method described by Pidwill et al. (2018). To do so, 40 different images of each biofilm were captured and the number of bacteria adhered to individual hyphae were counted. It was seen that *S. aureus* was able to avidly bind to *C. albicans* hyphae of WT and *ece1Δ/Δ* strains (Figure 5.5). As expected, deletion of *als3* considerably influenced the association between *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*. Contrary to previous findings, *S. aureus* was still able to adhere to *C. albicans* hyphae with between 1 and 5 bacteria adhering to 51% of hyphae. In 7% of cases, 20 or more bacteria were found to adhere to some *C. albicans als3Δ/Δ* cells (Table 5.2). *S. aureus* showed similar levels of binding between WT and *ece1Δ/Δ C. albicans*, with the majority of hyphae having 6-19 bacteria bound (56% and 50%, respectively). Despite having similar binding patterns for *S. aureus*, *C. albicans* WT was found to be more likely than *ece1Δ/Δ* to have 20 or more bacteria bound to individual hyphae (33% compared to 11%).

Table 5.2: Percentage of hyphae in each subcategory of bacterial binding

Group (Number of bacteria per hyphae)	SC5314	<i>als3Δ/Δ</i>	<i>ece1Δ/Δ</i>
Group 1 (0)	0	9.729	4.583
Group 2 (1-5)	9.915	51.76	33.57
Group 3 (6-19)	56.81	31.45	50.61
Group 4 (20 or more)	33.9	7.688	11.96

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.5: *Staphylococcus aureus* adheres directly to *Candida albicans*. *C. albicans* biofilms of WT (A) *als3Δ/Δ* (B) and *ece1Δ/Δ* (C) were grown for 2 h in 8-well chamber slides before the addition of *S. aureus* pre-stained with 1.5 mM hexidium iodide (red). Calcofluor white (1.5 mM; blue) was added to the bacterial inoculum to specifically label *C. albicans* (blue). Bacteria and calcofluor white were incubated with *C. albicans* biofilms for 1 h before washing with PBS and imaging using an EVOS cell imaging system. 40 separate fields of view were imaged for later quantification. Excitation/emission spectra of calcofluor white and hexidium iodide were 357/447 and 531/593 nm, respectively.

5.4.4 *Staphylococcus aureus* is responsible for modulating the *Candida albicans* transcriptome in mature biofilms

Differential expression (DE) analysis was performed to identify transcriptional changes in *C. albicans* biofilms when interacting with *S. aureus*. Multivariate analysis by principal component analysis (PCA) shows variance between samples by biofilm maturity and presence of *S. aureus* (Figure 5.6). The greatest amount of variance is seen between 4 h and 24 h. Some variance also occurs between 24 h single and dual-species biofilms. Early, 4 h samples also form to groups; however, other unknown mechanisms drive this grouping.

Figure 5.6: Presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* determines mature biofilm transcriptome. Principal component analysis plot shows distinct grouping of 24 h samples. PCA plot displays variable of largest variance along PC1 (65%) and second largest along PC2 (13%).

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

It is clear that a high number of genes are differentially regulated at early time points (Figure 5.7). However, expression levels of genes in dual-species biofilms are similar to that of their single-species comparator. Although the expression of many genes were above or below the Log_2 cut-offs of 1.5 and -1.5, respectively, these failed to reach statistical significance (Figure 5.8). Only one gene from all 4 h dual-species biofilms was significantly up regulated (Figure 5.8C). This gene was *PGA10*, which is involved in iron acquisition and ultimately, biofilm formation (Pérez et al., 2006). From this, it was concluded that any significant and strain specific changes in *C. albicans* transcription occurred within mature biofilms. Therefore, further analyses focused on the 24 h time point.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.7: Levels of differential gene expression is comparable between single and dual-species biofilms at early time points. Heatmaps show the top 50 most differentially regulated genes presented as normalised Log₂ fold change in WT (A), *als3Δ/Δ* (B) and *ece1Δ/Δ* (C) single and dual-species biofilms at 4 h.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.8: *Candida albicans* transcriptional changes occur in mature polymicrobial biofilms. Volcano plots shows Log₂ fold change versus the negative Log₁₀ of the adjusted *P*-value. Genes of interest in 4 h dual-species biofilms containing WT (A), *als3Δ/Δ* (B) or *ece1Δ/Δ* (C) can be identified where expression levels are above or below the Log₂ fold change cut-offs of -1.5 and 1.5 (green) and those that are also highly significant ($P < 0.01$; red).

Limited numbers of genes with increased expression were observed in single species biofilms with only 12 upregulated genes in total being specific to *C. albicans* only biofilms (Figure 5.9A). Each dual-species biofilm presented its own distinct patterns of up-regulation with 50 and 101 upregulated genes in WT and *als3Δ/Δ* dual species biofilms (Figure 5.9B). A depleted response of the *ece1Δ/Δ* strain was seen with only 27 upregulated genes identified and all of these were specific to the strain.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.9: *Staphylococcus aureus* induces strain specific gene upregulation in *Candida albicans*. Venn diagrams showing the number of genes upregulated in 24 h single (A) and dual-species (B) biofilms.

5.4.5 *Staphylococcus aureus* creates a more virulent fungal genotype in mature dual-species biofilms

More detailed analyses of differentially expressed genes showed some similarities between strains (Figure 5.10). Interestingly, adhesion of *S. aureus* to *als3Δ/Δ C. albicans* induces the upregulation of genes normally triggered by external stressors such as *MDR1* and *CAP1*, each of these genes were upregulated by a Log_2 fold-change of 3.6 and 1.8, respectively (Figure 5.10B). A core response of *C. albicans* in response to the presence of *S. aureus* was identified. This included heat-shock protein chaperone genes such as *SIS1*, *ABS1* and *SSA2*. Other genes of interest involved in this core response were virulence genes *ACE2*, *HSP104* and *HSP70*.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.10: Differential levels of gene expression is observed at 24 h in dual-species biofilms. Heatmaps show the top 50 most differentially regulated genes presented as normalised Log₂ fold change in WT (A), *als3Δ/Δ* (B) and *ece1Δ/Δ* (C) single and dual-species biofilms at 24 h.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Gene interaction networks created using ClueGO. Figure 5.11 shows binding of *S. aureus* to *C. albicans* hyphae within a 24h biofilm induces the upregulation of genes of related function. Genes are grouped by function, taking into account their gene ontology (GO). When binding to WT *C. albicans*, likely via Als3, *S. aureus* stimulates the increased expression of several genes divided into two distinct groups linked by ATPase activity genes which are classified by all three GO terms; molecular functions (Vos et al.), cellular components (CC) and biological processes (BP). Genes in the larger network are involved in fungal virulence and biofilm formation. These genes are classified by functions such as fungal cell wall, biofilm matrix and peptide binding ($P < 0.05$). Deletion of *ALS3* and *ECE1* have noticeable effects on gene expression triggered by *S. aureus*. As mentioned above, when *S. aureus* is unable to adhere to Als3, this results in a vastly different gene expression profile. This results in division of genes into 4 unrelated groups (Figure 5.11B). Despite a high number upregulated genes specific to the dual-species *als3Δ/Δ* biofilm, only 5 gene nodes reached statistical significance ($P < 0.05$). Genes composing these significant nodes are implicated in cellular metabolism, protein folding and plasma membrane components. Although still capable of expressing Als3, the dual species biofilm of *ece1Δ/Δ* and *S. aureus* displayed a notably different gene network (Figure 5.11C). Many of the genes implicated in these networks are shared between WT and *als3Δ/Δ* *C. albicans* or are associated with stress responses and protein folding and binding.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.11: *Staphylococcus aureus* induces significant upregulation of biofilm-associated genes when binding to Als3. Gene networks show interactions between upregulated genes specific to WT (A), *ALS3* (B) and *ECE1* null mutants (C) dual-species biofilms. Genes of similar function are grouped together to form nodes (circles) and nodes with similar functions are linked by edges (lines). Nodes are coloured by levels of significance and node size increases with the number of genes involved in each function. Networks were created using ClueGO.

As previously mentioned, a core response of *C. albicans* to the binding of *S. aureus* was detected. These genes were highly upregulated in WT *C. albicans* (all over Log_2 fold change of 2). Genes involved in this response were virulence and biofilm genes such as *ACE2*, *HSP70* and *HSP104* (Figure 5.12A). An interesting response from *als3Δ/Δ* was the increased expression of genes that are typically upregulated in response to external stressors. Some of the genes with the highest increased expression were *IFD6*, *HAK1*, *MDR1* and *CDR4* with a Log_2 fold increase of 4.6, 5.5, 3.6 and 4.4, respectively (Figure 5.12B). As seen in Figure 9, a limited response was seen from *C. albicans ece1Δ/Δ* cells. One of the few genes specific to this strain was *HSP21* (Figure 5.12C). Despite reported loss of virulence following deletion of *ECE1*, there is still upregulation of key virulence genes such as *ACE2* and *HSP21*.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 5.12: Identification of key genes with increased expression in dual-species biofilms. Log₂ fold change of key genes in 24 h dual-species biofilms of WT (A), *als3Δ/Δ* (B) and *ece1Δ/Δ* (C) *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*.

5.5 Discussion

The presence of polymicrobial biofilms during infection affects patient outcome due to decreased susceptibility to antimicrobial treatments and increased duration of hospital stays (Sancho et al., 2012). With understandings of interactions between fungi and bacteria improving, polymicrobial biofilms are being identified in increasing numbers during infection. Of these inter-kingdom biofilms, *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* are frequently co-isolated (Tsui et al., 2016). We now have a better understanding of the mechanisms by which these interactions benefit *S. aureus*. However, what remains unclear is how this relationship affects *C. albicans*. Gaining insights into how these organisms interact is crucial in developing novel, more effective treatments. Therefore, the work carried out herein aimed to characterise the relationship between these two nosocomial pathogens and define the transcriptome of *C. albicans* while in a dual-species biofilm with *S. aureus*. It was hypothesised, based on previous studies (Peters et al., 2012b), that *C. albicans* plays a central role in inter-kingdom biofilm development. To test this, bacteria that are poor or deficient biofilm formers (Beenken et al., 2003) were used. In agreement with previous findings (Kean et al., 2017), *C. albicans* was able to positively influence the biofilm formation of *S. aureus* bacteria within the biofilm. This increase in biofilm formation was largely achieved through the *C. albicans* hyphae acting as a substrate for the bacteria, a term referred to as a mycofilm (Kean et al., 2017). This agrees with previous theories that *C. albicans* germ tube formation is key in initiating the formation of polymicrobial biofilms (Harriott and Noverr, 2009).

The adhesion protein Als3 is highly expressed throughout all stages of *Candida* biofilm growth (Sherry et al., 2014). Peters et al. (2012b) showed that *S. aureus* binding to *C. albicans* hyphae was completely abolished using an *ALS3* knockout *Candida*. Contrary to this, it was found that *S. aureus* is still able to adhere to the fungal hyphae. This is likely due to expression of alternate proteins of the *als* family as *ALS1*, *ALS3* and *ALS5* have all been shown to be involved in biofilm formation and also bind *Streptococcus gordonii* (Hoyer et al., 2014, Klotz et al., 2007b, Roubarmohammadi et al., 2016, Sherry et al., 2014). The use of the biofilm deficient Newman's strain of *S. aureus* proves that it does not require the full arsenal of biofilm related genes as *C. albicans* hyphae can provide an

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

appropriate substrate for this process. Although bacterial binding was not eradicated, deletion of *ALS3* was found to significantly alter the binding pattern of *S. aureus* along with inducing considerable transcriptional changes in *C. albicans*. Interestingly, increased expression of over 100 highly interconnected genes involved in BPs such as response to drugs and cellular response to stress. Despite dual-species *als3Δ/Δ* biofilms sharing several genes with WT, there was little cross over concerning enriched GO terms in gene networks. This suggests that even though similar genes are upregulated in each strain, deletion of *ALS3* significantly alters how *C. albicans* interacts with and responds to *S. aureus* binding. Among the genes up regulated were *CDR4*, *MDR1* and *CAP1*. Although there is no confirmed role for *cdr4*, it is upregulated in the *C. albicans* core stress response (Enjalbert et al., 2006). Similar to *CDR1*, *CDR4* belongs to the ABC superfamily of efflux pumps, which can lead to speculation that the protein encoded by *cdr4* is also involved in drug resistance. *MDR1* and *CAP1* are also induced by external stressors such as antifungal drugs and oxidative stress, respectively (Feng et al., 2018). Therefore, it can be deduced that when *S. aureus* binds to adhesion proteins other than *Als3*, *C. albicans* perceives the bacterium as hostile and in turn this triggers several stress response pathways.

Ece1 is a recently characterised virulence gene in *C. albicans* responsible for the production of the first characterised cytolytic enzyme in this species (Moyes et al., 2016). This cytolytic protein was termed candidalysin and is typically found in the *C. albicans* cytoplasm or in cell secretions. The production of this protein is required for *C. albicans* to effectively damage epithelial cell membranes and trigger a downstream immune response. As this gene is involved in fungal virulence, it was not expected to influence Staphylococcal binding which was confirmed by exhibiting a similar binding profile to WT *Candida*. Based on these findings, it was hypothesised that no considerable differences in *C. albicans* transcription would be observed. However, there was considerably less differentially regulated genes in the *ECE1* null mutant than other strains. Although lacking the ability to elicit a proper immune response, *ece1Δ/Δ* is still capable of forming robust biofilms due to the significant up regulation of protein folding and binding genes as shown by the gene interaction networks above. These same cells may also prove to be more tolerant to external stimuli such as heat, which can be inferred from the significant upregulation of temperature response genes.

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

Comparisons between WT and *ece1* Δ/Δ single and dual-species biofilms revealed that mutant biofilms were lacking *PGA4*. This gene is required for proper cell wall biosynthesis whilst playing a minor role in regulating stress responses to antibiotics and oxidative stress (Ene et al., 2012). Expression of *pga4* is linked to expression of several other cell wall biosynthesis genes such as *CHT2*, *ECM331*, *BGL2* and *MP65*. Decreased expression of these genes likely results in improper integration of key virulence proteins. The observed attenuation of *C. albicans* virulence following deletion of *ECE1* can be attributed directly to a loss of candidalysin but also indirectly to differential construction of the cell wall resulting in poor integration of virulence factors. Despite there being no morphological differences in dual-species biofilms containing *ece1* Δ/Δ *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* there are noticeable changes in the *C. albicans* transcriptome. Therefore, it can be presumed that *ECE1* plays an important role in proper development of the fungal cell wall whilst in a dual-species consortium.

From searching the literature, this is the first study reporting the transcriptional changes in *C. albicans* following bacterial adhesion. It has been shown that adhesion of *S. aureus* to fungal hyphae increases drug tolerance and virulence for both species (Kean et al., 2017). Here it is shown that binding of *S. aureus* to WT *C. albicans* induces upregulation of several genes whose functions are all closely related in order to drive biofilm formation and fungal virulence which are associated with CC and MF such as hyphal cell wall and *HSP90* protein binding. Genes involved in these GO terms include *ACE2*, *HSP90*, *HSP104* and *FGR41*. *HSP90* is the most commonly studied heat shock protein in *C. albicans*. This is because of its involvement as a transcription factor in several virulence pathways such as biofilm formation, hyphal morphogenesis and virulence (O'Meara et al., 2017). Other genes such as *HSP104* and *ACE2* are also required for proper hyphal formation and virulence (Kelly et al., 2004, Fiori et al., 2012). Therefore, it can be deduced that the increased virulence of *C. albicans* that is observed within a dual-species inoculum with *S. aureus* is a result of upregulation of genes such as these.

Transcriptomics can be an extremely useful tool to give a snapshot of how cells are behaving at a certain point in time. However to gain a more detailed understanding of how this changes over time requires multiple samples which can

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

significantly increase costs. Although limited amounts of differential gene expression occurred after 4 h of incubation, this is not to say that *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* do not interact during early stages of biofilm formation. *S. aureus* has been shown to adhere to *C. albicans* after just 90 min of incubation together (Kean et al., 2017). This initial adhesion may induce large amounts of up or downregulation of *C. albicans* genes. Incorporating even earlier time points into this experiment could capture the immediate affect *S. aureus* has on the *C. albicans* transcriptome, which would help create a more accurate timeline of how gene expression changes within dual-species biofilms. Even though *ECE1* is a hyphal and biofilm specific gene, its main function is as a secreted protein (Moyes et al., 2016). Therefore, there may be other proteins found on the cell surface of *C. albicans*, which could more directly influence bacterial binding such as *HWP1*, and other members of the *als* adhesin family. The inclusion of additional knockout mutants of *C. albicans* would give an even better understanding of how this fungal pathogen interacts with *S. aureus* within polymicrobial biofilms. Transcriptomics can be a powerful tool in characterising the reaction of a population of cells to stimuli, however, levels of mRNA expression does not always directly correlate with protein expression (Liu et al., 2016). For that reason, analysis of the *C. albicans* proteome would provide sufficient data to provide more reliable and conclusive insights to cell behaviour and response that may not be deciphered by individual analyses.

Both *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* can be found in the lungs of patients suffering from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Su et al., 2015, Shimizu et al., 2015). Based on the high binding affinity these organisms have with one another the likelihood of them interacting *in vivo* is high. Despite their clinical significance in other respiratory diseases such as cystic fibrosis, fungi are somewhat ignored when studying the pathogenicity of conditions such as COPD. The data herein shows that bacteria found in the COPD lung is capable of inducing *C. albicans* to present a more virulent phenotype by driving the expression of genes associated with biofilm formation. As previously shown, *C. albicans* biofilms can behave as a substratum for bacterial biofilms and in turn protect these bacteria from antimicrobial therapies (Kean et al., 2017, Kong et al., 2016). Therefore, with increases in biofilm formation and antimicrobial tolerance, inter-kingdom interactions that take place within the respiratory tract may be responsible for

Modulation of the *Candida albicans* transcriptome by *Staphylococcus aureus*

persistent colonisation of bacterial pathogens that is associated with COPD. However, further analysis of the transcriptome of *C. albicans* while interacting with *S. aureus* and other bacteria is an important step in developing a more in depth understanding of the interactions between fungi and bacteria in the lung. This is integral in developing novel and more effective treatment regimens for COPD exacerbations.

5.6 Key findings

- *S. aureus* binds directly to *C. albicans*, preferentially via Als3
- *S. aureus* induces the upregulation of genes associated with virulence and biofilm formation
- When adhering to alternative adhesion proteins following deletion of *ALS3*, *S. aureus* induces the expression of stress response genes
- Ece1 does not impact staphylococcal binding but does alter the fungal transcriptome
- Bacteria can therefore create a more virulent fungal genotype which may translate to an increase in inflammation in the COPD lung

6 General Discussion

6.1 Introduction

The overarching aims of this thesis were to define and characterise the lung microbiome in COPD. The first aim was to define the COPD lung microbiome at the genus level and unveil its functionality using a meta-analysis of publicly available datasets. Results from this analysis were then used to inform the development of a multi-species biofilm model that can be used in the future to study members of the lung microbiome in a more relevant environment *in vitro*. Finally, the interactions within this biofilm model were interrogated using RNA-seq to determine mechanisms that could drive inflammation in COPD.

6.2 Identifying current and future trends in COPD microbiome research

The literature review, paired with bibliometric and ontology-based analyses in **Chapter 2** identified an increase in the popularity of the COPD microbiome as an area of research since its emergence in 2010. However, this also revealed that we are currently missing a key piece of the puzzle concerning functional analyses of the COPD microbiome, either as a whole or as individual inhabitants when compared to diseases such as CF or asthma. For example, in the field of CF microbiome research, there is much more interest regarding the functional profile of the lung microbiome, which was made evident by the number of mentions of terms such as ‘biofilm’ and ‘virulence’. This is likely due to the field of the COPD microbiome being in its infancy compared to that of CF so in years to come it is expected that this area will be addressed in COPD research. Despite being in its early stages, the lack of functional and *in vitro* analyses in the COPD microbiome is still somewhat surprising considering evidence in the literature pointing towards the microbiome playing a substantial role in the progression of COPD. Although not undeniably confirmed, there is strong evidence in the literature that indicates the presence of biofilms in the lungs of COPD patients. For instance, immune cell activity and microbial clearance mechanisms in the COPD lung are severely impaired, creating ideal conditions for the formation of biofilms. In patients with COPD, the same bacterial species have been isolated from the lungs over long periods, again leading us to suspect the presence of biofilms (Murphy et al., 2004).

6.3 Defining the microbiome in COPD and investigating its functionality

The analysis of **Chapter 3** in this thesis aimed to address some of the current limitations in the COPD microbiome literature by utilising *in silico* analyses to describe the lung microbiome in the COPD lung. This was achieved through the secondary analysis of publicly available microbiome datasets using a standardised pipeline. Analyses showed that there were no significant differences in microbiome diversity in COPD compared to health, there were sufficient compositional changes which allowed for accurate classification of lung microbiomes at the genus level. Key genera used in distinguishing healthy from COPD microbiomes included *Haemophilus*, *Moraxella*, *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Pseudomonas* and *Porphyromonas*. Key genera exhibited a functional profile involving virulence associated pathways such as two-component systems, bacterial secretion systems and biofilm formation. From this it can be concluded that the microbiome contributes, along with other factors, towards inflammation in the COPD lung.

Although there were no significant differences in microbiome diversity, when coloured by study, clustering of datapoints was clearer compared to all other variables. This suggests study-specific experimental design factors contribute to data outcomes. These findings suggest more standardised experimental design procedures should be followed when embarking on a COPD microbiome study. Doing so will help with effectively combining results to draw accurate conclusions surrounding the COPD microbiome. This standardisation could lead to the identification of the 'gold standard' study design for the COPD microbiome. Lastly and indirectly, **Chapter 3** shows that deposition of raw sequencing data following NGS studies, in particular microbiome studies should be more closely monitored to ensure it is done properly and to a standard that allows accurate secondary analysis.

Chapter 3 demonstrates the possibility of using the lung microbiome as a distinguishing feature to aid the diagnosis of COPD. This can be done using the microbiome as a whole or by using key genera identified through machine learning approaches. Success rates in correctly distinguishing a COPD microbiome from

that of a healthy patient being below 100%, the microbiome cannot be used single-handedly in COPD diagnosis. Pairing this with inherent difficulties in retrieving samples from the lungs such as the invasive techniques required to do so as well as the difficulty in removing contamination from the oral cavity, care must be taken when using the microbiome in diagnosis. However, with current difficulties in diagnosing COPD, recent advances in benchtop sequencing such as the Oxford Nanopore (<https://nanoporetech.com/>) could be used in future in tandem with traditional methods such as spirometry to aid in the diagnosis of COPD.

6.4 Antimicrobial therapies in COPD cannot remove multi-species consortia

Chapter 4 sought to develop a multi-species biofilm model informed by the results of **Chapter 3**. This biofilm model included *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Porphyromonas gingivalis*. *C. albicans*, which has previously been dubbed as a ‘keystone commensal’ due to its ability to readily interact with bacteria (Janus et al., 2016) proved instrumental in the formation of robust, multi-species biofilms by acting as a scaffold for both bacteria to adhere to. This confirmed previous findings that both bacteria possess a high binding affinity for *C. albicans* Als3. The adherence of bacteria to *C. albicans* hyphae has also been shown to increase virulence and antimicrobial tolerance. This was confirmed by multi-species biofilms exhibiting increased tolerance to individual and combination therapies between antibiotics and antifungals. This can be attributed to the presence of *C. albicans*. The *C. albicans* biofilm matrix has been implicated in the protection of bacteria and itself from antimicrobial therapies (Kong et al., 2016). The binding of both *S. aureus* and *P. gingivalis* to *C. albicans* has been reported to increase bacterial virulence through the production of toxins and secretion systems (Todd et al., 2019, Sztukowska et al., 2018). Using cell-free supernatants an increase in the ability of the biofilm to elicit an immune response in epithelial cells was documented. This immune response was exacerbated by antimicrobial therapy.

Although these findings indicate that current antimicrobials used in the management of COPD are not sufficient to effectively clear multi-species biofilms from the lungs, even in combination. Future *in vitro* studies should aim to test

more effective antimicrobial delivery methods in order to effectively disrupt and remove biofilm cells from the lung which will ultimately reduce levels of inflammation. Novel treatment methods which have shown positive results in the treatment of biofilm infections have been quorum sensing molecules which can negatively impact fungal biofilms (Bandara et al., 2020). Other promising results have come from repurposing current drugs which display antifungal properties (Vila and Lopez-Ribot, 2017, Abduljalil et al., 2022). With recent studies showing novel anti-*Candida* treatment options this may prove promising in the removal of interkingdom biofilms, of which *C. albicans* is a keystone member.

As shown in the previous chapter, the lungs are home to a plethora of bacteria and previous studies have shown a wide range of fungi also inhabit the COPD lungs (Tiew et al., 2020, Su et al., 2015). To more accurately model the lung microbiome *in vitro*, the use of 'real-world' biofilms should be pursued. This has been reported previously in the context of modelling oral diseases by taking saliva samples from donors to model oral diseases (Kolderman et al., 2015, Nance et al., 2013). This same approach could be taken in COPD using sputum as a starting culture. Doing so can allow for biofilm conditions to be manipulated to monitor the composition of the established biofilm through PCR or benchtop sequencing methods such as the Oxford Nanopore. Doing so would allow for more detailed and accurate modelling of the microbiome *in vitro* which would in turn help clarify how the microbiome responds to stimuli observed in COPD and how this response can alter disease progression.

6.5 Fungi aid in driving inflammation in the COPD lung

Concluding remarks from **Chapter 4** stated that multi-species biofilms containing organisms found in the COPD microbiome increase production of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-8. Therefore, **Chapter 5** aimed to identify possible mechanisms behind this finding with a focus on fungi. To achieve this, the transcriptome of *C. albicans* was characterised in both the presence and absence of both bacteria in the biofilm model. When grown in the presence of *P. gingivalis*, the transcriptome of *C. albicans* was largely unaffected. These findings indicate a commensal relationship between *C. albicans* and *P. gingivalis* as previous studies have shown the bacteria benefit from this interaction but based on transcriptomic analysis, *C. albicans* is unaffected. This is a light contrast to the

synergistic relationship between *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*. Interactions between these organisms has been extensively studied in previous years but has always done so from the bacteria's point of view. This was the first report of the *C. albicans* transcriptome when grown with *S. aureus* and it was found that that had a large impact on the fungal transcriptome, causing the upregulation of virulence-associated genes. Notably, the binding of *S. aureus* to *C. albicans* induced the increased expression of *ACE2*, *HSP90*, *HSP104* and *FGR41*. All of which are key adhesion and virulence genes with *HSP90* being one of the most extensively studied virulence-associated genes and plays a crucial role in biofilm formation (O'Meara et al., 2017, Kelly et al., 2004, Fiori et al., 2012, Lan et al., 2017).

In addition, the role of the recently characterised virulence factor Ece1 in staphylococcal interactions was investigated along with the key adhesin Als3. Although *S. aureus* preferentially binds to Als3 and following its deletion, the way in which *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* interact is significantly altered which is reflected in its transcriptome. When unable to bind to Als3, *S. aureus* induces the upregulation of stress response genes such as *CDR4* and *MDR1*. Deletion of *ECE1* also affects the fungal response to *S. aureus*, likely through different architecture of the cell wall, indicating an indirect role in these interkingdom interactions. However, the *ALS3* gene is highly expressed at both early and late stages of biofilm formation in clinical isolates. Meaning that these virulence pathways are likely upregulated in the lungs of COPD patients where *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* are both present, providing mechanisms by which the lung microbiome may drive the inflammation that is characteristic of COPD.

Findings from **Chapter 5** reveal mechanisms by which *C. albicans* can drive lung inflammation in COPD via direct interactions with *S. aureus*. However, future analyses can build upon these findings using metatranscriptomics. Despite being in its early stages, this is a promising technique which can provide insight into 'the big picture' regarding how microbes in the lung are behaving rather than merely reporting on what is present. Metatranscriptomics can not only build upon these findings but also those of **Chapter 3** by revealing more detailed annotation of the current state of the microbiome compared to reporting on the most commonly associated metabolic pathways that are associated with key OTUs.

6.6 Future work

Although the work presented in this thesis gives an in-depth description of the composition and functionality of the ‘typical’ microbiome in COPD and its inhabitants it also highlights current caveats in our knowledge in this field. These caveats lie particularly in the area of ‘what are they doing?’ rather than ‘what is there?’. Findings reported in **Chapters 3 and 5** begin to elucidate this but additional studies are required. Studies focusing on the metatranscriptome of the microbiome will aid in furthering our understanding of its role in COPD progression. Another avenue to explore is utilising *in vitro* studies, much like in the field of CF, to build upon our understanding of the contributions of individual organisms.

6.7 Concluding remarks

In conclusion, the overarching aims of this thesis were to investigate the role of the microbiome in COPD. This was achieved by utilising a large-scale meta-analysis of the COPD microbiome to inform the development of a multi-species biofilm model that can be used to study COPD microbiome constituents *in vitro*. Although COPD is a highly heterogeneous disease, clear trends were identified in microbiome dynamics between health and disease. It is important to note that although the use of antibiotics in COPD therapies is encouraged in certain cases, the rates of long-term colonisation and frequent exacerbations remains high. Therefore, more effective anti-biofilm therapies should be more regularly employed in patients where long-term bacterial colonisation is reported.

Strengths and weakness for this thesis are outlined below:

Strengths:

- Provides accurate profile of the ‘typical’ microbiome in COPD and how it differs from health which was achieved through a standardised bioinformatics analysis pipeline which addresses limitations in previous COPD microbiome studies.
- First report of modelling organisms commonly found in the COPD lungs *in vitro*

- First report of the effect that *S. aureus* has on the transcriptome of *C. albicans*, elucidating mechanisms behind the increased virulence observed when both organisms are isolated from the same site.

Weaknesses:

- Organisms selected for the modelling of the COPD microbiome could be changed to represent a more pathogenic biofilm containing traditional respiratory pathogens such as *Haemophilus influenzae* or *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.
- In addition to the point above, the development of a 3-species biofilm model still struggles to capture the complexity of the microbe-microbe interactions that take place within the lungs of COPD patients. Therefore, a biofilm model containing additional organisms would have been more accurate.
- Although Chapter 5 was the first report of the *C. albicans* transcriptome, analysis focused on the genes which were upregulated. Further analysis should address downregulated genes to understand fully, the effect that *S. aureus* has on the *C. albicans* transcriptome.

The key findings of this thesis are outlined below:

- Our knowledge of the role of the microbiome in COPD is currently limited by our lack of understanding surrounding the functionality of the microbiome and how its constituents interact
- The diversity of the lung microbiome is not significantly dissimilar to that of healthy individuals
- The lung microbiome in COPD is dominated and best defined by bacteria genera typically associated with the oral cavity
- Current antimicrobials used in the management of COPD are not effective in the removal of established multi-species biofilms. This poor anti-biofilm effect can then lead to increased inflammation in the lungs and repeat infections in the future
- Direct, interkingdom interactions may play a key role in driving inflammation whereby bacteria induce the upregulation of fungal genes involved in virulence and biofilm formation

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